

Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals

DISCUSSING WAYS OF IMPLEMENTING COARA
COMMITMENTS 1, 2 AND 3 IN RESEARCH FUNDING
CRITERIA, PROCEDURES AND CULTURE

COARA WORKING GROUP “IMPROVING PRACTICES IN THE
ASSESSMENT OF RESEARCH PROPOSALS”

May 2026

Dedicated to the memory of Jean-Emmanuel Faure

Contents

Detailed Contents	4
List of Acronyms	8
Summary	10
1. Introduction	11
2. Fostering the diversity of research contributions, activities and careers - Ways of implementing CoARA commitment 1 in assessment criteria and processes	14
3. Optimizing qualitative review - Ways of implementing CoARA commitments 2 and 3 in assessment procedures.....	62
References	86
Organisations affiliated to this WG	88
Working Group Overview	91
Annexes.....	93

Detailed Contents

List of Acronyms.....	8
Summary	10
1. Introduction	11
2. Fostering the diversity of research contributions, activities and careers - Ways of implementing CoARA commitment 1 in assessment criteria and processes	14
2.1 Designing grant types, call foci and competition spaces to allow for diverse projects	14
2.2 Improving the clarity in criteria and processes.....	22
2.3 Diversifying the pool of reviewers	25
2.4 Providing dedicated space in CVs for displaying a broader variety of research outputs, activities and career trajectories.....	28
2.5 Balancing the qualification of the applicant and the quality of the research idea	36
2.6 Countering “mainstream bias” in assessment procedures	40
2.7 Consideration for sex, gender and diversity in the composition of research teams and in the scientific content of the projects to promote quality.....	45
2.8 Incentivising open science practices	51
2.9 Recognizing diverse or non-linear career paths	58
3. Optimizing qualitative review - Ways of implementing CoARA commitments 2 and 3 in assessment procedures.....	62
3.1 Before the review - Demand management	62
3.2 The selection of and guidance to reviewers.....	64
3.2.1 Prerequisites for identifying appropriate reviewers	64
3.2.2 Guiding principles for the selection of appropriate reviewers and panels of balanced composition	64
3.2.3 Guidance and training to reviewers and panels - format and content.....	66
3.3 The external written review.....	69
3.3.1 Putting external reviewers in touch with each other.....	69
3.3.2 Optimizing the form and submission procedures for reviews	71
3.3.3 Making the best use of rapporteurs and RFO officers in the processing of reviews.....	72
3.4 Discussing proposals - the panel or board meeting	74
3.4.1 The panel or board discussion and its structure	74

3.4.2 Recognizing the role of the board or panel chair(s).....	79
3.4.3 Discussing individual project budgets.....	80
3.4.4 Information management during the review and panel discussion	81
3.4.5 Concluding the discussion(s): Coming to a funding decision.....	82
3.5 After the review	84
3.5.1 Formulating decisions.....	84
3.5.2 Recognizing, rewarding and debriefing reviewers.....	85
References	86
Organisations affiliated to this WG	88
Working Group Overview	91
Annexes.....	93
Survey 1. The understanding and operationalisation of “research quality”	93
S 1.1 Introduction and method.....	93
S 1.2 Main findings.....	94
S 1.3 Further detailed results of the survey	106
Survey 2. Selection of reviewers and panel composition (survey result).....	111
S 2.1 Guiding principles for the selection of reviewers and panel composition that support quality and diversity of selected projects (q 19)	111
S 2.2 Practices in relation to mentoring and training of reviewers on responsible assessment (q 23, q 31 and q 32).....	113
S 2.3 Further Survey Results	116
S 2.4 Survey Questionnaire	117
Survey 3. The information requested from applicants.....	121
S 3.1 Introduction	121
S 3.2 Survey findings.....	122
S 3.3 Survey questionnaire	129
Other initiatives and projects.....	133
Literature on research assessment and reform activities	135

Document Information

Output Title	Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals – Discussing Ways of Implementing CoARA Commitments 1, 2 and 3 in Research Funding Criteria, Procedures and Culture
Working Group	Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals
Topic	Research assessment in research funding organisations (RFO)
Draft Version	4 (endorsed by CoARA Steering Board)
Publication Date	29 May 2026
Output Type	Actionable policy resource
Producer(s)	CoARA WG Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals
Project Leader(s)	In alphabetical order : Anna Christa, Yvonne Fors, Matthias Kiesselbach, Matteo Marengo, Cristina Martinez
Editor(s)	In alphabetical order : Anna Christa, Yvonne Fors, Matthias Kiesselbach, Matteo Marengo, Cristina Martinez
Reviewer(s)	WG members, public consultation, CoARA Steering Board
Status	Final

Please cite as:

CoARA WG Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals. (2026). CoARA Output. Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals – Discussing Ways of Implementing CoARA Commitments 1, 2 and 3 in Research Funding Criteria, Procedures and Culture. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17977045>

Revision history			
Version	Date	Revised by	Comments
Version 4	29 May 2026		Endorsed by CoARA Steering Board without revisions
Version 3	17 April 2026	Matthias Kiesselbach, Anna Christa, Matteo Marengo, Yvonne Fors	Final version after community consultation, submitted to SB for endorsement procedure
Version 2	19 Dec 2025	Matthias Kiesselbach, Anna Christa, Matteo Marengo, Yvonne Fors	Pre-endorsement draft published for community consultation
Version 1	18 Dec 2025	IPARP WG	Pre-endorsement draft

Acknowledgements:

We would like to thank Monica Schofield, Victoria Abakumovski, Ida Retter, Robert Nuske, Jan-Erik Refle, Michael Louis Moser, Zuzanna Gorenstein and others for their feedback during the public consultation.

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial intelligence
AKA / RCF	Research Council of Finland
ANR	French National Research Agency
ARRA	Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment
AvH	Alexander von Humboldt Foundation (Germany)
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DFG	German Research Foundation
DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
EDI	Equity, diversity, inclusion
ERC	European Research Council
ESF	European Science Foundation
FCT	Foundation for Science and Technology (Portugal)
FNR	Luxembourg National Research Fund
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
FWO	Research Foundation Flanders
HRB	Health Research Board (Ireland)
HUN-REN	Hungarian Research Network
INCa	Institut National du Cancer - French National Cancer Institute
KKS	Knowledge Foundation
NHMRC	National Health and Medical Research Council (Australia)
NIH	National Institutes of Health (USA)
NSE	Natural Sciences and Engineering
NSERC	National Sciences and Engineering Research Council (Canada)
NWO	Dutch Research Council
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
PI	Principal investigator

RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RoRI	Research on Research Institute
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
ZonMw	Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development

Summary

The CoARA Working Group “Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals” (2023-2025) provides strategic guidance for research funding organisations seeking to align their assessment practices with CoARA commitments, in particular commitment 1 (recognize diverse contributions to research), commitment 2 (base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation), and commitment 3 (abandon inappropriate uses of journal- and metric-based evaluation).

Recognizing the complexity and diversity of funding systems, the Working Group does not propose uniform solutions. Instead, it offers a structured set of considerations, questions, and a rich collection of current and emerging practice examples from various funders that can inform context-specific reform processes across different organisational settings.

Emerging from the report, the following core ideas serve as a framework for navigating the reform process:

Overall premise

As a funder, be as explicit and self-reflective as possible in all your decisions regarding research assessment

Fostering the diversity of research contributions, activities, and careers

<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div>Encourage applicants, wherever appropriate, to reflect on sex, gender and other diversity dimensions in the project design (scientific content)</div> </div>	
---	--

Optimizing qualitative review

<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <div>In your feedback to applicants, give reasons for the decision and show your commitment to responsible research assessment</div> </div>	
--	---

1. Introduction

You are holding in your hands - or reading on your screen - the report and discussion paper of the CoARA Working Group (WG) "Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals". In this WG, research funding organisations (RFOs) and organisations representing the research community from across the world came together between early 2023 and late 2025 to discuss ways of better aligning RFO assessment practices with the CoARA commitments (Arentoft, et al., 2022).¹ The results of the discussions within the WG - this text - can be thought of as both a technical guide and a source of ideas.

This document primarily addresses RFOs - at both executive and officer level - who recognize the importance of research assessment reform along the lines of the CoARA, and who seek inspiration regarding changes to their assessment processes and practices. It assumes familiarity with research funding, and a willingness to look at research funding from different perspectives, including those of administrators, policy makers, research institutions and the research community at large. Members of the latter groups may also find this document interesting. This may be particularly true for researchers. After all, it is the assessment of their project proposals which is the subject of the WG's discussions and hence of this text.

This guide is quite substantial, because it deals with a complex subject matter.

The journey of a research proposal comprises many stages between its submission and the decision, and interventions into the RFO practices are conceivable at each stage. Such interventions, moreover, typically have repercussions elsewhere, which must be understood and carefully considered.

Furthermore, not all RFOs are the same. Some of the RFOs represented in the WG cover the whole spectrum of science, others focus on specific disciplines; some are mission- or call driven, others are organized as bottom-up funders; some fund basic research, others applied research; some focus exclusively on academic research, others encourage partnerships with industry, government or society; some are privately funded, others receive funding from the government. Funders have vastly different histories, legal or regulatory environments, internal workings, outside expectations and missions, and all of this can impact their reform trajectories.

Finally, it became clear during the WG's discussion that there is no dearth of examples of novel and piloted practices and interventions among member organisations, and thus an equally rich body of experience to draw on. As there are almost always interesting differences in nuance - reflecting the diversity of funding organisations - the WG decided to include close to all examples to fully capture this richness.

¹ In this document, "CoARA commitments" refers to the commitments laid down in the *Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment*, the principal document behind the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

In view of the complexity, some of the material in this document does not take the form of recommendations but rather of questions, topics or examples which RFOs are invited to consider, each with an accompanying technical discussion, and many with practical examples of already existing practices or pilots. The members of the WG hope that the careful and dedicated reader will find in this guide many useful ideas to be adopted, perhaps in modified form, in their own respective organisation.

While the document is not aimed at convincing its readers of the importance of research assessment reform or of the specific CoARA commitments - that has been done elsewhere - the text may yet contribute to giving shape to the meaning of "research assessment reform". In this sense, it can also contribute to the normative discussion surrounding it. One of the points which the discussion laid down in this document clearly underscores is that for the RFOs assembled in the WG, research assessment reform is not about supplanting or dissolving the focus on *research excellence*. On the contrary: the primary goal of research assessment reform is to ensure that high-quality research is properly recognized, in the dual senses of avoiding false positives and of avoiding false negatives. Of course, this formulation is meant to cover the *ex ante* assessment settings typical of RFOs, in which the focus of assessment is the *likelihood* that high-quality research *will* take place.

One important topic which is not systematically addressed in this document is that of artificial intelligence. There are two reasons. Firstly, addressing A.I. in the context of research assessment and its reform would require a separate comprehensive treatment. Secondly, other fora and working groups, for example the CoARA WG "Ethics & Research Integrity Policy (ERIP) in Responsible Research Assessment for Data and Artificial Intelligence" or the Science Europe Working Group on A.I., have set themselves the task to deliver such a treatment.

One word about the structure of the document. The following chapter 2 focuses on the first of CoARA's commitments - *to recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research*. It is organized in 9 sections, roughly following the order in which RFOs process proposals, which were deemed particularly important and fruitful in a series of WG workshops.

Chapter 3 then focuses on CoARA's second and third commitments - *to base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central (...)* and *to abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics*. This chapter closely follows all major steps in the RFO work cycle, starting well before the proposal submission and going well beyond the funding decision. This chapter is the outcome of a number of in-person and online meetings.

The Annex comprises comprehensive empirical material. It contains three surveys, one on the understanding and operationalization of "research quality" among RFOs, one on how RFOs select and guide reviewers, and one about what information RFOs request from their applicants. The chapter also addresses envisaged or already piloted changes under these three headings. The results - themselves complex - give a detailed picture both of how RFOs currently (around 2024 and 2025) operate and about which changes are on the way.

The WG recognizes that the discussions on research assessment reform are sure to continue - for instance within the DORA Funder Discussion Group, who have recently published a Practical Guide for Funders which covers some of the topics of this document, too (DORA, 2026) - and that concerning a number of aspects, more research on research is needed. At the same time, it hopes that the document you are holding in your hands - or reading on your screen - is a useful contribution to the reform, tuned to its current stage.

2. Fostering the diversity of research contributions, activities and careers – Ways of implementing CoARA commitment 1 in assessment criteria and processes

CoARA commitment 1 deals with the recognition of a broad variety of types of scientific contribution and of careers as a key aspect of a more responsible mode of research assessment. In its discussions, the Working Group decided on a broad reading of the commitment, the spirit of which also includes *scientific activities*. These can include coding research software, curating data, developing research infrastructures or knowledge valorisation. In short, the commitment calls for a holistic mode of research assessment, taking into account all relevant products, careers and activities which are of potential scientific value - of course including, but going well beyond the production of journal publications as the conclusion of research. This chapter focuses on ways of better aligning the practices of research funders with CoARA commitment 1.

2.1 Designing grant types, call foci and competition spaces to allow for diverse projects

RFOs are particularly well placed to help develop the research system to better reflect CoARA commitment 1. When assessing the expertise of a researcher, which is usually an important part in the evaluation of a research proposal, they should consider a broad range of previous scientific contributions, practices and activities. However, this is only one aspect of RFOs' role in furthering CoARA's first commitment. In order to increase researchers' confidence to invest their time into the kinds of activities which they deem maximally valuable for science, RFOs can - besides *recognizing* diverse past activities - also take steps to *foster* a diversity of contributions, practices and activities in the projects which they fund going forward.²

This section discusses three areas within which RFO may consider programme-related changes to foster a diversity of projects: deciding on foci of calls and programmes,

² The CoARA WG has discussed the question of the appropriate reading of commitment 1 at length and tentatively holds that the commitment should be read in a broad way, encompassing besides the *recognition* of diverse contributions, careers and activities also the *fostering* of the same. Such a reading, in the WG's opinion, coheres better with the plausible goals of assessment reform.

designing grant types (or modes, or vehicles), and structuring competition spaces. In a fourth sub-section, it discusses other areas of action – the exact formulation of criteria, and monitoring of decisions – aiming to foster a broader diversity of projects.

Foci of calls and programmes

Both standing programmes and discrete calls target specific ranges of projects, with specific degrees of inbuilt flexibility. Among other things, they are instituted to address particular scientific needs or to allow particular kinds of research projects to be carried out. However, science develops rapidly, and it is a live possibility that after some time, a funder's programme portfolio no longer covers the needs of science and academia optimally, or that a programme or series of calls may have outlived the original purpose for its institution.

Funders are advised to periodically evaluate these questions systematically and to assess the effectiveness of their funding instruments. One way of doing this is to draft, ideally with relevant stakeholders, a list of types of projects deemed scientifically valuable, and to check whether for each of them, a specialized funding programme, or room in a general funding programme, exists. The list could include project types like the following: replication studies, methodological projects, projects aiming for surveys or meta-surveys as their principal output, projects targeting the development of (research) infrastructure, highly experimental and data-driven projects, highly theoretical projects, projects necessitating longer durations, projects of particular scientific risk, projects which accompany clinical, ecological, managerial, policy or other real-world interventions, projects requiring inter- or transdisciplinary collaboration (perhaps of specific sorts, e.g. inclusion of data or computer science or particular community actors) and many others. Of course, for different scientific areas, different such types will come to mind.

Even where it is theoretically possible to apply for funding for a given project, there may be barriers in the specificity of the grant type and/or due to the structure of the competition spaces. The following sub-sections discuss these interdependent topics.

Grant types (modes, modules)

The grant types (or funding modes, funding modules) which a funder offers have a strong and sometimes unexamined effect on the kinds of projects, and consequently work modes and project outputs, which are planned and submitted as proposals, and end up being funded.

Questions which funders interested in allowing a maximum diversity of projects may address include: do the allowable cost types cover a sufficiently broad range of staff (besides researchers and research assistants, for example administrative staff for complex projects, software engineers for projects with coding needs, interpreters for projects in which translation is needed etc.), services (for instance, data science services, general or specialized legal services, translation, accessibility, open access (OA) publication) or goods (for example, non-standard equipment for replication studies, specialized computers, means for accessibility), are there different possible project durations, or sufficiently flexible durations? Have funders optimized the degree of flexibility within the regulative framework

in which they operate (e.g. might it be possible to increase the level of generality for funding items, simplify accounting rules, simplify project extensions)?

Competition spaces

When designing their funding portfolios, one of the principal design decisions of funders concerns the structure of their competition spaces. In the standard case, competition spaces are congruent with funding programmes or calls. If, for example, a funder introduces a programme or issues a call for coordinated projects in clinical research, then a natural arrangement would be for all proposals received in this programme or against this call within a given period to compete with one another.

However, competition spaces can be designed differently. One possibility is that they can be more fine-grained: within a given programme or call, a funder can, for example, introduce separate competition spaces for applicants from different career stages. In this way, the funder can guarantee that applicants from all career stages are selected for funding, ensuring a particular kind of diversity - in the present case, a diversity of career stages - in the funding slate.

Depending on the financial and administrative organisation of a funder, competition spaces can also cut across funding lines. Here, too, they can be more or less fine-grained. Several funding programmes can simply share a singular competition space. Or this space is subdivided, for example - again - along the lines of different career stages. Once again, diversity is ensured, but this time not within each funding programme or call, but across programmes or calls.

Typically, a competition space is constituted by a separate budget and a corresponding grouping of proposals in the assessment, but there are ways of dividing competition spaces without separating budgets. Separate competition spaces are conceivable along different spectra and can be used to address various dimensions of CoARA's first commitment, e.g. diversity of profiles, practices and outputs, or several dimensions at the same time. They can be instituted, for example, for specific applicant groups (e.g. separate spaces for different career stages or various underrepresented groups), for specific types of collaborative work (e.g. specific numbers of collaborators, for specific types of disciplinary inclusion from mono- to transdisciplinary work), for projects of particular expected impact (e.g. separate spaces for applied research or for fundamental research), for projects of specific levels or risk (e.g. high risk, low risk), for reflective projects (e.g. for meta-research projects, overview projects), for projects of specific financial dimensions, and many more.

When tailoring competition spaces, funders are well-advised to keep an eye on secondary, communicative effects. A particular danger is a lowered reputation for protected programmes.

Supporting diversity of project-type without separate calls, programmes or competition spaces: reviewing criteria, and using monitoring for unbiased panel or board discussions

Of course, some funders may have good reasons to opt against narrowly targeted programmes and calls. And indeed, wider funding programmes or calls (up to all-purpose programmes and calls) allow a broader variety of different project ideas to enter the competition, including projects of unforeseen types. Here, too, funders can take steps to ensure that all of these projects have adequate chances of receiving funding. Two of them, one related to criteria, one focusing on the monitoring of decisions, will be discussed in what follows.

The first one is to design the review criteria with a diversity of project-types in view. Of course, there is no one-size-fits-all approach to this matter, as different funders employ different criteria sets matching their missions. Moreover, the review criteria lie at the heart of a funder's work and should not be changed lightly; particular care is needed to ensure that research excellence remains in the focus of assessment. However, funders can reflect critically whether the formulation, operationalization and order of their review criteria are such that all project-types which are considered potentially valuable have an appropriate chance of success. For example, is it sufficiently clear in the formulation and explanation of the review criteria that an "advance in knowledge" or "novelty" can include the strengthening of an existing theory's or common hypothesis's epistemic foundation? Might it be that scientific risk is framed in an overly positive way ("high risk, high gain"), thus disadvantaging projects with a lower risk but a higher potential for advances in knowledge? Can the operationalization of the feasibility criterion - it could be a yes/no criterion, it could share its scale with other criteria, it could come with its own scale, it could be asked at different stages - be optimized to give appropriate chances to projects where feasibility is of lesser or of particularly high concern?

Secondly, the monitoring of decisions can make funders aware of different project-types' relative success rates. While some such differences may be linked with different degrees of scientific quality, there is always the possibility of scientifically unjustified barriers and biases. There is some anecdotal evidence, for instance, that in some general funding programmes, certain project types including replication studies or reflective science (science on science) may be disadvantaged through implicit biases. In light of this possibility, funders may find it useful to screen their decisions - either by evaluation of past decisions, or in the form of real-time monitoring - by project types. With a carefully constructed (and periodically reviewed) matrix of relevant types, such data may give indication about previously undetected barriers for some kinds of project and can also be fed back to review boards or standing panels. Of course, a panel or board should not use this data to revise individual quality judgements. But the data may help uncover project-type related biases, and could influence discussions in cases of tied quality, particularly around the financial cut-off line (i.e. the boundary between fundable and not fundable proposals imposed by the available budget).

Of course, other kinds of monitoring may also help develop funding modules, and other aspects of the funding portfolio.

Practice Examples

NWO: Separate competition space for replication studies

As an example of a separate competition space for a specific type of research - realized in the form of discreet calls -, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and Open Science NL have piloted dedicated calls for replication studies. Three rounds of calls ran between 2016 and 2020 and a further call is being executed in 2025 by NWO together with Open Science NL. The programme was instituted in response to an expressed need by researchers who often found that their applications for replication studies were being rejected in other programmes, due to not deeming to meet the "innovation" criterion. With the fourth round in 2025, Open Science NL aims to take the next step in normalising replication research and increasing insights of the replicability of scholarly findings. Ultimately, the aim is to ensure that research proposals for replication studies have a stronger chance of success in other funding programmes.

NWO: Programmes for under-represented groups within the research community

Another example of a separate competition space, in this case specifically for an under-represented group of researchers, is the Dutch Research Council's (NWO's) 'Mosaic 2.0' promotional grant programme. This programme is aimed at first and second generation Dutch researchers with a non-Western migration background. By funding PhD positions, the goal of the programme is to stimulate the influx of this group of researchers into science. The programme has been well-received from both within and outside of the target group and can count on a broad support.

FWO: Designing competition spaces on the basis of career stage and scientific seniority

The Research Foundation - Flanders (FWO) designs competition spaces on the basis of career stage and scientific seniority in their programmes for postdoctoral fellowship and fundamental research projects. In the programme for postdoctoral fellowships a distinction is made between applicants applying for "junior" and "senior" fellowships. Junior applicants are maximum three years post-PhD; senior applicants are between three and six years post-PhD and have at least two years of postdoctoral research experience. The junior and senior calls are parallel to one another - i.e. they take place at the same time and are evaluated by the same panels, but they are two separate competitions. Junior applicants compete only with other junior applicants; senior applicants compete only with other senior applicants. This creates a competition space for each applicant group in which they are compared to researchers with a profile that is relatively similar in terms of career stage and scientific seniority. A similar system is in

place for the FWO programme on fundamental research projects, where a junior call is organized for applicant (teams) of researchers at most 12 years post-PhD; the senior call receives applications from researcher(s) who are more than 12 years post-PhD. The success rate for each of these calls is the same.

DFG: A unitary competition space with separate programmes - an example of specialized programmes for specific career stages

In the German Research Foundation's (DFG's) funding portfolio, the Individual Research Grants programme is the largest by volume and number of funded projects. Apart from a maximum duration of three years, it is highly flexible, catering to all sciences and the humanities, and allowing for all kinds of projects to run.

Generally, the Individual Research Grants programme can be used for most research purposes. Experience and discussions with research communities has shown, however, that dedicated programmes for applicants of certain career stages are beneficial for an adequate and fair review which properly addresses specificities of these applicants' career situations. While the Individual Research Grants programme remains open to all applicants who hold a PhD and work in a German research institute, the DFG has hence instituted the "Walter Benjamin-Programme" for persons who recently obtained their doctorate, the "Emmy Noether-Programme" for exceptionally qualified early-career researchers prepared to form their first lab or group, and the "Heisenberg Programme" for persons meeting the requirements for appointment to a permanent professorship. These programmes are instituted to support career development; relevant information is included in the communication with the reviewers.

The Benjamin, Noether and Heisenberg applications, however, are discussed in regular sessions of the respective disciplinary Review Board, competing with applications in other programmes, including the broad-based Individual Research Grants Programme outlined above. They are also financed from the same budget (with auxiliary support for the Noether programme from global funds). Reviewers and Review Boards, however, can and do give special consideration to the applicant's career stage and career-related secondary aims of the programme. If needed, DFG officers place reminders of the specificities of the programmes in the review and board discussion. Partly for these reasons, the Walter Benjamin Programme for early career researchers has a higher success rate than the Individual Research Grants programme.

FWF: Career development programmes

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) started a reform of the Career development programmes in 2018, which was concluded with the launch of the ASTRA Awards programme in 2024. Based on evaluations, facts and numbers, the FWF streamlined three programmes (a two stage women's only programme, an incoming programme and an advanced stage excellent award) with the aim to provide equal chances and conditions to all applicants at the same career stage. With ESPRIT (Early-Stage Program:

Research - Innovation - Training) and FWF ASTRA Awards (for advanced postdocs), the FWF now offers two programmes for early and advanced stage researcher (R2, R3) offering the best conditions for all PIs. Programme aims and evaluation criteria are in line with the career stages. Whereas both programmes aim at funding excellent, innovative research, recruiting, retaining, and winning back outstanding researchers to strengthen Austria's research institutions and supporting outstanding women researchers, the programmes differ in their goals regarding career development. ESPRIT (R2) strives to career and skill development in terms of development/establishment of an independent research profile; ASTRA instead aims to support the consolidation of the principal investigators' academic careers and the achievement of the qualifications needed for academic leadership positions, especially senior faculty position.

Research Ireland: Investigators Programme supporting research in STEM and AHSS disciplines

Taighde Éireann - Research Ireland is a new, competitive research and innovation funding agency in Ireland. The establishment of the agency was a key action of Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy. Research Ireland was established on 1st August 2024, following an amalgamation of Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) and the Irish Research Council (IRC).

In Summer 2025, Research Ireland launched a new flagship initiative, the Investigators Programme to support research and innovation in all disciplines and interdisciplinary projects, which is open to researchers at a broad range of career stages. The Programme, which will last four years, will fund excellent researchers to undertake cutting-edge research, create training and employment opportunities, increase Ireland's capacity and reputation for excellent research, support researchers in leveraging success in European and international funding programmes, retain and attract excellent research talent to Ireland, support collaborative research partnerships, and promote innovation in the Irish research system. The Investigator Programme, which will fund up to €625,000, will consider proposals from established and emerging, independent researchers in any discipline seeking to carry out excellent research that delivers on the objectives of the programme.

The review process will consist of an initial Expression of Interest stage, with the top ranked proposals then being invited to submit a full proposal. Applications at both stages will be reviewed by a 'virtual panel' comprised of international reviewers. A careful selection process ensures the best-possible alignment of panel members with each proposal under review. Applicants will have to choose whether they will be reviewed as part of an Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS) or Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) panel. As the virtual panels are generalist in nature reviewers will be experts only in the broad subject area of the proposals which have been assigned to them. Applicants are advised to consider this when writing their proposal.

NSERC: Guidelines on the assessment of contributions to research, training and mentoring

In the assessment of applications, the Natural Science and Engineering Research Council (NSERC) of Canada considers a variety of contributions ranging from publications, development of tools and software, dataset creation, patents and copyrights to engagement in citizen science, research communication to specialist or non-specialist audiences, and advancements in equity, diversity, inclusion and accessibility in the research ecosystem. Contributions are assessed against their quality and impact.

To assess quality, the following indicators are used (but are not limited to):

- Consideration of EDI in all aspects of the research process
- Novelty, creativity and/or innovation in the methodology and/or application of the research
- Responsible and ethical research conduct, including honest and thoughtful inquiry; commitment to safety, security and integrity; adherence to professional standards and alignment of research with the needs defined by the community
- Suitable and rigorous methodology (including, as applicable, the use of appropriate statistics and reproducibility)
- Transparency and accessibility of results and appropriate data stewardship (including, where appropriate, open science and/or Indigenous data management protocols such as OCAP^{®2})

To assess impact, the following indicators are used (but are not limited to):

- Acceptance and use of research results by stakeholders, including members of the research community, relevant partners, specific communities or others who may benefit from the research
- Advances to reconciliation and the decolonization of research
- Advances to state-of-the-art research or technology readiness level
- Contributions to economic development or to environmental or social innovations at the local, regional, national or international level(s)
- Increases to equitable and inclusive participation in the research ecosystem
- Increased public understanding of, use of and/or interest in certain aspects of the Natural Sciences and Engineering (NSE).
- Influence on current policy, guidelines, regulations, laws, standards and/or practice
- Influence on the direction of thought and/or activity in the community or targeted partners.

The guidelines also provide updated language about delays and interruptions to research and reflect recent EDI policy advances.

Sources: Natural Science and Engineering Research Council (NSERC) of Canada, Guidelines on the assessment of contributions to research, training and mentoring, 2024: https://www.nserc-crsng.gc.ca/NSERC-CRSNG/Policies-Politiques/assessment_of_contributions-evaluation_des_contributions_eng.asp#0

2.2 Improving the clarity in criteria and processes

In order to know how to structure and present their project proposals, applicants need to know what kinds of projects funders seek to fund, and how they evaluate the proposals submitted to them. This information is typically relayed to applicants in call texts or programme announcements and descriptions, as well as in generic statements about a funder's review criteria. However, applicants sometimes state that more explicit information would be welcome. In particular, applicants often express the wish that review criteria and procedures of review be described in more detail. Applicants also sometimes point out the absence – in the case of most funding agencies – of an explicit definition of scientific quality or excellence.³

Of course, funders may argue that increasing the level of detail is not always appropriate: a call text or programme description should not allow matters to appear more definite than they actually are. Particularly with respect to the review criteria, a degree of flexibility in interpreting review criteria may be intended, so that scientific reviewers can ensure that different kinds of proposal or project each have a sensible chance at a positive funding decision.⁴ To an extent, this may also be true for the review procedures: panels are sometimes given some procedural leeway, for example regarding the order in which proposals are discussed, or the time allotted to different classes of proposals, in order to flexibly deal with the particularities of a given cohort.

At the same time, it may well be that the level of detail with which a funder describes the review criteria and procedures is not optimal and can usefully be increased. This can also be the case with respect to the level of interpretive freedom reviewers are granted: the exact boundaries of this freedom could be fixed in writing.

Information provided to applicants can also address the wider aims (perhaps the political or societal aims) of a funding programme, and include examples of projects which the funder seeks to support. It can also include guidance about the intended structure of projects, i.e. information on the typical or appropriate number of P.I.s, sub-projects, the appropriate division of funds between different cost items and other such matters. In this connection, applicants may find it helpful to see examples – or even a full database – of previously funded projects in a given programme, or against previous issues of a call.

All information which can influence funding outcomes (even indirectly or subtly) should not only be made available to reviewers, but also to the authors of proposals to be reviewed.

³ The fact that most funders operate without definitions of scientific quality or excellence is a result of Science Europe's 2020 survey (Technopolis, 2020) as well as this WG's recent survey (annex S 1).

⁴ The WG's survey (annex S 1, in particular S 1.2.2) shows divergent practices among the represented funders regarding explicit rules and information to reviewers on how to weigh criteria. Some funders (17 out of 35) indicate to reviewers how criteria are to be weighted, some (10 out of 35) do not. Among those who indicate weights, some do so in a loose way (see S 1.2.2). In practice, reviewers usually have broad freedom in weighting criteria.

Indeed, it is a good practice to make all material intended for reviewers standardly available to (potential) applicants, too. Resources permitting, applicants could also be granted the opportunity to discuss review criteria with representatives of the funding agency prior to applying.

In thinking about how to describe their programmes, criteria and procedures, funders may consider that additional information can - in addition to and independently of their direct usefulness for applicants - also increase trust in the review procedures.

In their efforts to optimize the amount and kind of information they publish on their procedures and criteria, funders may consider the following questions:

- Is the information on the kinds of projects sought sufficient? Are examples of projects given? Are examples of project outputs or impacts given?
- Is the public information on criteria and procedures as detailed as the internal regulations, and as the information presented to reviewers or internal stakeholders?
- Is the set of criteria coherent and stringent, understandable without prior familiarity with the funding programme or agency?
- Are the individual criteria described at an appropriate level of detail?
- Are the relative weights of criteria indicated?
- Are the review procedures described at an appropriate level of detail?
- Is the degree of freedom regarding the interpretation of criteria, and regarding their weights, indicated?
- Is the degree of freedom of review boards or panels in the way they discuss proposals indicated?
- Is it possible for an applicant to point to open questions or vague formulation, and to obtain additional information from the funder?

Practice Examples

HRB: Ireland Observer Initiative

In 2024, the Health Research Board (HRB), Ireland, implemented the Observers Initiative, inviting observers into panel meetings in order to better inform the research community about HRB review processes. Observers are invited from host Institution research offices to observe selected, suitable panel meetings, in the hope that they will widely pass on their first-hand experience to researchers and administrators inside and outside their organisation. In the panel meetings, competing applications are discussed for selection and ranked for funding; some meetings also have an interview component. To ensure that panels are not disrupted in their work, a limit of two observers per panel meeting applies.

The HRB ask observers to talk freely about their experiences of the HRB review processes within their own institutions. However, observers are barred from talking about any specific applications, specific details of feedback given, or application-specific panel discussions. This information is confidential, and each host institution taking part in the Observer Initiative is required to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement. Importantly,

confidentiality includes agreeing not to share direct feedback with individual applicants. After the panel meeting, the HRB ask for feedback on the process, to help identify whether the Observer Initiative met expectations and how HRB observer processes could be improved.

ANR: Inviting observers to evaluation panels to increase transparency

Since 2008, the National Research Agency (ANR), France, is certified ISO 9001, the international standard benchmark, for its project selection and contractualization processes. As part of this certification, the ANR has implemented a principle of observation of the scientific evaluation panels by internal ANR observers who do not take part in the scientific debates or decision-making process of the projects.

This observation of several evaluation panels of the call according to the same observation grid makes it possible to ensure compliance with the selection process as written in the reference documents of the call, and allows, if necessary, to identify points for improvement and generalize the good practices observed across all of the scientific evaluation panels.

2.3 Diversifying the pool of reviewers

For all funding organisations participating in the WG, the most important criteria in the selection of external reviewers and review panel members are the reviewer's scientific qualifications and the expertise in regard to the proposal(s) at hand, usually understood as disciplinary proximity and experience with the kind of research (and sometimes technology, management, fieldwork conditions, regional/national circumstances, etc.) projected in the proposal at hand. These are criteria with respect to which funders seek to avoid all compromises, even if the search for appropriate reviewers proves difficult.

The WG affirms the appropriateness of these criteria for selecting reviewers. At the same time, it emphasizes that criteria such as these are typically employed by RFO officers, and that in such a human and socially embedded employment, there is always the possibility of an unintentional and unnoticed addition of further - implicit - criteria into the search. Biases, after all, do not only operate at the level of reviewers, but can also operate at the level of RFO officers selecting reviewers. For this reason, the pool of reviewers available to a funding agency can be unintentionally narrowed down, both in terms of numbers, but also in terms of reviewer characteristics.

It is easy to see that a high number of potential reviewers is preferable to a low number. The WG would argue that this is also true for the degree of diversity in the pool of potential reviewers. A high diversity in the pool of reviewers in its many guises - in terms of age, gender, career stage, cultural background, field of academic and non-academic experiences, country of affiliation and other factors - can have a beneficial impact on the quality of assessment, by extending the range of considerations which may be relevant for a project and hence in the assessment of research proposals.

The WG would suggest the following methods of supporting the diversity in the pool of reviewers, emphasizing that the suitability of each method depends on the mission of the funder and the nature of its calls and funding programmes:

- broadening criteria and internal targets for reviewer selection,
- training of RFO officers on reviewer selection,
- various methods of raising and sustaining awareness among RFO officers, including in everyday work settings,
- developing and broadening reviewer databases, wherever used,
- where AI tools are used in the search for reviewers, making sure that these do not suffer from narrow training data (and keeping in mind the continuous training of the same),
- inviting broader groups of academics to sign up for reviewing roles, where applicable,
- allowing academic communities - through disciplinary societies, research institutions or in other ways - to suggest members for reviewing roles,
- allowing applicants to suggest suitable reviewers,
- encouraging or offering applicants to act as reviewers of future proposals,
- in some disciplines or settings, considering the inclusion of relevant non-academic reviewers,

- training broader groups, including younger researchers, to review, and affirming their membership in the academic community within which peer-review takes place,
- communicating in targeted ways with specific associations or groups of researchers,
- considering previously unused forms of reviewer recognition or reward.

It is, of course, also important to follow CoARA commitments 2 and 3 in the reviewer search: a reviewer search which (only) follows quantitative metrics is not likely to be of high quality. This may be particularly true with respect to reviewer diversity.

The WG wishes to argue that a broad reviewer pool does not only benefit the RFO, but also the research communities. Reviewing, after all, is not only a burden, but also constitutes participation in an important aspect of scientific communication. Reviewing broadens horizons and helps to stay on top of scientific developments. Broadening the reviewer base may therefore also serve to broaden access to excellence.

Practice Examples

ESF: The pool of reviewers as community of experts

At the European Science Foundation (ESF), a non-profit organisation which specialises in research assessment and funding programme management, reviewers are identified and invited by scientific officers who validate the Community membership as well as all reviews provided by experts.

Reviewer expertise matching goes hand in hand with seeking and monitoring diversity in the reviewer pool. To guarantee both quality and diversity, reviewers are not selected solely on the basis of publication metrics; rather, their CVs are examined by the scientific teams to assess evaluation experience, career stage, and research outputs. ESF follows targets for gender balance and geographical balance. In addition, ESF seeks to include reviewers with intersectoral profiles, bringing in expertise from industry, and other non-academic sectors. Among the ca. 10,000 assessment reports provided by ESF each year, ca. 60% are provided by the members of the ESF Community of Experts. In order to ensure relevant assessments, ESF regularly identifies experts outside of the pool, which also provide a good way to expand and renew the Community.

The scope of assessments carried out each year for a wide variety of calls across different national contexts also contributes to identifying reviewers from diverse fields and backgrounds, thereby supporting broad disciplinary coverage. Gender balance is continuously monitored, and ESF takes proactive steps—such as reaching out to female academic associations and networks—to strengthen the representation of women within its colleges. Finally, the Community of Experts is international in scope, encompassing more than 90 countries, with helps to avoid over-representation of any single country.

Volkswagen Foundation: Reviewer Lottery

The Volkswagen Foundation aims to further acknowledge the indispensable contributions of peer reviewers and increase the visibility of their efforts. Starting in 2023, the foundation has been experimenting with a reviewer lottery. Each reviewer who participates in the Foundation's review processes within a calendar year stands a chance to win a prize. Annually, twenty-five prizes of €10,000 each are awarded, with the stipulation that they must be used for research purposes. Following the draw, winners are required to submit a brief description of how they plan to use the funds.

<https://www.volkswagenstiftung.de/en/news/interview/incentive-bonus-10000-euros-reviewers>

2.4 Providing dedicated space in CVs for displaying a broader variety of research outputs, activities and career trajectories

The question of how to provide space in CVs for candidates to display a broad range of research outputs and career trajectories has drawn a lot of attention in the debate on how to reform research assessment. While the definition of what a narrative CV is still debated, it can be said that such a researcher assessment tool serves the purpose of accompanying more traditional information on education and background with discursive information narrating trajectories, skills, and achievements. The rationale of including narrative elements has to do with information diversification, which allows for a greater consideration of biographical context and quality over quantity. To achieve these goals, RoRI developed five recommendations that constitute an important reference on how to implement narrative CVs (Research on Research Institute (RoRI), Varga, & Kalténbrunner, 2025). The *Résumé Resources Library* co-developed by the Joint Funders Group is another notable resource to support the adoption of narrative CVs. As DORA recommended, it is not only important to adopt such tools, but also to train those involved in evaluation processes and monitor.

WG members tackled such critical topics in the context of the reflection on information requested from applicants (see also WG survey results in the annex). While some general concerns regarding increased workload, confusion among applicants and reviewers and possible disadvantages for non-English speakers remain on the adoption of fully-narrative CVs, it emerged that many WG members have adopted similar initiatives with a good degree of success.⁵ It emerged that the changes relating to information requested from applications should be embedded in a broader change of research assessment systems and research culture more in general. The desired development would include more focus on quality and more responsible use of quantitative indicators. A more responsible use of quantitative indicators does not mean simply abandoning them altogether; rather, it means careful contextualisation, strict observance of their limits, and generally avoiding an overreliance on them, while adopting qualitative indicators that serve as key complements to quantitative evaluation.

The following practice examples describe various initiatives on CVs from different institutions.

⁵ The WG survey reflects this: a number of funders either already pilot or employ CVs with narrative elements (see the practice examples) or are seriously considering this issue (see S 1.2.2).

SNSF: Narrative CVs

The Swiss National Science Foundation's (SNSF) CV template comprises five elements: Education and training, previous and current employment, major achievements with selected work, net academic age, and ORCID ID number. The focus is on the achievements and the associated selected works. A lengthy list of publications is not part of the CV. The achievements do not have to be directly associated with the current application. The idea is to give a general description of the most important research achievements to date. Achievements can include contribution to: Generation of knowledge, innovation and advancement of research; development and support of peers and the wider research community; broader society

According to data collected in an evaluation, a majority of applicants across all domains listed the maximum of three achievements and ten work examples, suggesting they are making full use of the new format's structure. Despite the format encouraging diversity, publications remain the most common work type listed, accounting for 87% to 96% of all works depending on the research domain. However, nearly a third of all CVs (29%) included at least one work category other than publications.

<https://www.snf.ch/en/gKcnwW6aEft4bMPF/page/your-curriculum-vitae-all-about-the-cv-format>

Strinzel M, Kaltenbrunner W, van der Weijden I, von Arx M, Hill M (2022) SciCV, the Swiss National Science Foundation's new CV format. *BioRxiv*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.03.16.484596>

HRB: Narrative CVs

In the case of the Irish Health Research Board (HRB), a narrative-style CV is adopted for funding schemes that build research capacity and capabilities (e.g. postdoctoral or research leadership stages). Such a CV was adopted in 2017 but was further developed later to better align it to the Royal Society's Resumé for Researchers, and guidance for applicants and reviewers were further improved, informed by feedback from researchers and reviewers and in line with the international community. The CV template is not solely based on a narrative structure and includes some quantitative metrics, complemented by narrative-based sections that support a qualitative assessment. The HRB requires lead applicants and mentors to use the narrative-style CV. Recently the HRB is adopting also a team-based CV in some schemes where a leadership team applies for funding. Such a CV is currently not used to assess investigator-led project or programme schemes.

<https://www.hrb.ie/funding/hrb-narrative-style-cv/>

The HRB has also evaluated the experience of those using the narrative-style CV by surveying research applicants, mentors, where applicable, and reviewers in different career schemes. Key take aways are that there is a familiarity and general satisfaction with

the CV template and guidance from the applicants' perspective; reviewers value the broader context provided but face the challenges to assess more qualitatively the content and some of the non-traditional research outputs.

<https://www.hrb.ie/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/HRB-Narrative-style-CV-Round1.pdf>

<https://www.hrb.ie/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/HRB-Narrative-style-CV-Round2.pdf>

FNR: The implementation and evaluation of a Narrative Profile

The Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) introduced a narrative-style CV in 2021 for all Principal Investigators (PIs) and Co-PIs requesting funding from FNR programmes, called the "Narrative Profile". The purpose of this change was to streamline and simplify processes through a structured CV template in the following way:

- To align with the concept that research (and researchers) should be assessed on its own merits, and that the value and impact of all research outputs be considered for research assessment.
- To allow an applicant to be more fairly evaluated on their scientific vision, appropriate experience, and contributions to science and society, instead of solely metrics, journal names, and other information that does not fully represent the potential of a researcher.
- To broaden the types of achievements that can be seen as relevant, including practices related responsible conduct of research (ethics and integrity), Open Science, mentoring, contribution to science and society.

The template has four sections, which allow an applicant to give a broad and deep view of their profile as a researcher, including a personal statement, space for describing relevant professional experience, as well as key outputs, contributions, and achievements that give context and demonstrate their fit to the proposal. The Narrative Profile must be accompanied by an updated ORCID profile, which complements the qualitative CV template with a more complete profile of a researcher's contributions to research.

Over the first three years following the introduction of the Narrative Profile, data was collected through a feedback survey sent to applicants and reviewers. The data collected and reports drafted are all freely available (<https://www.fnr.lu/narrative-cv/>). The results show a continuous acceptance of the Narrative Profile among both applicants and reviewers, with the template perceived as better demonstrating a broader range of skills and experiences compared to a standard CV template. In addition, reviewers see this broadening of what is presented in the CV as important in the evaluation of research.

Research Ireland: The narrative CV and DORA principles

The implementation of the Research Ireland Narrative CV in relevant research funding programme calls was built upon a foundation of community consultation, numerous funder working group collaborations, and a review of international best practice. A

narrative-style CV was introduced in 2019, and a new narrative CV template and scoring system was further developed to incorporate modules from the Royal Society's Resumé for Researchers. Guidance and templates relating to the Research Ireland Narrative CV will continue to be informed and strengthened by these groups, as well as iterative consultation with the research community, including Early-Career Researchers. A Narrative CV template for large-scale, team-based grants will continue to be developed and implemented on research programmes where relevant.

A variant of the Narrative CV is deployed in early career researcher programme calls, as well as gender blind peer review and extensions to eligibility windows to account for eligible career breaks/leave.

The Research Ireland Narrative CV does not permit the inclusion of most journal- and publication-based indicators, in line with DORA guidance and principles. Research Ireland advises applicants that, if these indicators are included, applications may be deemed ineligible and rejected prior to expert review. Guidance and resources for reviewers on the evaluation of narrative-style CVs will continue to be developed and strengthened. This guidance will be informed by consultation and feedback from the research community, DORA resources, and the CoARA National Chapter (Ireland). The Research Ireland Narrative CV has contributed to a national shift in conversations in the research and innovation sector from a myopic focus on quantitative publication and research performance indicators/metrics as proxies for research quality to a broader valorisation of diverse research career pathways and outputs.

<https://www.researchireland.ie/funding-policies/narrative-cv/>

RCF: Narrative CVs and revised instructions to reviewers

In 2022, the Research Council of Finland (RCF) implemented a narrative CV section for certain funding forms open to individual researchers. The detailed instructions for the narrative CV are tailored to suit the funding form. For example, for research fellow applicants, the narrative section, called the 'Merits and increased competencies', is designed to allow the applicants to describe their merits, research interests, motivation, future plans and means to progress in their career. The description should focus on the personal research career path with as many concrete examples as possible.

The instructions for reviewers and decision makers have been developed alongside the information requested from applicants. The reviewers are explicitly asked to recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research. When assessing researchers' merits and their competence in delivering the proposed project, reviewers are asked to consider the value and impact of all relevant outputs, not only publications. Further, when reviewing the competence of the applicant, the reviewers are asked to consider the content and quality of publications, rather than their number or venue of publication, or the impact of the journals in which they were published. Quantitative indicators can be used to support the qualitative

review in a responsible manner. Reviewers are also asked to be sensitive to legitimate delays in publication and personal factors or other types of leave, diverse career paths, part-time work and disabilities that may have affected the applicant's record of outputs. In line with the review process, the decision-making process also takes into account the many different career paths of researchers, the impact of research and the promotion of open access.

NWO and ZonMw: Evidence-based CVs

The Dutch Research Council (NWO) and the Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) both use an evidence-based CV, a CV in narrative form, in their joint Talent Programme to assess the quality of the applicant. The evidence-based CV consists of two parts: a narrative academic profile and a list of key output. Within the academic profile, applicants can describe their profile, their research agenda/vision, relevant skills and activities. Applicants may also provide context about situations that have hampered their ability to demonstrate their qualities. In the key output section applicants are requested to list and provide context for a maximum of 10 output items that best demonstrate their qualities, and that are relevant to the application, their own and/or other scientific fields, the research idea and/or society. The evidence-based CV format is designed to accommodate all scientific disciplines, and NWO and ZonMw recognise that typical numbers and types of output vary from one discipline to another. Therefore, a broad definition of output is used, and applicants are made aware of the broad range of output they can include in the CV via a drop-down menu that shows several types of output. In this way, NWO and ZonMw invite applicants to not only include more "traditional" academic output items but to also include more "non-traditional" output items. Types of output that are included in the (non-exhaustive) drop-down menu are for example: article, code, dataset, exhibition, lecture series, policy paper, software, working paper and many more. (More information: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/evidence-based-cv>)

FWO: Adaptations to the application form in the context of the "second axis"

In the context of the reforms to its research assessment procedures and practices, coined as the 'second axis', FWO made several concrete changes to its application forms to capture more diverse research(ers) profiles. These include the introduction of a narrative element, which draws attention to more than only 'classical' research output and is in line with a more extensive definition of 'impact'. These conceptual adaptations are operationalised by means of a CV showing a broad set of activities, a section in the application form dedicated to career paths and breaks with an explanation of their context, a publication list without explicit distinction made between Web of Science or similar types of publications, and a separate listing in the application form of the five main

publications and/or achievements within the previous five years (that are most relevant with regard to the newly proposed research).

More specifically, the 'research statement' as part of the CV is described as 'a narrative on the applicants' scientific career in the past, present and future'. The explanation on this section points out that this statement should reflect in one narrative how the career evolved and will or can further develop. This is meant as an opportunity to present a diverse range of activities and achievements in a context where FWO wishes to leave room for different profiles of academic researchers. This diversity will also be taken into account during the evaluation of the application.

FWF, HUN-REN, DFG and KKS: CV templates allowing for broader research outputs

Applicants of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) are required to list their ten most important academic publications, as well as their ten most significant additional research achievements such as freely accessible research data including software and codes, awards, contributions to conferences, keynote lectures, significant research projects, peer review activities, promotion of junior researchers, exhibitions, interactions with society (including citizen science or transdisciplinary activities), science communication, knowledge transfer, licenses, or patents. If available, a persistent identifier or link to each research achievement must be provided.

The Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN) works with a number of categories intended to display a broader variety of research outputs, activities, and career trajectories. Categories include: Research outputs beyond publications, teaching and training activities, mentoring and support for early career researchers, societal and economic impact, international and national collaborations, funding and granting experience, awards, recognition and professional service.

The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) has adopted a hybrid CV template, including optional narrative space to add supplemental career information (e.g. career breaks due to parental leave, diseases etc.). It also allows the provision of information on activities like reviewing, teaching, mentoring, academic self-governance, supervision of early career researchers. Up to a maximum of twenty elements are allowed in the scientific results section, distinguishing outputs between typical publications (max. 10) and any other kind of published results (max. 10).

The template is available under: <https://www.dfg.de/de/formulare-53-200-elan>

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (2024). Introduction of a Standardised CV Template - Interim Report After One Year. Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18314376](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18314376)

In 2023, the Knowledge Foundation in Sweden (KKS) changed its approach to CV template to encourage broadening review of merits and also for narrowing the merit gap between junior and senior scholars.

This CV format is restricted to a maximum 1 A4 page, serves as motivation to focus on the merits, experiences and publication of most relevance for the project and not on the accumulation of merits in general. Moreover, the number of research outputs is restricted to ten (10) of most relevance for the intended project. This can be an advantage for junior applicants compared to senior applicants. It also easy on the burden of the reviewer.

The applicant is asked to consider for example the following categories: Degrees; positions; research output (ten research results/outputs incl. scientific publications, documented artistic merits, instrumental- or product development, data set, software, patent, process- or policy development, as well as implementation of research results); educational activities (pedagogical qualification, teaching, training and supervision, education development including development of open teaching resources and learning objects; cooperation (with academia, the business sector, or other societal actors, communication efforts); academic leadership (project management, activity development, assessment assignments, centre management, department assignments, granted funding).

More information: <https://www.kks.se/en/broadened-review-of-academic-merits-and-advanced-assessment/>

Berlin Charité and Berlin Institute of Health: MERIT Projects - an assessment tool based on structured templates

"MERIT Projects" is a tool based on structured project templates and corresponding assessment guidelines that aim to promote quality-oriented, fair, and transparent research assessment in intramural funding procedures. Developed within the Trust-funded overall "MERIT" project, it includes the use of structured projects templates and corresponding assessment aids and open peer review to enhance reliability, transparency, and mutual learning between applicants and reviewers. Qualitative assessment (operationalized as "strong"- "medium"- "weak") is preferred over numerical grading to avoid false precision and promote reflexive, content-based evaluation.

Between 2018 and 2022, the templates were applied in 556 funding applications, with 158 incorporating open feedback. Integrated as "QUEST criteria" into more than six funding lines at BIH and Charité, these tools have been systematically evaluated for their feasibility, quality enhancement, and contribution to more robust and equitable research funding decisions.

While the tool has been developed, and is currently used, for intramural funding allocation, it could in principle be adapted to extramural project assessment settings.

See <https://www.bihealth.org/en/notices/wt-bih-merit> for more details.

Kip, M. (2025). Structured project templates with integrated responsible research & innovation (RRI) and open sciences (OS) criteria and corresponding assessment aids for

reviewers for (intramural) research funding lines at Charité and BIH. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609457>

FCT: A hybrid model integrating narrative CVs with national infrastructure

In 2023, the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) piloted its new a Narrative CV format in the new RESTART Programme and has since extended its implementation to all its main calls. This new format aims at broadening the recognition of diverse career paths, profiles and contributions in its funding and institutional evaluation processes. This FCT new Narrative CV format developed the model proposed by the Royal Society "Resumé for Researchers" into a template comprising three sections: (i) a 'Scientific and professional profile' that includes contextualising education, key qualifications, employment history, and also career breaks or non-linear gaps and pathways; (ii) a 'Contributions to science and society' section with four sub-modules of contributions: (a) to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge, (b) to the development of individuals and/or research teams, (c) to the scientific community, and (d) to the broader society; and (iii) a qualitative description of up to five 'Selected outputs and/or activities', where additional and detailed information is provided explaining the researcher's role, contributions and impact. This format represented an evolution of previous FCT models specifically used in calls for the funding of individuals, where a section similar to iii already existed.

A key element of this new FCT format is its "hybrid" or "dual-tool" approach. Even though the Narrative CV is the sole object under assessment, FCT also provides evaluation panels with access to the applicant's full and structured CV, publicly available on the national CIÊNCIA VITAE platform, as a consultation document. This national CV system, which includes other outputs categories beyond publications, acts as a factual record and verifiable backend. This dual tool approach preserves integrity and some level of continuity: the structured CV (with verified data on publications, projects, etc.) remains in place for transparency, while the Narrative CV provides the qualitative, comprehensive and contextualized information under assessment.

Looking forward, FCT is now embedding this reform systemically and expanding interoperability. In May 2025, a new "personalised narrative CV" section was launched within the CIÊNCIA VITAE platform and FCT, is developing an API for this new narrative module to allow other Portuguese institutions to import this Narrative CV into their own evaluation processes, providing a scalable, national-level infrastructure for a more qualitative research assessment.

2.5 Balancing the qualification of the applicant and the quality of the research idea

In project-based funding programmes, it is often the case that the project proposal and the applicant are assessed under separate review criteria or headings. The rationale is that besides the quality of the proposal (where criteria such as the originality of the research ideas, the suitability of the methods and the potential for significant advances in knowledge stand in the center), it is also important to assess the capacity of the applicant to carry out the project.

However, the applicant's assessment might lead to unintended consequences, like reputational bias having an undue influence on peer review outcomes. For example, the European Research Council (ERC) observed that researchers based at highly visible and well-funded institutions, or at well-connected centres of excellence, were more likely to be awarded ERC grants than those in remote or unknown institutions. Similarly, the US National Institute of Health (NIH) heard concerns that reputational bias was existing towards well-established investigators and highly funded institutions.

The question these agencies saw themselves facing was how to include an assessment of the applicant's expertise into the overall project assessment without falling into the traps of biases such as the Matthew effect or the halo effect. In reaction to this challenge, the agencies sought to review their assessment practices to focus the evaluation on the scientific content of the proposal and the likelihood of the project's scientific success, with the applicant's qualification as a contributing factor to the latter. Here, it is not the applicant's overall academic merits, but the person's specific project-related expertise which stands at the center of assessment. A further, related aim of reviewing assessment procedures was to ensure a level playing field for applications of all investigators, regardless of their race, ethnicity, gender, career stage, or setting.

Such practices support the implementation of the CoARA commitments and principles including those to focus research assessment criteria on quality, recognise the contributions that advance knowledge and the (potential) impact of research, and ensure gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness.

Practice Examples

ERC: Novel procedures for panel evaluations

The European Research Council (ERC) has recently revised its evaluation process. One of the novelties include changes to the weighting of the assessment of the proposed project and the assessment of the applicant.

In the past, both the proposal and the applicant were numerically graded in the first step of the evaluation, on equal scales of 1-5, and the scores were then added up. This practice has now been discontinued.

Instead, the ERC sought a way to put a stronger emphasis on the evaluation of the project proposal starting with the initial ranking of the applications. During the individual remote evaluation, panel members evaluate the research project itself, without considering the information on the applicant and individually decide on a score. The subsequent evaluation of the applicant is separate and does not influence the project score. This avoids the possibility that the application from an apparently 'strong' PI with a weak proposal could end up with a similar combined score as one from a less accomplished PI with a brilliant proposal. If a panel opts to rank proposals before the panel discussion, only the project score - not the applicant evaluation - can be used for this purpose.

M. Leptin, Evaluation of research proposals: the why and what of the ERC's recent changes, 2024, https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-02/Evaluation_of_research_proposals.pdf, pp. 10-11

NIH: A simplified review framework

A new "Simplified Review Framework" of the US National Institutes of Health (NIH) came into effect in January 2025.

The five former review criteria (defined as Significance, Innovation, Approach, Investigator, and Environment) have been reorganised into three broader factors to help reviewers focus on crucial questions that determine scientific merit. Reviewers will consider all three factors in determining the overall impact score, which reflects their overall assessment of the likely impact of the proposed research.

- Factor 1: Importance of the Research (Significance and Innovation), factor score 1-9;
- Factor 2: Rigor and Feasibility (Approach), factor score 1-9;
- Factor 3: Expertise and Resources (Investigator and Environment), either rated as sufficient for the proposed research or not (in which case reviewers must provide an explanation).

A significant concern being addressed in the simplified framework is the potential for general scientific reputation to have an undue influence on application review. By changing the evaluation of Investigator and Environment to a binary decision of sufficient or not in the context of the proposed research, Factor 3 aims to help mitigate this potential biasing influence.

'Simplified Review Framework' webpage, a central repository of information on this initiative, including not only background and details on this new peer review framework, but also reviewer and applicant guidance, training and resources: <https://grants.nih.gov/policy-and-compliance/policy-topics/peer-review/simplifying-review>

FWO: Balancing candidate and project scores

Since 2019, Research Foundation Flanders (FWO) applies a proportion between candidate evaluation and project evaluation for the assessment of projects and fellowship applications that provides enough room for the ideas to be developed in the future without being overshadowed by achievements in the past.

With regard to fellowships, for the calculation of the total score the share of the candidate score in the weighing was 60% but is meanwhile lowered to 50% and the share of the score for the project part was increased from 40% to 50%, in order to decrease the impact of achievements in the past (i.e. the CV, publication list a.o.) in favour of potential for the future (the research proposal).

For the same reason, there is a distribution of 25% for the team and 75% for the research proposal in applications for fundamental research projects.

A similar proportion exists for the projects on strategic basis research.

Volkswagen Foundation: Anonymized proposals (double-blind review)

The Volkswagen Foundation, Germany's largest private, non-profit academic funding organisation, has a long tradition of experimenting with its review procedures. Among the procedural experiments and interventions piloted so far is the full anonymization of funding proposals. This was done in some funding programmes, including "Experiment!" (2013–2021), "Open Up" (2021–2025), and "Next - Rethink Neurodegeneration" (2025).

- Jury members do not know applicants' names, affiliations, or CVs; review is based solely on project idea.
- Designed to reduce bias, particularly with regard to age, gender, institution, or career level.
- Highly rated by applicants and panelists for perceived fairness; "the idea counts, not the CV".

FCT: RESTART - Rebalancing criteria for careers gaps and supporting researchers after parental leave

Launched by Portugal's Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) in 2023, the RESTART Programme is a competitive grant scheme tailored for researchers returning to work after a significant parental leave. Its design explicitly promotes equal opportunity in research careers by helping new parents bridge the gap in scientific activity caused by parental responsibilities. RESTART offers up to 18 months of project funding for scientists who took at least 120 days of parental or adoption leave (or 72 days of shared maternity/paternity leave) over the past year of the Call opening. By focusing on those early-career researchers most impacted by career breaks, the programme aims to restore competitiveness at a critical career stage and prevent talent loss from the research system.

RESTART's evaluation process was carefully aligned with its inclusion-focused objectives. Proposals are assessed not only on scientific merit and feasibility, but also on the anticipated impact of the project on the applicant's career development. This additional criterion directs evaluators to consider how the funding will help the researcher regain momentum, reflecting the programme's goal of a "competitive return" to research. FCT also piloted its adoption of a new narrative CV format for RESTART applicants, allowing researchers to contextualize their achievements and explain any productivity gaps during leave, enabling a more comprehensive and fair assessment of each researcher's track record and potential. By adjusting both funding criteria and assessment practices, RESTART exemplifies how policy goals of fairness and equal participation can be built into a programme's design and assessment implementation. Notably, this initiative aligns with international recommendations on supporting researchers after career breaks and a better work-life balance, making it an innovative approach in this regard.

More information can be found under: <https://www.fct.pt/en/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/outros-apoios/programa-restart/>

2.6 Countering “mainstream bias” in assessment procedures

The existence of a “mainstreaming” bias in research funding, namely the tendency to favour projects with long-established methods and subject areas over methodologically or thematically disruptive projects, is difficult to prove and remains⁶. However, most representatives of funding agencies see at least such a possibility, given that there are plausible hypotheses about how such a bias can arise and operate. Putting aside the thesis that all project funding with “ex ante” assessment is inherently and necessarily conservative (which could only be countered by increasing no-strings-attached funds for researchers, or perhaps distributing research funds on the basis of past achievements, i.e. in the form of prizes) the most plausible candidates of conservative leanings in research funding are (a) hesitations of applicants to submit truly disruptive proposals, and (b) potential biases against such proposals in the review and evaluation procedures.

Funders may try and address (a) through the clear and transparent presentation of the programme aims and/or review criteria, including through text explicitly calling for theoretical development along as-yet unrecognized lines, high-risk research, or out-of-the-box hypotheses. This could be done in existing funding lines, or in novel, dedicated funding lines. Of course, funders will also have to make sure that such proposals receive a serious chance at funding, and to instill a degree of confidence in potential applicants that the expense of time and resources needed to prepare an application have a sufficient likelihood of yielding a return. For this reason, funders are well advised to put some thought into (b): ruling out potential biases against disruptive proposals in the review and evaluation process.

The working group has discussed several methods which relate to the procedures of the review:

- Funders can give panels of reviewers explicit leeway in interpreting criteria or in assigning relative weights to criteria so as to accommodate proposals which excel in some conceptual dimension but which do not meet or excel in all criteria. For example, in this way, reviewers can be given the opportunity to recommend funding a project whose feasibility is as-yet difficult or impossible to estimate, which proposes to use an as-yet untested method or whose underlying hypothesis or theory is controversial.

With a view to transparency, reviewer leeway in the interpretation or weighing of criteria should be clearly indicated in the programme or call description, and

⁶ Most studies emphasize the paucity of data surrounding this thesis. However, there appears to be some evidence supporting the existence of a bias against “novel” or “high risk” research in generalized funding programmes; see for example (Ayoubi, Pezzoni, & Visentin, 2021). This also appears to be true for the European Research Council (Veugelers, Wang, & Stephan, 2025).

funding decisions should be justified as carefully as possible. It may, furthermore, be wise to limit reviewer leeway to certain funding lines.

- Funders may consider allowing or inviting review panels to give proposals charitable consideration where two or more reviewers or external reviews are diametrically opposed to each other, as controversy may (of course defeasibly, under certain conditions) indicate disruptiveness. At a minimum, funders should allow enough time for discussion in such cases, so that all panel members fully understand the reasons of a controversy.
- A related approach is to assign “wild cards” or “joker cards” to members of review panels, which can lead to positive funding decisions in spite of controversy among panel members. Here, too, such an approach ought to be clearly indicated in the programme description or reviewing guidelines, and it may be advisable to limit it to certain funding lines. Funders interested in this approach should note that the limited experience with “wild card” pilots indicates that reviewers are frequently hesitant to make use of the option; more experimentation and research on the approach may be needed.
- One source of “disruption” in science are novel links between disciplines. To counter “mainstreaming” biases attaching to interdisciplinary proposals, funders should ensure that all included disciplines are represented in the review, be it in the form of external written reviews or of participation in the review panel and/or decision board. Ideally, this also goes for intersectional disciplinary expertise, i.e. expertise by a person or persons familiar with multiple collaborating disciplines. Given these important considerations, funders may find it useful to institute specialized administrative procedures and/or dedicated panels or boards for interdisciplinary projects. Of course, the latter may only be possible in certain scientific areas or for certain interdisciplinary combinations.

Other interventions discussed in this discussion paper may also have anti-conservative (side) effects. These include, firstly, the design of programmes and competition spaces (see section 2.1). One obvious approach, attempted by some funders, is to offer specialized funding programmes or calls for ideas going beyond the research mainstream. Such programmes are sometimes described as “high risk, high gain” programmes. A second idea discussed by the WG is the proposal to steer the debate away from the applicant and towards the $\square\square\square$, or by detaching the discussion of an applicant’s expertise from the discussion of the project as such (see section 2.⁷). \square The proposal to improve the monitoring of funding decisions may also be of relevance (see section 2.1, last subsection), as better monitoring may help uncover mainstream bias in recent funding decisions.

⁷ Note, however, that certain kinds of funding programmes focusing on researchers rather than projects may well promote disruptive research; e.g. programmes targeting researchers with a proven track-record of disruptive research, or programmes for researchers who want to carry out a significant change of research area. Academic prizes can also have this effect.

ZonMw: Funding high-risk research to foster unexpected insights and breakthroughs

The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) supports unconventional research through its Off Road programme. The aim of the programme is to realise new insights and unexpected breakthroughs in (bio)medical and/or health research. Off Road encourages researchers to pursue bold, innovative ideas that may not fit within traditional funding frameworks. The emphasis of the applications is mainly on developing a promising but risky out-of-the-box idea into a proof of concept. This means that, although the developed idea can have a long-term character, the project is mainly aimed at testing the hypothesis behind the concept/idea. The outcome may be negative, but what counts is that every result, whether or not there is an effect, helps science move forward.

A distinctive feature of Off Road is its assessment procedure, which deliberately avoids mainstream bias:

- Reviewers are asked to assess executability, not feasibility. Proposals must be realistically doable within the project timeframe, and applicants must demonstrate the necessary expertise and access to relevant techniques.
- The programme accepts that not all projects will succeed. Both positive and negative outcomes are valued for their contribution to scientific process.
- Reviewers are specifically instructed to evaluate the high risk-high gain potential of each proposal, rather than its likelihood of success.

More information about the Off Road programme:

<https://www.zonmw.nl/en/program/road-doing-research-beaten-track>

SNSF: SPARK - funding the rapid testing or development of novel and unconventional scientific research projects using double blind review

The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) has been concerned that risky, unconventional out-of-the-box project ideas get systematically refused because of concerns over their feasibility, at the expense of funding more incremental projects that are often biased towards established researchers. In order to counter this tendency, the SNSF has instituted a specialized funding programme: "Spark", a programme designed to fund the rapid testing or development of novel and unconventional scientific approaches, methods, theories, standards and ideas, etc.

The focus of Spark is on promising ideas of high originality for which preliminary data are not necessarily available (high-risk research). Positive results might then become the basis of a bigger project; negative results will also be regarded as knowledge gained. The focus is on projects or ideas that are unlikely to be funded under other funding schemes. To reduce the bias that comes from knowing an applicant's track records, applications are evaluated in a double-blind reviewing process. This ensures that

applications are evaluated on their own merits and not based on an appraisal of the applicant.

Applicants must submit a brief description of relevant educational and employment histories and confirm that they have the expertise needed to carry out the project. In addition to evaluating the scientific quality of the proposal, evaluation focuses on the novelty and unconventionality of the idea proposed. Data now suggest that this format supports higher success rates for Early Career Researchers than in conventional project funding.

Volkswagen Foundation: Experimenting with review procedures

The Volkswagen Foundation, Germany's largest private, non-profit academic funding organisation has a long tradition of experimenting with its review procedures. Some of the piloted interventions aim at expanding the diversity of research or project types which get selected by decision boards: distributed peer review, a partially randomized selection (lottery) and joker votes (wild cards in the panel discussion).

Distributed Peer Review (DPR):

- Tested in 2024-2025 as part of the "Open Up" funding initiative for humanities and cultural studies.
- All applicants are required to act as reviewers for other submissions, providing reciprocal assessment.
- In this experiment DPR run in parallel with traditional panel review; comparison of selection methods was possible and funding recommendations combine outcomes of both streams.
- Aims to enhance fairness, scalability, and robustness of peer review.

Research on Research Institute; Butters, Anna; Benson Marshall, Melanie; Pinfield, Stephen; Stafford, Tom; Bondarenko, Alexander; et al. (2025). Applicants as Reviewers: Evaluating the Risks, Benefits, and Potential of Distributed Peer Review for Grant Funding Allocations (RoRI Working Paper No. 17). Research on Research Institute. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.29994841.v2>

Partially randomized selection ("Lottery"):

- Repeatedly applied, e.g. in the "Experiment!" funding initiative supporting exploratory projects.
- Randomization complements, rather than replaces, expert judgment: after initial eligibility check and quality screening by an independent jury, proposals are entered into a supervised lottery to select grantees. In addition, the jurors directly select the best grants for approval.
- Enables allocation of funds to unconventional/high-risk ideas and increases diversity among grantees.
- Outcomes suggest research quality and output are comparable for jury- and lottery-selected projects.

Joker Votes (Panel Review):

- Panel members in the "Experiment!" initiative were allowed to use a joker to support a favored application not otherwise selected by consensus.
- Ensures panelists can champion outlier proposals that may not fit conventional evaluation, expanding methodological pluralism.

2.7 Consideration for sex, gender and diversity in the composition of research teams and in the scientific content of the projects to promote quality

Adequately considering sex, gender and diversity in research teams at all levels as well as the sex and gender dimension in the content of the research project (where potentially relevant) increases the quality and relevance of research and the capacity for innovation. It also contributes to a more inclusive research environment with more diverse perspectives and to reducing biases and “blind spots” in knowledge production.

The WG identified existing or possible new practices by research funding organisations relating to evaluation criteria and to procedures that address the CoARA principle to “ensure gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness” and thereby also contribute to CoARA commitment 1 to “recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research”.

Gender and diversity in the composition of research teams

Excellent science needs diversity and originality. It is therefore essential to consider different perspectives in research, as well as the experiences and characteristics of everyone working in science. The WG discussed numerous practices relating to evaluation criteria and to procedures that can promote gender and diversity in the composition of research teams. While most of the practices have a strong focus on gender equality, many funders have started to broaden their efforts towards further diversity dimensions like age, disability, socio-economic status, ethnic origin, etc. Instead of discussing practices in detail here, the reader is referred to the outputs of another CoARA working group “TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research”⁸ which has substantially reflected on the topic. Considerable work has also been carried out by EU funded projects GRANteD (Grant Allocation Disparities from a Gender Perspective), and SUPERA (Supporting the Promotion of Equality in Research and Academia) that already identified some examples of practices by research funding organisations. Another collection of good practices can be found in the 2024 Science Europe “Practical Guide to supporting diversity in research environment” (Science Europe & Morris, 2024).

Sex and gender dimension in the content of the research project

A growing number of research funding organisations have identified appropriate consideration of sex and gender in research and innovation content (where relevant) as part of their definition of research quality and their award criteria (see also WG survey results in annex S 1). For example, in relevant cases, sex and gender dimensions are important aspects in the design of a research project in the context of research question or proposed

⁸ <https://www.coara.org/working-groups/wg-tier-towards-an-inclusive-evaluation-of-research/>

methods, without necessarily being the focus of the project. It may indeed require data disaggregation by sex, gender, or other dimensions to enable targeted analysis, thereby improving the quality of the research results and their impact. An obvious example is the importance of appropriately considering the sex and gender dimension in clinical research. Many other concrete examples of how sex and gender analysis can lead to new discovery and innovation have been identified by experts working for the European Commission (European Commission & Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2020).

Practice Examples

Topic: Consideration for sex, gender and diversity in the scientific content of the projects to promote quality

A growing number of research funding organisations (e.g. NCN, RCN, KKS, ANR, Research Ireland, DFG, European Commission under the main Work Programme part of Horizon Europe, NHMRC, RCF) are recognising the importance of considering sex and gender in research and innovation content, where relevant, as part of their definition of research quality and their award criteria. Applicants are asked to describe how sex and gender perspectives are taken into account in the research content (if relevant), when presenting the research questions and methodology. Accordingly, reviewers evaluate the appropriate consideration of gender in the research content when assessing research quality.

Polish National Science Centre (NCN), Regulation for granting funds for the implementation of tasks financed by the national science centre in the scope of research projects, 2023: https://www.ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/uchwaly-rady/2023/uchwala50_2023-zal1.pdf#page=10

Research Council of Norway (RCN), call documents available on its website, 2024: <https://www.forskingsradet.no/en/call-for-proposals/2024/researcher-project-for-scientific-renewal-thematic/>

French National Research Agency (ANR), Gender equality plan 2024 - 2027: <https://anr.fr/fileadmin/documents/2024/ANR-Plan-action-egalite-genre-2024-2027-en.pdf>

European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 2024: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

DFG Proposal Guidelines for Individual Grants Programme: www.dfg.de/formulare/54_01

SUPERA project: Call text and content

The SUPERA project recommended ensuring that the call texts are inclusive, gender-neutral and avoid stereotypes. The call texts should also include sex or gender dimension in the description of the scientific areas covered, whenever appropriate. Research

funding organisations should consider the inclusion in their calls of gender-specific topics and research-on-research actions on gender. For example, the Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area Programme part of Horizon Europe includes specific funding for actions supporting the development of inclusive gender equality plans in research and innovation organisations across EU Member States and associated countries.

The European Commission under Horizon Europe main Work Programme part, and other research funding organisations also reported the practice of internal review by their staff of the draft call texts, to improve the way in which the gender dimension is taken into account (as well as other cross-cutting priorities such as open scientific practices).

SUPERA project, Guidelines for gender-sensitive communication in research and academia: <https://www.superaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/SUPERA-guidelines-gender-sensitive-communication.pdf>

SUPERA project, resources and examples webpage, 2023: <https://www.superaproject.eu/rfos-journey-map/>

European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 2024: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Topic: Increasing gender balance in selected projects

Several research funding organisations take measures to limit gender bias in the evaluation process. Having a Gender Equality Plan in place is an eligibility criterion under the main Work Programme part of Horizon Europe, for public bodies, research organisations and higher education establishments from EU countries and non-EU countries associated to Horizon Europe. The Gender Equality Plan is expected to be a public document, supported by resources for the design, implementation, and monitoring of the included actions, supported by training and capacity-building, and with arrangements for data collection and monitoring. The European Commission recommends five thematic areas to be covered by a Gender Equality Plan:

- work-life balance and organisational culture.
- gender balance in leadership and decision-making.
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression.
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.
- measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

In its practical guide to improving gender equality in research organisations, Science Europe recommended some practices to reduce gender bias in assessment like to avoid penalisation for parent-related leaves, or for caregiving. Similar efforts are undertaken by the DFG (German Research Foundation), e.g. through an eLearning platform and a video clip on avoiding biases (see also below) and by FWO (Research Foundation Flanders, Belgium), which asks in each application how gender issues have been taken into account

with regard to content as well as team composition. FWO has a gender equality plan in place.

The GRANteD project advocated for considering re-ranking strategies to increase the number of granted women, by modifying the ranking order of applicants approved for funding based on their sex/gender. Re-ranking can take various forms. The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) has undertaken to mandate at least 50% of the funds for women who are leading projects in its ESPRIT programme, regardless of the proportion of female applicants. Furthermore, the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), has opened the possibility to extend grants under its main programme, CORE, in case of long-term leaves of essential project staff such as illness, pregnancy, parental leave, or caregiving responsibilities, which impact on the project timeline

ANR (French National Research Agency), Action plan for Gender Equality and Gender Mainstreaming 2020 - 2023, 2019 : <https://anr.fr/fileadmin/documents/2020/PA-Genre-ANR-en.pdf>

Science Europe: practical guide to improving gender equality in research organisations, 2017: https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/ubbllodu/se_gender_practical-guide.pdf

Science Europe: Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments, 2024: https://scienceeurope.org/media/zqai44sd/202402_practical_guide_to_diversity.pdf

H. Schiffbänker, A. Sauer, H. Peterson, GRANteD deliverable D6.3 - Reforming peer review practices - lessons learned from the implementation of gender equality policies in Research Funding Organisations, 2024: <https://zenodo.org/records/10613191>

Austrian Science Fund (FWF), objectives and principles of the strategy for equal opportunities and diversity, webpage, 2024: <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/equal-opportunities-and-diversity/objectives-and-principles>

European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 2024: European Commission, Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans, 2021: [programme-guide horizon en.pdf](#)

Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), grant extension guidelines, 2024: <https://www.fnr.lu/core-grant-extension-guidelines-now-available/>

NWO: A piloted intervention to increase opportunities for female researchers

In 2024, the Dutch Research Council (NWO), together with the Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw), announced the launch of a pilot within the Vidi grant (a part of the Talent Programme) to increase opportunities for talented female researchers. The pilot, based on successful existing review procedures formerly implemented at [Science Foundation Ireland \(SFI\)](#) (now Research Ireland) and extensive in-house research, consisted of a ranking strategy to increase the number of granted women.

In this pilot, all weighted final scores following the assessment by the committee, supported by external referees, are rounded to the nearest multiple of 0.5, resulting in more proposals receiving similar scores. Proposals with the highest final scores will still receive the grant. Around the funding limit, where proposals are of comparable quality, preference is given to female applicants.

See <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/nwo-launches-pilot-vidi-grants-to-increase-opportunities-for-talented-female-researchers>

DFG: various measures to support gender equality in research work

Over the years, the German Research Foundation (DFG) introduced several practical measures to remove barriers in scientific work resulting from parenthood or care duties. For example, a principal investigator (PI) who has a child during a project can extend the project duration and/or request funds for further support. Persons in need of childcare during a review session can seek funds for babysitting. While such measures are open to members of all genders, they are disproportionately requested by women, and have mainly been introduced with the aim of improving gender balance in mind. The DFG has also introduced measures specifically targeted to women. For instance, in order to increase the share of female coordinators of large coordinated research units, women can request funds for organisational work to relieve them of certain administrative duties. Lastly, for coordinated research units, DFG offers funds for measures aimed at improving gender balance within the unit. If a proposal contains convincing measures, reviewers can opt for granting these extra funds along with the funds for the scientific work.

More information: <https://www.dfg.de/en/basics-topics/basics-and-principles-of-funding/equal-opportunities>.

See also: eLearning platform "Mitigating Bias in Scientific Evaluation and Decision-Making Processes" https://sites.dfg.de/sites/bias_tutorial_en/ and film <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yNdFVV3jAlI>

Research Ireland: Gender Dashboard

As part of Research Ireland's commitment to improving the representation of Historically Underserved Communities in its portfolio of grants, the Gender Dashboard has provided an analysis of gender disaggregated data across a cohort of funding programmes since 2011. It is one of several actions that Research Ireland has undertaken to address and examine the underrepresentation of women in grant funding. The analysis aims to expose unintended biases that may exist in Research Ireland's grant review processes by examining application success rates and funding amounts across different funding programmes by gender (binary).

Although the current analysis represents data from STEM (Science Foundation Ireland) applications for funding prior to the establishment of Research Ireland, the Dashboard

reflects the success of gendered initiatives implemented by both legacy agencies. The Dashboard's data establish that there are no apparent biases in Research Ireland's review process. Specifically, the overall year-on-year success rates for men and women are comparable; this was also evidenced in an independent review undertaken of the [IRC Gender Strategy and Action Plan](#), published in 2022. The data for all Research Ireland programme calls since its establishment will be included in future updates of the Dashboard accounting for the expanded remit of Research Ireland.

The Dashboard is available under

<https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/research.ireland/viz/GenderDashboard-External/GenderDashboardv1>

The anonymised data presented as part of the Gender Dashboard is available to use free of charge and licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC-BY\) Licence](#).

2.8 Incentivising open science practices

Open science is defined as *"an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community"* (UNESCO Recommendation on open science (UNESCO, 2021)).

Open science practices increase research collaboration, support transparency in the research process, reproducibility of research results, and make knowledge accessible and re-usable by everyone.

The benefits of open science have prompted several funders to include requirements and obligations aiming to incentivise the adoption of relevant practices in their funding programmes. Most interventions of funders so far focus on the open access (to publications), but some piloted practices also include the dimensions of collaboration and transparency.

The 2024 survey on the strategic approaches to, and research assessment of, open science, carried out by Science Europe, shows that a majority of its members include open science as part of the funding requirements for funded projects (Morris & Saenen, 2024). This includes in particular: open access to research articles, books and research data; Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (FAIR) research data (including data management plans); Open source research software, code, and tools; stakeholder engagement; citizen science and public engagement; open research methods. Members of CoAlition S, an international consortium of research funders, have equally implemented requirements to make scientific articles stemming from research they fund immediately available in open access. Other organisations, like the European Commission, are incentivising open science practices across the whole lifecycle of a project, from the proposal until the reporting stage.⁹ At the same time, it needs to be noted that what a researcher can do in terms of open science in a given setting (discipline, country, institution) depends on the infrastructure available in that setting. Therefore, together with incentivizing individual open science practices, e.g. by making funds for OS activities within projects available, funders are called upon to develop and fund the availability of the (digital) infrastructures which make OS practices possible in the first place. Good OS by definition, rests on data and infrastructures which are in the hands of the scientific community/communities, rather than those of commercial enterprises. On a related but distinct note, data and infrastructures underlying research assessment activities should ideally be open and community-owned, too.

⁹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en

Horizon Europe: Open science practices as part of the definition of research quality and evaluation criteria

Horizon Europe, the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation for the period 2021-2027, incentivises and rewards open science practices more broadly, not only open access to publications and research data management. As a major novelty for the main Work Programme part, the quality of the open science practices is evaluated at proposal stage, under the “excellence” award criterion. As part of this criterion, applicants need to describe how open science practices are implemented as an integral part of the methodology and show how their implementation is adapted to the nature of their work, therefore increasing the chances of the project delivering on its objectives. Open science practices include:

- Early and open sharing of research (for example through preregistration, registered reports, pre-prints, or crowd-sourcing);
- Research output management;
- Measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs;
- Providing open access to research outputs (such as publications, data, software, models, algorithms, and workflows);
- Participation in open peer-review;
- Involving all relevant knowledge actors including citizens, civil society and end users in the co-creation of R&I agendas and contents (such as citizen science).

European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 2024: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Topic: Mandating open science practices in grants

Several research funding organisations mandate some open science practices:

The Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) requires that publications are published in Open Access Journals, or on Open Access Platforms, or made available through Open Access Repositories, under a Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license. Open Access must be immediate upon publication, without embargo periods. Data underpinning research publications must be made available at the time of publication, as openly and as freely as possible. A Data Management Plan must be drafted for all projects accepted for funding. Researchers and institutions are expected to ensure the preservation of research data by deposition in trusted repositories in such a way that the data are as findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) as possible.

The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) has an Open Access Policy for peer-reviewed publications in place which requires open access for all FWF-funded peer-reviewed publications including books. Articles need to be published Open Access under the Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license without delay (See <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/open-science/open-access-policy>). Since 2019, the FWF requires a Data

Management Plan (DMP) (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/open-science/research-data-management>) for funded projects, emphasizing adherence to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles for research data. The data management plan needs to describe how data and its metadata are collected, organized, stored, published, shared, and archived for a given project. Furthermore, the FWF requires open access to the data underlying publications since 2019 (See <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/open-science/open-access-policy/open-access-policy-for-research-data>). The FWF's Open Science Strategy is supported by various funding initiatives such as the FWF Open-Access Block Grant (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/funding/portfolio/communication/open-access-block-grant>), the funding programme to support open-access book publications (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/funding/portfolio/communication/book-publications>) and the funding programme to support digital publications (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/funding/portfolio/communication/digital-publications>). The FWF regards open research information as a key component of open science and therefore makes information on all FWF-funded projects as openly available as possible, including the use of persistent identifiers such as grant DOIs (See <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/discover/research-radar>).

Under Horizon Europe, the following open science practices are mandated in the funded projects:

- The open access to scientific publications;

The responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles of 'Findability', 'Accessibility', 'Interoperability' and 'Reusability', notably through the generalised use of Data Management Plans, and the open access to research data under the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary';

- The provision of information about the research outputs/tools/instruments needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications or to validate/re-use research data;
- The provision of digital or physical access to the results needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications.

The FWO (Research Foundation - Flanders) has made Open Access Green a requirement for all publications resulting from its funded research. The organisation allows for embargo periods of a maximum of 12 months. APC's for other types of Open Access are an eligible cost but there are no earmarked budgets for this item. In parallel, applicants find in the application forms a series of suggestions and incentives in order to be able to refer to implemented open science practices in relation to past achievements or planned research. The scoring grids are adapted in such a way that making research transparent and reproducible can help applicants to earn top scores.

Research Ireland is committed to ensuring equitable access to research outputs for all, irrespective of location or means. Research Ireland requires that all peer-reviewed research publications (excluding long-form publications, book chapters, and review articles) arising in whole or in part from Research Ireland-funded research are open

access. Research publications must be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence. Data Management Plans are required at application stage across the majority of Research Ireland funding programmes. Although not scored if the Peer review panel deems a DMP insufficient applicants are required to revise their Data Management Plan (DMP) before a grant is awarded.

The Dutch Research Council (NWO) and the Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) have implemented several Open Access practices within their funding instruments, focusing on Open Access Publishing, research data management, Citizen Science and Open Science infrastructures. For instance, NWO/ZonMw require that all publications emerging from research funded by their organisations must be made available in open access immediately upon publication. This includes scholarly papers, as well as conference proceedings, monographs and book chapters. NWO/ZonMw accept three different Open Access routes: Gold, Hybrid or Green Open Access. In addition, NWO/ZonMw have a data management policy in place which aims to make research data generated as part of NWO/ZonMw funded projects as open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) as possible. As such, the organisations require applicants to: complete a data management section when applying for grants (1), prepare a data management plan after the grant is awarded and before the project starts (2), and deposit research data resulting from the grant in a trusted repository, while taking into account the FAIR-principles (3).

Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), Open Science policy, 2024 web-page: <https://www.fnr.lu/open-science/>

European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 2024: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Research Ireland Interim Open Research Policy <https://www.researchireland.ie/about/policies/open-research/>

Dutch research council (NWO), Open Science policy: <https://www.nwo.nl/open-science>

Netherlands organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMW), Knowledge development: <https://www.zonmw.nl/en/about-zonmw/knowledge-development>

Topic: Reference to specific open science practices in the text of calls for proposals

Under Horizon Europe, individual call topics can specify some recommended open science practices, going beyond the legal obligations of the grant agreements. For example, the text of calls for proposals can suggest (or even mandate) practices such as open access to other outputs than publications and research data (like software or methods), citizen science or other forms of societal engagement, or measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs.

Furthermore, in the discussions of the Working Group, a few research funding organisations like the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO), the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), the French ANRS Emerging infectious diseases (ANRS MIE), the Knowledge Foundation Sweden (KKS), Research Ireland and the European Commission with Horizon Europe, reported that they carry out internal peer-review of their draft call texts to ensure that open science practices, gender equality and inclusiveness, and diversity of contributions are properly reflected in the various call texts.

European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme Guide, 2024:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Topic: Funding of research-on-research projects in relation to Open Science

Research funding organisations have the capacity to fund research activities on research. In the discussions of the Working Group, a few research funding organisations like the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO), The French National Research Agency (ANR) the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), the European Science Foundation (ESF) and the European Commission with Horizon Europe, reported providing financial or other support to research-on-research projects on open science, but also gender or research assessment. As an example, the EU funded project Open and Universal Science (OPUS) implements research on measures to incentivise and reward researchers to take up Open Science practices.

The Global Research Initiative on Open Science (GRIOS), hosted by the European Science Foundation, aims to synthesise current knowledge about Open Science, identify successful practices, identify gaps in knowledge and stimulate the funding of further research on Open Science. The initiative is open to research performing organisations, research funding organisations, science policy institutions and interested practitioners, willing to contribute. The GRIOS initiative builds on recommendations from the Research-on-Research Sub-Working Group of the G7 Open Science Working group.

To support its open science policies, ANR launched dedicated call in the field of Open science. Recently the ANR launched a specific call on research on research in open science which was open to all the scientific communities. This call invited researchers to adopt a reflective and critical approach to observing and studying their research practices in the context of open science. 10 projects received a total of 2 million euros. To visualize open science call data: <https://data.anr.fr/pages/open-science-en/>

Open and Universal Science project webpage: <https://opusproject.eu/>

Global Research Initiative on Open Science (GRIOS) webpage: <https://grios.org/>

Report from the Research-on-Research Sub-Working Group of the G7 Open Science Working group, 2023: <https://hal-lara.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-04415049>

Topic: Guidance for developing, implementing, and overseeing incentive structures

The Open Research Funders Group's "Incentivisation Blueprint" seeks to provide funders with a stepwise approach to adjusting their incentivisation schemes to more closely align with open access, open data, open science, and open research.

Developed by the Open Research Funders Group, a partnership of funding organisations committed to the open sharing of research outputs and other forms of scholarship, the Blueprint provides organisations with guidance for developing, implementing, and overseeing incentive structures that maximise the visibility and usability of the research they fund.

Incentivisation Blueprint by the Open Research Funders Group:

<https://www.orfg.org/projects-tools>

One example of incentivizing the preparation and sharing of research data along Open Science principles is provided by the Volkswagen Foundation. Its programme "Data Reuse" makes funds available for the preparing and sharing research data collected within Volkswagen Foundation funded projects on recognized research data repositories.

More information can be found under

<https://www.volkswagenstiftung.de/en/funding/funding-offer/data-reuse-additional-funding-preparation-and-storage-research-data-open-science>.

Topic: Open science in organisation-wide strategy and mission documents as a means to enable recognition and incentivisation

Many research funding organisations include a documented strategic approach to open science as part of their organisation's mission, strategy, or vision documents. The open science elements referenced in mission or strategy documents are most often related to open access to research outputs (publications, books, and data). It is these open science elements that are also most comprehensively embedded into research assessment processes, where dedicated criteria, questions, or sections are often used to gather information. This highlights a coherence between documented organisation-wide strategic approaches to open science and its practical support through research assessment processes. It also highlights the role that mission and strategy statements can play in enabling and driving the implementation of practical incentive structures for a broader range of open science activities and outputs (open research methods, open evaluation, public engagement activities etc.).

As an example, the Research Council of Finland, in its 'Strategy 2030' includes open science as part of its definition of responsible science. This translates into a documented approach to the consideration of open science in funding calls and the use of funding (<https://www.aka.fi/en/from-research-to-society/responsible-science/open-science/>)

through policies on open access to scientific publications and research data management.

The Open Science network of French funding agencies (ADEME, ANR, Inserm/ANRS-MIE, Anses and INCa).

In June 2020, the five agencies signed a Joint Declaration in favor of Open Science, affirming their desire to develop a concerted approach to fostering the dissemination and sharing of knowledge, with the following principles:

- promote open access to publications
- promote the opening of research data according to the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” paradigm
- share practices and methods for assessing the scientific quality of projects, in line with the recommendations of the San Francisco Declaration (DORA)
- inform and sensitize beneficiaries by sharing best practices
- open up data relating to funded projects, in line with the Open Government Partnership and the Law for a Digital Republic
- publish an annual report on actions and measures implemented.

Science Europe Survey Report Strategic Approaches to, and Research Assessment of, Open Science, 2024 - <https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/jcvjcnpe/202410-survey-report-strategic-approaches-and-research-assessment-open-science.pdf>.

Research Council of Finland, Strategy 2030 - <https://www.aka.fi/en/about-us/what-we-do/what-we-are/strategy/>.

Research Council of Finland, Considering open science in funding calls and use of funding. - <https://www.aka.fi/en/from-research-to-society/responsible-science/open-science/>

Open Science network of French funding agencies:

<https://anr.fr/fileadmin/documents/2020/Declaration-en-faveur-de-la-Science-Ouverte.pdf>

<https://anr.fr/fr/actus/details/news/science-ouverte-la-feuille-de-route-du-reseau-des-agences-de-financement-pour-lannee-2023/>

2.9 Recognizing diverse or non-linear career paths

Some researchers complain that current academic culture privileges certain types of talent and career path, at least in some disciplines, such as the life-sciences, parts of the natural sciences and the social sciences: the linear academic professional without significant career breaks or detours to non-academic jobs.

This linear track typically starts with a PhD degree, contains one to three postdoctoral positions, then issues in a tenure-track assistant professor or group leader position, followed by professorship, with some variation between countries (e.g. in some countries, an assistant professorship or reader/lecturer position can precede full professorship). As the stages follow one another back-to-back, the model leaves little wiggle room for life to happen along the way, be it in the form of children, sickness, care duties, financially unstable periods or scientifically unsuccessful projects.

The reason behind the privileging of linear career tracks likely has to do with the assumption that an uninterrupted career optimizes scientific capacity and thus produces the best scientific results. It is reasonable to think that this assumption can systematically disadvantage groups in which careers are often less straightforward, and that it can thus promote socioeconomic inequality, elitism, exclusion of minority populations, caregivers, women, or persons with portions of their career outside of academia.

Why should the academic system take researchers with non-linear careers into account? One reason is simply that a larger talent pool is preferable to a smaller talent pool. A further consideration is that persons with non-linear careers may bring unusual or particularly productive perspectives or capabilities or skills to the research environment. This has relevance for the selection or priorities of research questions, possibly also for the pursued hypotheses and methods, and (thus) for the societal impact of research: at least in some disciplines, research aiming for societal impact can benefit from researchers reflecting the composition of society at large. Emerging evidence supports this hypothesis in the field of clinical research.

Non-linear careers are becoming increasingly common. There are several factors that contribute to this. One, and perhaps the most important, is that the average work life has increased and will continue to increase in the near future. Many societies are currently undergoing a demographic shift towards a growing working-age population. This brings with it a need for increased interpersonal and operational skills fostering inclusive work environments (e.g. skill development, lifelong learning, talent strategies). Another factor is technological advancements, including artificial intelligence (AI), which change the needs and skill sets needed to perform a certain job. Research-based jobs are typically heavily influenced by the available technologies and will also therefore need to be agile and ready to absorb the rapid changes. Thirdly, a number of recent events from the recent corona pandemic to political upheavals in countries with previously stable political conditions have led (and sometimes forced) many people to become more flexible and embark on detours

in their careers. Researchers are not spared, and sometimes particularly hard-hit by such developments. Precarity in employment can, of course, also provide a strong impetus for changing course in a career. Furthermore, in many societies, starting or expanding a family today takes place at a later date, over a longer period, and with more equitable sharing of related duties. Finally, there may also be a shift in preferences, with sabbaticals for personal projects becoming more valued.

In order to increase their programmes' openness to applicants with non-linear careers, funders could consider action under five headings: (a) Funding programmes, (b) information requested from applicants, (c) flexibility in funding modules, (d) review guidelines and (e) wider communication.

Firstly (a), depending on their general aims and on the scientific needs of the respective discipline, funders should consider the diversity of applicants - including the diversity of (previous) careers - when designing programmes and calls. This can mean opening special calls or programmes, but can also mean liberalizing the formal conditions for applying throughout various programmes and calls.

Secondly, funders may (b) consider alternative strategies for gathering information on previous careers and research outputs. For instance, funders may consider offering room for justifications of career breaks and periods of low productivity per default. A narrative or hybrid CV template could be a good way for a scientist to describe the factors that have affected their career - focusing on factors which affected the career, rather than expanding on the issue itself.

Thirdly (c), funders may consider increasing flexibility for child care or other care duties (or flexibility for unforeseen circumstances in general) during the funding period. This may also include the portability of grants to other research institutions in case of employment changes.

Fourthly (d), funders should make it clear to reviewers - both in formal review guidelines and in informal communications - that their goal is not to identify the most prestigious string of affiliations or publications, but the right kind of expertise to carry out a specific, proposed project. Reviewers ought not to expect, value or prioritize only one kind of career path for every kind of research project.

Finally (e), funders may want to focus on their communication strategies. Are their calls, programmes and other communications formulated in an open and welcoming way towards diverse groups, including groups with non-standard career paths? There is good reason to believe that communicating the value of non-linear career researchers to institutions (who can hire them), to reviewers (who assess their projects) and to the research community at large (within which many persons with non-linear careers work) may contribute to developing a researcher base with more diverse and broader talents and with higher motivation.

Topic: Consideration of career breaks, career delays and other personal circumstances

Several RFOs, such as DFG, FWF and ANR provide room in the CV templates or proposals for applicants to contextualize career breaks or personal circumstances which may have led to publication gaps, atypical career paths, or limited international research experience. Examples of special personal circumstances or delays include periods of absence due to childcare responsibilities, maternity leave, caregiving responsibilities, chronic/long-term illness as well as pandemic-related downtimes. Time delays in an academic career may also be indicated, e.g. for persons who are the first in their families to pursue an academic career (“first-generation academics”), for various compulsory and voluntary services, language acquisition, migration or integration phases, displacement or asylum procedures. In evaluating the qualifications of applicants, reviewers are asked to consider the individual career stage of the applicants, and to give appropriate consideration to periods of absence and restricted academic activity.

FWF: https://www.fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/Website/Dokumente/Foerderung/Portfolio/Einzelprojekte/fwf_pat_application_guidelines.pdf

DFG: <https://www.dfg.de/en/basics-topics/basics-and-principles-of-funding/equal-opportunities/applicants-funding-recipients/personal-circumstances-faq>

NWO: instruction videos for reviewers on inclusive assessment

NWO has implemented practical tools on inclusive assessment with the goal of broadening the often limited ideal image of what a good researcher or a good proposal is. NWO has developed two videos for reviewers and committee members involved in the evaluation process. The videos inform reviewers and committee members about implicit bias regarding an ideal image and provide practical suggestions, based on scientific research, to optimise the evaluation process. In addition to these videos, NWO provides tips for reviewers and a factsheet. The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) is currently implementing the use of the videos in its evaluation process.

See more here: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/inclusive-assessment>.

NWO, ZonMw and SNSF: considering the net academic research time of a researcher

In the Evidence-based CV, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and the Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) ask applicants to give an estimate of their net academic research time. This is the amount of time the researcher has actually spent on research work, after deducting management tasks, education, leave, interruptions and non-scientific work. The committee is instructed to evaluate the

applicant's track record of achievements in relation to their net academic research time in order to make a fair comparison with other applicants (see <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/nwo-talent-programme/faq>). Additionally, the form provides space for applicants to, if applicable, explain any special circumstances that have led to reduced productivity during their career. Additional information about the number of months spent on research can help the committee interpret the academic achievements and scientific output.

A common problem in evaluating the track records of applicants is that they may have had very different amounts of time available for research. All applicants to the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), as part of their narrative CV, also have to submit information that allows estimation of a net academic age, the time available for academic research between receipt of the PhD degree and submission of the application. Within this timespan, applicants can deduct the time spent on maternity or paternity leave, illness, continuing education, public service or working in a non-academic context. Applicants list the activity, the duration and the date in full time equivalents, which along with the degree awarding and application submission dates allows calculation of a net academic age. This information is validated by the SNSF and the resulting net academic age attached to the applicant's narrative CV. By blinding evaluators from the detail of the calculation, the SNSF minimizes the extent to which secondary criteria, that are not evaluation criteria from willingly or unwillingly entering the evaluation.

Research Ireland: retaining talent in the research and innovation sector

Research Ireland is committed to minimising and mitigating any existing or perceived factors that may limit the participation of individuals in the research endeavour. In particular, Research Ireland is committed to supporting the retention of individuals in Research and Innovation and to encourage individuals back into research careers following maternity, paternity, or adoptive leave. Research Ireland invites its grant holders to apply for a supplemental discretionary allowance to support their Research Ireland funded grant when either a Principal Investigator (PI) or a team member funded on a Research Ireland grant - including postgraduate students - takes a period of maternity, paternity, or adoptive leave. For more information, see <https://www.researchireland.ie/about/policies/maternity-paternity-adoptive/>.

3. Optimizing qualitative review – Ways of implementing CoARA commitments 2 and 3 in assessment procedures

CoARA commitments 2 and 3 highlight the need to optimise the qualitative dimension of the review in assessment procedures. While commitment 2 states the centrality of qualitative evaluation supported by quantitative indicators, commitment 3 focuses on abandoning the use of bibliometric measures such as the Journal Impact Factor in the review process. Given their role in assessments procedures, RFOs play a key role in implementing these commitments. Based on the outputs of the Working group, this chapter provides information on how to ensure that the assessment procedures are compliant with CoARA commitments 2 and 3.

3.1 Before the review – Demand management

In order to alleviate pressure on the reviewing system and to make time - time for qualitative review, and time to conduct actual research - some funders have begun to think seriously about managing the demand for their funding programmes.¹⁰ Lower demand for funding programmes means smaller numbers of applications and thus a reduced burden on the review system. If done correctly, demand management may also increase the quality of applications. This could make review more interesting and thus support the qualitative nature of review - although it may make decisions for review boards or panels harder, too.

There are several different approaches to limiting the demand of funding programmes: thematically narrow calls for proposals, tightened eligibility (and other formal) requirements, restricted parallel submissions (per applicant or per institution), restricted re-submissions after rejection and shortened submission windows.

However, all these approaches have significant downsides which need to be carefully weighed against the reasons which may speak in their favour. Among the downsides, the following are particularly noteworthy: most approaches only shift demand from one funder to another; many approaches limit the freedom of researchers and thus the diversity of ideas offered; many approaches increase the pressure on researchers; and some

¹⁰ For funding organisation, the term “demand management” may sound odd. As their demanded product is *funding* itself, one could also speak of “supply management”. In this paper, we speak of the *demand* for funding programmes and hence of “demand management” and understand ways to limit the number of proposals or funding requests being submitted to funding agencies.

approaches nudge applicants to submit premature proposals. In fact, from the perspective of this discussion paper - i.e. that of supporting the qualitative mode of review - for most approaches and in most cases, the downsides of the demand management approaches outweigh their potential advantages (although there may be other reasons for these approaches, stemming from other perspectives, such as legal or financial considerations.)

From the qualitative review perspective, two approaches appear to be promising: restricting the thematic scope of a call or series of calls and limiting re-submissions of rejected proposals. Both can contribute to lowering the number of proposals to be reviewed, and both - particularly the second - may have a positive effect on the quality of the proposals to be reviewed. The first of these two approaches, in limiting the thematic scope of proposals, can also make for a more scientifically rewarding review discussion, as the circle of invited reviewers can be limited to the closest experts. Experience of WG members suggests that review discussions among close experts are less likely to focus on quantitative or formal matters and more likely to concentrate on scientific contents.¹¹

In general, however, all demand management measures should be employed with great care. If they are newly introduced, they should be announced ahead of time and explained. Two properties of the funding system which are in the interest both of the funding agencies and of the scientific communities are stability and transparency. Without stability and transparency, it is difficult to plan ahead. When introducing demand management measures - be it a tightening of eligibility criteria, a discontinuation or pause in a funding programme or a series of calls, or any other measure - funders should hence keep these properties firmly in view.

¹¹ The WG realizes, of course, that this approach is not always available, e.g. in programmes which are open to researchers of many disciplines, and in which comparisons among researchers of multiple disciplines are unavoidable.

3.2 The selection of and guidance to reviewers

3.2.1 Prerequisites for identifying appropriate reviewers

Finding and recruiting reviewers belongs to the core activities of research funding, and all RFO have developed rich experience in this field. Out of the many issues falling under this heading, the WG wishes to highlight one point which can be seen as a prerequisite, and which has relevance to the qualitative nature and depth of assessment. To find the right reviewers who can provide in-depth, qualitative reviews, it is very helpful to draw on RFO staff with close personal links with the research community, ideally also having relevant research experience themselves. RFO staff who are meeting this condition are not only in the position to look beyond publication-based metrics in selecting reviewers and to consider, for instance, potential candidates' breadth of interest, fairness of approach or prior experience with reviewing. They are also - importantly - in a good position to secure a positive response when requesting researchers to provide a review. The acquaintance with members of the community, the scientific understanding of their work and the visibility as a member of the broader academic community are invaluable assets in this regard. Even when reviewer databases or AI-based tools or services are used to search for reviewers, qualified RFO staff are, in many cases, needed to fill in knowledge not elsewhere available, to be appropriately recognized by potential reviewers and to communicate in an effective way.

3.2.2 Guiding principles for the selection of appropriate reviewers and panels of balanced composition

Most of the funding organisations in the WG apply formal general guiding principles for appointing assessment panel members and external peer reviewers (see WG survey results in annex S 2 and European Peer Review Guide (Marras, 2011)) . Having such principles in place supports the uniformity and transparency of panel and reviewer appointment. Depending on their content, they can also aid the qualitative nature of assessment.

Principles for the selection of reviewers and panel members, of course, depend on the role of a specific panel and the RFO's needs regarding individual reviewers. Their nature and application may also depend on the programme, the criteria in focus or the scope of the funding organisation. The guiding principles may be different also for different funding programmes or calls within the same organisation. Importantly, they should be transparent. The scope of each panel and their individual area(s) of expertise or experience should be known to the applicants.

In many cases, RFO's guiding principles for the appointment of reviewers or panel members address the issue of diversity. Organisations apply guidelines for balancing panels regarding different parameters, aspects or scope: disciplinary coverage (scientific expertise), experience in multi-/transdisciplinarity, sex and gender, career stage, industrial or societal relevance, geographical balance, ethnicity, size and orientation of the affiliated higher education institution, public sector, etc. Concerning the assessment of

multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary research proposals, an increase of awareness that this may require a certain expertise itself and not only representatives from the different disciplines the project is emanating from, may be in place. The WG wishes to highlight that a diverse reviewer base and diverse panels not only support CoARA commitment 1 but also benefit the qualitative nature and depth of review enshrined in CoARA commitments 2 and 3.

Regarding the seniority of reviewers, organisations represented in the WG have different approaches. Some favour senior researchers because of their experience, also in matters of research assessment itself. Others emphasize the importance of (also) including younger reviewers, who may be less entrenched in qualitative assessment culture, and whose scientific experience may not fall behind that of more senior peers - on the contrary, it may even compare favourably, for instance regarding aspects of research infrastructure or technology. Some WG members note that often, younger researchers are particularly motivated to engage deeply with research proposals and experience this as an intrinsically interesting scientific activity. Reservations against bringing junior academics may be eased by inviting them e.g., to participate in review panels as observers, to allow them to gain experience into the review system and motivate them to participate.

Regarding the scientific officers moderating or guiding assessment sessions, the organisations represented in the WG also have different practices. Some use an additional neutral officer as observers in their panels to support the panel chair and supervise the processes regarding rules of conduct, conflict of interest and to ensure all criteria and dimensions are applied in the assessment. Others give RFO officers more substantial roles, not only - but also - to act as engines for moving review in the direction of the CoARA commitments, including commitments 2 and 3.

Having guiding principles in place is not the same thing as applying them. To apply and fully attend to the principles during the whole process of selecting reviewers and forming panels can be practically challenging. However, making exceptions from, or sidestepping the established principles should always be explained and transparently communicated.

With respect to the methods used to identify suitable reviewers, different approaches are applied depending on the programme or instrument. The methods range from the use of internal or external databases to using services that support identifying reviewers with the right expertise. Some organisations also require applicants or grant-holders to serve as reviewers. Indeed, conducting peer review not only often constitutes a rewarding exercise, but it may also foster application skills. Spreading review tasks widely in the research community also increases transparency of the funding process in general. Moreover, shifting roles from time to time between applicant and reviewer may support the preparedness to conduct one's review in a deep and qualitative mode.

Recently, discussion of the issue of open review has intensified in the research community. In open review, the names of the reviewers are known to the researchers under review. Most of the relevant discussion focuses on the review of manuscripts for journals or alternative publication venues. However, with new laws mandating open review even for project

funding in some countries, notably Finland, the funding community also took note of the discussions. The WG does not wish to express a particular view on the matter, but many of its members are closely observing the issue. The Finnish experience is of particular interest. While it is too early to derive specific conclusions, the WG members will be interested to determine whether their key hypothesis - that open review disincentivizes negative review (including appropriately negative review) but incentivizes careful argument and depth of engagement - will be borne out by actual experience.

3.2.3 Guidance and training to reviewers and panels – format and content

RFOs' policies aimed at reforming research assessment can be implemented effectively only if reviewers are aware of - and fully understand - them. Reviewers also need to be equipped with tools and information that will enable them to perform their tasks in alignment with these policies. Appropriate training and guidance of reviewers is thus essential to achieving a more responsible research assessment. The panel and reviewers also need to be equipped with a solid understanding about RFOs' policies, the objectives of the funding programme, rules regarding conflict of interests, rules of conduct, the evaluation criteria and how to apply to the criteria in balance with relevant aspects as well as the evaluation process. In short, an outline of what is expected of them as reviewers/panel members. Guidance and training to reviewers can be provided stepwise as support throughout the evaluation process. Some funders provide information to reviewers about the full cycle of evaluation from the call to funding decision (see also WG survey results in annex S 2).

Funders can offer the assessors different formats of information, and on different levels of detail. That may entail for instance both written and vocal guidelines/information, both general and specific information. This information can be in the appointment letter or in other written documents. Training through guided sessions, information pre-meeting or formats like instruction videos, active webinars, is also possible and can assure that the same information is provided to everybody at the same time. The instructions or webinars should preferably be easily accessed at an already existing digital review environment or portal.

Depending on the funding process and the number of reviewers involved, offering an in-person or an online meeting/training sessions may be considered a solid, adaptive and efficient hands-on support, as well as a motivator. It may also be a way for the funders to improve the "quality assurance" of the process, compared to only providing the remote reviewers with written documents. However, online training modules can be very effective with larger pools of reviewers and can be constructed in a way to assure that the assessors actually take the training.

As stated above (in section 2.2), it is important that all material given to reviewers should also be accessible to applicants.

During the panel meeting the funder can provide more detailed guiding first hand. This is also a way for the funder to follow and monitor the quality assurance of the procedure. Since the panel chair often play a crucial role in general but also when implementing more responsible research assessment practices, the role as chair may therefore require specific training and instructions. Some funders provide guidance designated to the chairs on how to perform their assessment responsibly and other objectives for the funding programme (see also section 3.2.2). After the panel meeting or after the funding decision the funder may benefit from an evaluation of the assessment process from the panel or constructive feedback on the information and training provided. However, it requires some routines in place for systematically handling of the information for constructive change to be implemented in a structured way.

Practice Examples

FNR and DORA: Six concrete suggestions to improve responsible assessment of funding applications

The Luxemburg National Research Fund (FNR) and the Declaration on Research Assessment Group (DORA) have co-developed a video and a one-pager with six practical tips for fostering a more holistic evaluation process. They are intended to be used in the reviewers' briefing.

Video tutorial "Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators": https://youtu.be/NlutQj_nppE?si=gJcyKL_8okjziuf

One pager: <https://www.fnr.lu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Responsible-research-assessment-DORA-FNR-1pager.png>

RCF: Responsible research evaluation as part of Review Principles

The Research Council of Finland (RCF) has included a section on "Responsible research evaluation" as part of a document outlining review principles. This section references the fact that the organisation has signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and DORA and is following Finland's national recommendation on good practice in researcher evaluation, signaling the commitment to adhere to these initiatives in its evaluation processes. It also outlines what responsible evaluation means, asking reviewers to take into account a broad range of outputs, activities and practices other than publications, and indicates how to use metrics in an appropriate manner.

https://www.aka.fi/en/research-funding_1/responsible-science/responsible-researcher-evaluation/

<https://www.aka.fi/globalassets/10rahoitus/2025-liitteet/talvihaku-2026/rcf-review-principles-2025.pdf>

NWO: Tips to support responsible research assessment by evaluation panels

The Dutch Research Council (NWO) produced guidance (including video, written guidance) and a factsheet to support responsible research assessment in evaluation panels. This material offers concrete tools to improve interaction and group dynamics, under five main themes: Biased Language, Criteria, Structure, Time and Accountability.

Factsheet: <https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/NWO-handout-inclusive-assessment-tools-for-evaluation-committee-meetings.pdf>

3.3 The external written review

The foregoing section focused on the *selection of and guidance to* both external reviewers (who supply written reviews about specific proposals) and panelists and board members (who look at whole cohorts of proposals and thus evaluate proposals within a comparative perspective). The following pages look at interventions into the *actual review work* itself. This section (3.3) focuses on the external written review; the next section (3.4) will consider the ensuing panel or board discussion. Once again, note that the text assumes a clear division between these stages, but the reader is reminded to keep in mind that some funders employ hybrid assessment practices. (See the UKRI's 2023 "Review of Peer Review" Guide, (Kolarz, et al., 2023, p. 3))

3.3.1 Putting external reviewers in touch with each other

A number of funding organisations - among them FCT (Portugal), AvH (Germany) and ESF (Europe) - have begun experimenting with schemes connecting multiple remote reviewers with one another during the review phase. In all cases, communication between reviewers is organized through the funders' online portals. While the precise ways in which reviewers can communicate with each other - and with the funder's officers - differ to some degree, the approaches share the same motivating thought. The idea is that if reviewers gain access to each other's evaluation, upon initial completion of their own review, their own review can subsequently be improved. In some cases, this process is used in case of diverging assessments between the external reviewers, to facilitate consensus building. This idea can be backed up by multiple plausible auxiliary hypotheses but must be weighed against serious downsides (which are discussed below). Firstly, access to other reviewers' thoughts may help reviewers avoid oversights and thus take a more comprehensive look at a proposal. Secondly, reviewers are enabled to react to views inconsistent with theirs, making it possible to build in arguments and thus offer discursively richer reviews, while inducing others to do the same. Of course, they can also correct errors, including their own. Thirdly, the move may make high quality, in-depth qualitative review more likely, as for many researchers, scientific debate - which would arise during the review - is intrinsically motivating and can spark scientific ideas. Fourthly, communication between reviewers may lead to better calibrated reviews, making it easier for the funding organisation to process multiple reviews in a sensible and fair way.

Note that it is possible - and practiced in the mentioned pilots - that different proposals are reviewed by different experts (otherwise, the model would amount to no more than a classical panel review). Furthermore, the review phase can be succeeded by a final panel or board discussion in which the various proposals and their reviews (which may reflect the discussions between reviewers) are compared.

Of course, the potential benefits of enabling communication among reviewers must be weighed against possible downsides. There appear to be several among latter. Firstly, for some constellations of reviewers, there may arise a mainstreaming effect, as some reviewers could tone-down or alter reactions differing from others', even without the

backing of convincing arguments. The emergence or the strengthening of biases is also a serious danger to be considered and - if and when it arises - checked. Secondly, the demand of time and care involved in a review increases when reviewers do not simply have to process a proposal, but also other reviewers' reactions to it. However, in a setting in which a larger cohort of proposals is given to a group of reviewers, communication among this group may decrease the workload for each reviewer by allowing a division of labor between reviewers (which could, however, counteract some of the above-mentioned benefits, depending on the administrative details).

Practice Example

Alexander von Humboldt Foundation: Peer Circle Reviewing

The Alexander von Humboldt Foundation sponsors scientists and scholars, irrespective of academic discipline and nationality. The selection is based on a process that relies on external reviews. In order to address actual challenges (e.g. increasing numbers of interdisciplinary applications, the general burden on the peer review system) and ensure a balanced, high-quality evaluation of all applications the foundation began further developing its current peer review process. Essentially, the aim is to develop the existing procedure into an interactive, digital review process known as "peer circle reviewing."

It is a different approach to organizing the review phase of the selection process. The idea behind the procedure is to transform the review into a collective task. In this procedure, a defined group of reviewers digitally reviews several applications on a secure platform, exchanging expertise and comparing findings. All reviewers from a particular field of research form a Peer Circle together with the committee member responsible for that field. Depending on the field of research, Peer Circles can consist of 7 to 15 members. The reviewers are appointed for a longer period of time, during which they are asked to participate in the parallel review of several applications in their field of expertise at specified intervals. The appointment of experts to a peer circle is based on their professional competence. Furthermore, the members of a peer circle should represent a variety of subject areas and academic age groups and be gender-balanced. For each application, one or two of the reviewers are designated as "first reviewers", who are expected to start the review process with a structured but comprehensive assessment. Other reviewers are expected to review those parts of the applications that they believe they can review given their experience and expertise. Finally, the reviewers are expected to comment on one another's statements. Taken together, this should produce a high-quality and complete assessment of the application.

In a small pilot project launched in March 2022, the new procedure for reviewing applications in the foundation's main programme, the Humboldt Research Fellowship programme, was tested and evaluated. The external evaluation of the pilot project has yielded positive results: in the evaluator's opinion, the Peer Circle procedure is at least equal to the traditional procedure in all aspects, with clear advantages in some areas. In particular, the procedure is well suited for evaluation in programmes for individual

grants, as all selection criteria are taken into account in a balanced manner. During this evaluation the risk of premature consensus-building in the sense of suppressing dissenting views was addressed. It was recognized as a potential risk but did not materialize. In general, discursive consensus building was considered a positive feature of the procedure, as it led to clearer recommendations for the committee members.

(<https://www.humboldt-foundation.de/en/explore/figures-and-statistics/evaluation/evaluation-of-the-2022-peer-circle-experiment>)

With additional funding from the Boehringer Ingelheim Stiftung, the AvH is currently setting up a corresponding organisational and technical procedure so that it can be used as a review procedure for the majority of applications in the future.

3.3.2 Optimizing the form and submission procedures for reviews

Both forms and submission procedures for reviews differ widely between different funders. It is reasonable to suspect that some approaches are better suited to enable and incentivize reviewers to give in-depth qualitative reviews than others.

The first obvious consideration is that of time and effort needed to access proposal documents and deliver and submit a review. The less time a reviewer must spend on figuring out just what is expected, and on submitting the review, the more time there is to carry out the scientific evaluation itself. Of course, funding organisations have a legitimate interest in conveying the criteria and (perhaps) the aims and other parameters of the funding programme in question. They are well advised, however, to be only as precise as necessary, while also being as brief as possible. Regarding the submission procedure, it appears that an increasing number of funders find that simple-to-use online portals constitute the most efficient means of sending evaluations from reviewers to funders. Both reviewers and funders can benefit from an online system that takes care of the transfer, storage and use of a review.

A second consideration concerns the form or the data fields used for the reform. Under this heading, there is broad consensus among funders on some points, but divergence of views on others. There is consensus that while it may be beneficial to divide the form (or offer distinct data fields) by individual criterion or question, the number of individual questions or fields should not be too high. The likelihood of an in-depth qualitative review is felt to be highest when reviewers have some freedom to develop their thoughts, and that this freedom could be unduly restricted by too many narrow questions. An example of a funder which has followed this thought is Wellcome Trust, which operates with only three broad criteria and a correspondingly simple review form. The questions or criteria, moreover, should be easy to understand. Furthermore, there is consensus that funders should avoid (over)burdening reviewers with technical and administrative questions. Such divergences from the scientific substance of the proposals could demotivate reviewers and hence make a thorough scientific assessment less likely.

There is less consensus on the question of grades. While some funders hold that grades – both individual grades per criterion and overall grades – belong to the set of standard assessment procedures, help reviewers focus their thoughts, serve to explain funding decisions to applicants and the public, and are not detrimental to the qualitative nature of review (note that grades are entered by reviewers or panelists – ideally – after a qualitative review), other funders are of the opinion that the expectation to supply numerical grades could well stand in the way to a qualitative review. Grades, according to the latter view, are highly subjective in the dual sense of being prone to biases and being dependent on personality and mood. The latter is particularly distortive when grades are given by different people (individual reviewers) rather than a joint board grading all proposals in an assigned cohort. According to the funders which opt against grades, it is also unclear what – apart from ease of aggregation – numerical grades *add* to qualitative arguments. A minimum consensus among funders holds that if grades are requested, then each grade should be associated by a clear descriptor, so that the subjectivity of given grades is minimized. Another minimum consensus is that grades must always be accompanied by qualitative – i.e. textual – arguments.

3.3.3 Making the best use of rapporteurs and RFO officers in the processing of reviews

An important area with potentially significant impacts on the nature of the overall assessment is the question of how the external review is introduced into the panel's or board's discussion.¹² Two issues which are of particular importance are the respective roles of RFO officers and rapporteurs in the processing of reviews. (To avoid overlap between this point and the following section on how to steer the panel or board discussion, this section deals mainly with aspects of the *preparation* of a panel discussion.)

Potential contributions from RFO officers range from pre-processing reviews (e.g. assessing whether reviews are all useful, assessing whether all relevant criteria have been considered) via communicating with the reviewer (e.g. to request further information from the reviewer) to distilling key arguments or the overall recommendation from a review. Here, there are uneven practices between different funders. Most funders restrict the role of RFO officers to formal tasks (usually due to accountability concerns), while a minority allows or expects RFO officers to take a more active role in preparing or even steering the review discussion. All funders recognize, though, that RFO officers can – in the roles which their respective systems assign to them – play a significant role in supporting a predominantly qualitative review. They can help ensure that relevant criteria are fairly considered, or that all sections of a review are understood and considered by the panel or board members. In some systems, they can also remind panels or boards of specific arguments, the importance of

¹² As, for instance, in the UKRI Review of Peer Review report (Kolarz, et al., 2023, p. 7), it is assumed here that reviews are submitted by external experts who are not members of the panel or board which discusses a cohort of proposals. See also the ESF European Peer Review Guide (Marras, 2011, p. 24ff).

specific aspects of a given project, and the like. Funders may dedicate some thought to optimizing the role of RFO officers in ensuring a qualitative review.

Equally or even more important are the rapporteurs. In many organisations, not all panel members are expected to read each proposal within a given cohort, and the respective review or reviews, with the same level of precision or care. Instead, individual panel members are assigned the role of a “rapporteur”, meaning that they are responsible for selected proposals and the respective external reviews. They are then expected to introduce both to their colleagues in the panel or board.

In this context, there are some methods to support a qualitative review. Among the more formal aspects of the panel or board discussion, it appears important to assign neither too few nor too many proposals to a given rapporteur, to give rapporteurs time to process the proposals and reviews, and to ensure that in the panel or board discussion, there is enough time to introduce the proposals and reviews. There are further substantive ways, too. Rapporteurs should be encouraged to engage with a review’s arguments, e.g., during the panel discussion and/or in their own pre-assessment report before the panel meeting. They may even take a critical stance with respect to them - argumentative engagement in a panel often leads to a more dependable overall review than a simple registration and enumeration of considerations.

One important downside of the use of rapporteurs is the danger of disengaging other board or panel members. Some funders have methods in place to avoid an outsized role of rapporteurs. One such method, which is employed by FCT, is to request all members of a board or panel to come prepared to report on all proposals, and to only assign the actual rapporteur role before the meeting. Of course, this method is not suitable for large cohorts of proposals. Having two or even three rapporteurs assigned to each project (e.g., as in the case of ESF) can be another way to ensure participation of the panel members. Another method is to request rapporteurs to only begin a discussion by introducing qualitative aspects of the proposal and the reviews, and to only state their overall grade or recommendation after other panel or board members have weighed in.

3.4 Discussing proposals – the panel or board meeting

3.4.1 The panel or board discussion and its structure

In most RFO's practices, the incoming external reviews are read and processed in an ensuing panel or board meeting. In this meeting, proposals are typically evaluated from a comparative perspective, taking into account larger cohorts of proposals received against a call or within a set time. (See, again, the UKRI's 2023 "Review of Peer Review" Guide, (Kolarz, et al., 2023, p. 3)).

The structure of the board or panel meeting – and the structure of each proposal discussion – has a substantial impact on the qualitative nature of review. In what order should proposals be discussed? Could or should non-competitive proposals be set aside? Should a random order be followed, or should the discussion follow a preliminary ranking? And in each proposal discussion: should all criteria be addressed? Should the panel be free in what criteria to focus on in each case? Should each section be concluded by giving a section grade? Or do grades detract from qualitative arguments?

While the practices of the funders diverge widely, there is one point on which all funders converge: time. Having sufficient time to discuss all relevant aspects of a proposal is the principal condition for a deep qualitative assessment. In fact, this is true for both the time to prepare for a review meeting, and for the time allotted to the meeting, or the discussion of proposals itself: lack of time makes review shallow and strongly increases the temptation to rely on indirect quantitative metrics in the assessment.

While this is both true for ad-hoc panels and for standing panels or boards, it bears emphasizing that from the perspective of qualitative review, there is a particular value of instituting – if and when possible and suitable – standing boards or panels with extended terms of office. Such bodies are in a good position to make comparisons across multiple (many) proposals and to develop sensible, discipline-specific interpretations of criteria and decision principles. This can increase consistency and deepen discussion, particularly in qualitative assessment. Of course, this benefit must be carefully balanced against the various downsides of overly long terms of office. Moreover, it bears emphasizing that ad-hoc panels (one-off panels), too, can take a qualitative approach to assessment: they, too, ought to be encouraged and equipped to assess research qualitatively. Beyond the consideration of time, there is no clear convergence of practices and recommendations, but funders may find the following considerations helpful.

Not only is the overall time for a review or board meeting relevant, but also how the time is divided between proposals. One way to optimize the use of time for critical discussions is to identify non-competitive proposals first to be able to set them aside, either for *en bloc* rejection or for very brief case discussions. A proposal can also be marked for expedited rejection within the case discussion, e.g. following a request from the rapporteurs (if rapporteurs are used), or after by suggestion by the chair. It must, of course, be possible

for each panel or board member to ensure that a proposal which they deem competitive is properly discussed (e.g. is taken out of the list of non-competitive proposals, irrespective of the rapporteur's initial call). Funders should also be able to put forward proposals for discussion if there are specific issues which merit attention. At any rate, if a meeting is organized along these lines, the board or panel can focus on the competitive cases, ensuring a deep qualitative review of the same.

Some funders, in order to direct reviewers' attention to the proposal rather than the applicant, begin by creating a shortlist of proposals, and focus – in this stage – on the ideas and contents of the proposal rather than the qualification of the applicant. The latter is then discussed only in the cases which pass the first stage.

A further idea is to stimulate scientific discussions – and in this sense deepen the qualitative nature of the review – by giving panels or boards some explicit leeway in what aspects to focus on or what questions or arguments to explore at greater depth when considering individual proposals. It may also be beneficial to allow funders to make such suggestions. Such an approach could, of course, mean that the different review criteria are not uniformly considered for all proposals under review. For instance, in one case discussion, the panel might focus on whether the proposed scientific method is as novel as claimed, while in another, the panel might focus on whether a particular collection of primary data is of high scientific value to the discipline. While some funders would be prepared to allow such uneven discussion (perhaps even welcome it, as it could also increase the diversity of projects which are recommended for funding), others emphasize that it could be detrimental to fairness. This could be an example of a tension between the aim of supporting qualitative discussion and the aim of procedural fairness.

A final idea to elicit qualitative arguments from reviewers is to focus case discussions not around (cardinal) grades, but on pairwise comparisons between proposals, for example neighboring proposals in a ranking table. In such discussions, the board or panel determines which of two proposals is ranked higher and supports its respective verdicts with qualitative comparative arguments. Of course, this method may not be suitable for funders for which grades are important for other, e.g. legal, reasons.

Practice examples

HRB: Structuring research assessment procedures

The Health Research Board (HRB), Ireland's principal health research funder, aims to have a minimum of three scientific peer reviews and two public reviews conducted at Stage 1 of the application assessment process, in order to shortlist proposals that scored highest to proceed to the panel for Stage 2. The public reviewers do not give a score, but a rating and feedback on the quality of public and patient involvement (PPI) included.

Any proposals that have outlier scores from the peer review process are brought through to the panel and scheduled for discussion at the start of the day. The panel is allocated applications based on their area of expertise. Each application receives one primary

reviewer and one secondary reviewer, to focus on the specific application and independently assess and score in advance of the meeting. Written feedback and a preliminary score are requested in advance of the panel and the discussion on the day is formatted as follows for each application:

Discussion of Applications

Each application will be discussed for 15 mins in the following format:

Primary Reviewer (5 minutes)

The primary reviewer will summarise the strengths and weaknesses of the application based on their assessment, summarising comments from the peer and public reviews, and highlight any concerns that remain following the written applicant response

Secondary Reviewer (5 minutes)

The secondary reviewer will comment on any additional strengths and weaknesses they noted and highlight any additional concerns that remain following the written applicant response

Panel Discussion (3 minutes)

The remaining panel members will then have an opportunity to comment on their assessment of the application, highlighting any strengths or weaknesses that have not been addressed

Preliminary Score Allocated (2 minutes)

The primary and secondary reviewer reveal their initial independent scores and a preliminary consensus score, in line with the assessment criteria and scoring narrative provided in the assessment guidelines will be agreed by the panel as a whole. The Panel should also advise on any conditions of funding during this discussion.

Final Discussion, Ranking and Recommendations

At the end of a session, once all applications have been reviewed and discussed, HRB staff will provide an overview of the preliminary consensus scores and ranking. The panel will have the opportunity to discuss all applications again as required, and guided by the chair, will agree the final ranking around a cut-off point for funding. The Panel will make final recommendations for funding, agree any conditions of funding as necessary and also make recommendations for a reserve list for funding if applicable and quality depending. The chair acts as an independent guide to progress the discussions and ensure there's no unconscious bias and consensus obtained.

RCF: Structuring research assessment procedures

The Research Council of Finland (RCF), Finland's main public scientific funder, aims to conduct two scientific peer reviews during Stage 1 of the evaluation process for

applications submitted to the winter call. Typically, these reviewers also serve as panel members in Stage 2.

Applications that receive a grade of 5 or 6 (on a scale from 1 to 6) from at least one reviewer will be shortlisted and proceed to Stage 2 of the assessment process – the panel discussion. Applications reviewed by only one expert will also proceed to the panel stage. Less competitive applications that receive an overall grade of 1–4 from both reviewers will not be discussed in the panel meeting. However, their individual reviews will be given to the decision-maker and the applicants.

Reviewers are assigned applications based on their expertise. Each reviewer evaluates the assigned applications independently and submits both a numerical grade and written feedback prior to the panel meeting. All panel members will have access to the applications and the reviews before the meeting (except those applications that have a conflict of interest). The discussion on the day is formatted as follows for each application:

Discussion of Applications

Applications are generally discussed in order of strength, beginning with those that received a grade of 5 or 6 from both reviewers. The panel Chair is encouraged to allocate more time to these stronger applications as well as to cases where there is a significant discrepancy between the two reviewers' assessments. The Chair facilitates the discussion, ensures fair evaluation and that consensus is reached.

Each application is discussed for approximately 5–10 minutes, following the structure below:

Reviewers

The two appointed reviewers present their assessments, focusing on the application's key strengths and weaknesses.

Read-only/Reader

In particular, when the reviewers' opinions differ significantly, a third panel member can be assigned as a "read-only" or "reader". They will be requested to read the application and form a general impression before the panel meeting and their perspective can play a crucial role in the panel discussion.

Final Grade Allocation

Also, other panel members are invited to comment and raise any additional points or concerns. The panel then discusses and agrees on a final overall rating for the application. If the final grade is 5 or 6, sub-ratings for specific review criteria will also be decided.

Application Ranking and Final Review Report

At the end of the process, the panel ranks all applications that received a final grade of 5 or 6 within each funding instrument. The ranking is based on the review criteria and the instrument-specific objectives outlined in the review forms.

One reviewer will serve as the summariser during the panel meeting, drafting the panel's summary assessment of the application. Another reviewer will act as the checker, with the ability to suggest modifications before approving the summary. This summary highlights the proposal's main strengths and weaknesses, supported by justifications.

Funding Decision

Funding decisions are made by the decision-making bodies based on the final review reports, application rankings, the Research Council's science policy objectives, and their own established policies. These criteria and policies are published on the website prior to the opening of each call. However, the decision-making bodies have the power to decide whether to fund applications regardless of the panel rankings. Justifications for each funding decision are provided in the official decision notice.

ESF: Panel meeting protocol and preparation

The European Science Foundation (ESF) follows a structured protocol to ensure that panel meetings dedicate sufficient time in collective discussion to all applications under assessment. In advance of the meeting, panel members receive comprehensive guidelines and a live briefing covering the call background, panel and chair's mandate, the evaluation criteria, and the step-by-step protocol of the meeting. The briefings of the panel and the chairs are particularly useful for a shared interpretation of the evaluation criteria among the panel members.

Each proposal is assigned to two or sometimes three rapporteurs, with the lead rapporteur selected for closest disciplinary match. Rapporteurs prepare independent pre-assessments, submitted online, which are visible to all panel members ahead of the meeting (but only once all rapporteurs have submitted their pre-assessments). As a rule, five to eight applications can be assigned to individual panel members (depending on the panel size and disciplinary coverage). Rapporteurs are usually given between three to four weeks to prepare their individual pre-assessments and prepare for the meeting. Where applications have been assessed by external reviewers (different from the panel members) prior to the panel meeting, panel rapporteurs consider these reports but are also expected to critically evaluate the application and contribute their own assessment (if their judgement on certain elements differs from that of the external reviewers, proper argumentation needs to be provided in the pre-assessment). While rapporteurs carry primary responsibility for in-depth review, all panel members are asked to familiarise themselves at least with the main elements of all applications within the (sub-)panel's remit, ensuring that discussion benefits from the broadest collective expertise.

Panel meetings are structured to balance efficiency and depth. In some cases, the panels are divided into smaller disciplinary sub-panels to ensure a more in-depth discussion. Rapporteurs first summarise the proposal, external reviews, and any applicant rebuttals, as well as their own assessment, after which the full panel discusses each application. A dedicated ESF scientific panel secretary supports the chair and ensures that the protocol

is followed throughout; the panel secretaries are also the ones who set up the panel and made the allocations of applications to panel members. Prior to the meeting, the secretary prepares a summary document that consolidates all pre-assessment, external reviewers, and rebuttal data, helping structure the discussion. In some cases, the panel secretary provides the panel chair with summary statistics of the scores to detect systematically harsh or lenient reviewers and to adjust for individual scoring biases. The order of discussion is confirmed with the chair. It is common that non-fundable proposals, where rapporteurs are in consensus, are briefly discussed first. Then the panel can focus their discussion on other applications, with particular focus on the applications where rapporteurs' assessments diverge. Each application is evaluated according to the established criteria, and panel members typically agree on common scores and the associated opinion for each criterion that are then used to establish the final ranking. There are usually at least two rounds of discussion, and in most cases, voting is not required, as decisions are reached by consensus.

3.4.2 Recognizing the role of the board or panel chair(s)

When designing review procedures, it is easy to focus on structural aspects and neglect the "human" side. One dimension belonging to the latter which is particularly easy to underestimate is the way in which Panel or Board discussions are chaired. Yet, questions such as the following have a great impact on the mode of review, and indirectly on funding outcomes: How, and from what groups, are panel or board chairs *recruited*? What *qualities* should a chair possess? What *responsibilities* and *rights* do chairs have? On what *aspects* or *aims* should a chair put particular focus? How should chairs be *supported*, their work *recognized*? Among other things, all these questions are of importance to the concern of this paper: how to ensure a primarily qualitative mode of review.

Between funding agencies, practices vis-à-vis chairs and chairing differ quite widely (more on that below). However, the WG members wish to jointly emphasize five points surrounding the issue of chairing. Firstly, as chairs have great impact on the course of funding discussions, funding agencies should devote substantive thought and care to the abovementioned questions around chairs and chairing. Secondly, whatever exact combination of qualities funders seek in (potential) chairs, these combinations are likely to be rare and hence of particular value. For that reason, funding agencies should appropriately recognize and reward chairing duties.¹³ Thirdly and connectedly, funding agencies should seek to develop, or support the development, of such qualities, by training, communication and perhaps incentivization. Fourthly, selecting a good chair cannot simply follow publication- or funding-based statistics; it should (also) be based on RFO officers' personal acquaintance with the research communities and/or the research management communities. Fifth and finally, for panels or board chairs to work effectively,

¹³ Note that there is a CoARA Working Group dedicated to the topic of Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review (<https://www.coara.org/working-groups/wg-recognizing-and-rewarding-peer-review/>). The reader is advised to refer to this Working Group's recommendations.)

they must be appropriately supported by the funding agency. This includes well-prepared documents, well-working discussion procedures and aids and perhaps access to, and briefings with, programme managers/officers and/or administration staff before and/or during the discussion.

Since the expectations and approaches of funding agencies and funding lines differ, the demands on chairs are also far from being uniform. The following is a sketch of the diversity of funders' answers to the questions at the head of this section. The differences start with the approach to who chairs meetings. While most funders secure researchers to act as chairs and the agency attends in an administrative capacity, others utilise members of the agency's staff to chair review board or panel meetings. Yet others use both academic and administrative chairs in meetings, sometimes as equals, sometimes with the latter taking a supporting role. Among the qualities which chairs should possess, the funders' answers range from academic excellence, reputable experience as a researcher, experience as a reviewer, sense of fairness (one might speak of epistemic fairness), ability to balance discussion and moderate ensuring all voices heard and consensus-seeking discussion style or personality to interest in scientific debate and scientific learning without bias or manipulation. In some funding agencies, chairs are members of the panel or board - this could mean that they have a vote in the final decisions -, in others, chairs are formally removed from the decision itself. Funders also differ on the strategies or interventions they expect from chairs. In some cases, chairs are seen as formal arbiters, for example mainly making sure that all voices are heard and all criteria covered. In others, their involvement in the scientific debate is envisaged or sought.

With an eye to this paper's main question, the WG endorses the view that chairs should not simply register reviews, grades or arguments, but play an active role in their interpretation and weighing. They are to approach scientific arguments, for instance arguments supporting a given grade or funding recommendation offered in an external review or by a panel member, as scientists themselves. It is a chair's responsibility that all relevant claims which a panel makes or endorses are backed up with appropriate reasoning and are (thus) consistent. Furthermore, the WG endorses the view that chairs ought to be aware of the main sources of bias in decision-making, as such awareness is crucial to a fair and scientifically appropriate interpretation and weighing of arguments.

3.4.3 Discussing individual project budgets

In most funding programmes, the specification of a project budget is an important aspect of the research proposal. This is the case whether the project budgets are flexible (in this case, applicants can set the project budget volume themselves and must justify it in their project proposal) or not (the project budget volumes within a funding programme are determined by the funder, and applicants are only asked to justify the cost items needed for their particular proposed project). Consequently, project budgets are discussed as part of the proposal discussion in the panel or board.

Some funders have found that encouraging or requiring reviewers or panel / board members to specifically assess and comment on project budgets can increase the

seriousness and depth of the proposal's qualitative assessment. Budget discussions often nudge evaluators to think seriously about the architecture of the proposed research project, which includes the time needed to achieve particular tasks, the number of persons or person-hours and equipment required to fulfil them, the probabilities of different possible outcomes, the adequacy of contingency plans and the like. Discussions of budgets may even induce evaluators to imagine themselves as the project's investigators, which can increase the seriousness of their assessment, and help them consider unobvious project details.

Besides simply asking reviewers or panel/board members to comment on project budgets, funders can also allow them to make suggestions regarding modifications (which, for administrative reasons, usually comes down to suggestions of budget *cuts*, as reviewers are typically not mandated to add cost items which were not requested, or to increase project demands). However, while this policy may have the additional benefit of keeping costs under control, it may also have negative side effects, ranging from the perverse incentive to applicants to build-in "budget buffers" in anticipation of cuts, to panels making exaggerated use of budget cuts in order to approve more proposals, thus harming the feasibility of granted projects. There may be measures against the latter (for instance, FWO allows panels to cut project budgets but keeps the saved funds in a separate account which is not immediately accessible to them), but the issue highlights the need for great care, as newly introduced measures can always have unintended consequences.

3.4.4 Information management during the review and panel discussion

Some funders have collected experience with the management of information during review: what data are available to which reviewer at what stage of the assessment? One reason for withholding certain kinds of information at certain stages is to suppress biases (for instance, some funders suppress personal information about the applicant in initial case discussions; some funders only allow rapporteurs to see the identity of external reviewers and their discipline(s) to better contextualise their reviews, while other panel members only see the anonymized external reviews to avoid any bias). But information management can also be used in order to deepen the qualitative discussion among board or panel members.

Some funding organisations, for example, which work with online review systems, only allow a panel member to read the opinions of other panel members after submitting their own preliminary review. In this way, they prevent panelists from being overly influenced by, or even taking over, other reviewers' opinions rather than coming to their own verdict on the exclusive basis of the proposal. For the same reason, funders may not disclose all panelists' individual grades to other panelists or only do so after a qualitative discussion has taken place. The point of sharing grades - for those funders which work with grades - may, in fact, primarily be to collectively check whether preliminary grades match the qualitative reasons on which the board or panel has converged during the discussion. Another example of information management is the withholding of budget data (budgets of proposed projects and/or budgets available for funding) to ensure that proposals which

are discussed after the available funding slots are already “filled” are not unfairly disadvantaged.

In general, the WG recommends that funders carefully check which information relevant to the review is disclosed (or emphasized) at which point in the review, with a view to supporting an unbiased, open and serious discussion of all competitive proposals.

3.4.5 Concluding the discussion(s): Coming to a funding decision

Funders employ many diverse strategies to conclude proposal discussions with clear funding recommendations, i.e. slates of acceptances and rejections of individual project proposals.

At first sight, the question of the optimal conclusion may not appear particularly pressing, as the case discussions themselves typically yield a ranking (whether a grades-based ranking or simply an ordinal ranking of funding priorities). If this is the case, the funder only needs to apply a cut-off line, which is determined by the available funds.

However, particularly in systems without grades, it is not at all obvious how to come to a stable slate of ranked proposals. Moreover, even with grades, it is very often the case that in the course of the discussion, the grades – which are usually supplied by different panel or board members or by different external reviewers – need to be calibrated and re-calibrated. Furthermore, when grading or ranking proposals, it is frequently the case that individual proposals raise systematic questions whose answers have relevance for other proposals and hence necessitate reopening other case discussions. Finally, it is common to find projects around the financial cut-off line which are very similar in quality, prompting the need for particularly close looks at these projects.

Many funders have found that in light of these points, two considerations are of particular importance. Besides the consideration of adequate discussion time (discussed above in subsection 3.4.1), many funders would argue that if at all possible, funders should aim for consensus among panel or board members. Aiming for consensus, not just about the final slate of funding recommendations, but also about substantive questions which come up during case discussions (for example, questions about weights or interpretations of review criteria), increases the likelihood of a serious, qualitative assessment. In order to achieve this, funders typically reserve time, at the end of a panel or board discussion, to jointly check the pre-final slate of proposed decisions for consistency and formally agree on the entire slate.

Some, but not all, funders would also judge that encouraging pairwise comparisons between proposals, for example neighboring proposals on a preliminary ranking table, can yield useful discussions and (hence) stimulate a serious qualitative assessment of the relevant proposals. (For some funders, however, pairwise comparisons are discouraged or even prohibited to ensure that all proposals are assessed fairly and strictly on their own merits.)

SNSF: Creating a ranked list with Bayesian Ranking, funding decision including optional lottery procedure

At the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), after the evaluation panel has evaluated each proposal, a ranked list can be created. However, a classification based solely on average ratings is problematic. Perhaps some members did not vote on all proposals because of conflicts of interest. Or some are reluctant to give high marks, while others judge less harshly. Therefore, the SNSF applies a procedure based on the Bayesian Ranking. This statistical model takes into account random fluctuations and other uncertain factors. In this process, each proposal is compared with every other proposal to create the final ranking. Based on this ranking and the available funding, the responsible committee of the Research Council determines a cut-off point for funding ("funding line"). If your proposal is above the funding line, it will be funded; but if it is below, you will unfortunately not receive any funding. The funding line might run through a group of proposals that are of exactly the same scientific quality. The responsible committee of the Research Council may then make a random selection by drawing lots; the proposals that are drawn will be funded. Alternatively, the SNSF may refrain from funding the entire group.

For more information, see <https://www.snf.ch/en/6cs2wnfJtcfFDL6o/page/evaluation-procedure>

Heyard, R., Ott, M., Salanti, G., & Egger, M. (2022). Rethinking the Funding Line at the Swiss National Science Foundation: Bayesian Ranking and Lottery *Statistics and Public Policy*, 9(1), 110-121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2330443X.2022.2086190>

3.5 After the review

3.5.1 Formulating decisions

Most – although not all – funders provide applicants with detailed feedback from the review (see WG survey results in annex S 2). Often, in addition to the (usually anonymized¹⁴) reviews, funders include a written justification of the panel’s or board’s decision (sometimes referred to as ‘panel consensus reports’). This is not only done for reasons of transparency, or because it is required by law. The feedback is also meant as a constructive aid for the applicant’s intended research project or future applications, particularly when the funder rejected the proposal. Constructive feedback from the panel, emanating from the panel discussion and explicitly linked with the criteria for both rejections and approvals, also makes the process more transparent.

If the application has also been reviewed externally before the panel meeting, those comments may be included in the written feedback or provided separately. In addition, some funders offer the possibility for applicants to contact RFO staff for further aid in interpreting the decision text.

All funders who provide such feedback report that it is usually very carefully read by applicants. Applicants not only appreciate specific suggestions or recommendations, but they also process indirect information to strategically plan (or fine-tune) future research activities. Indeed, funders often learn that individual formulations or vocabulary are intensively discussed among researchers and can have very weighty consequences on strategic decisions, up to and including career decisions.

Funders’ feedback, in other words, strongly reflects into the research community, and should therefore be taken very seriously by funders. Of course, this point is relevant to the aims of CoARA. As the feedback which an applicant receives reflects how a funder weighs previous achievements and contributions and planned future activities, funders are well advised to consider the CoARA commitments even when formulating votes. If a board, for example, noted a particular previous scientific contribution which may not have taken the form of a classical journal article, the funder should consider including this information in their textual justification, as it would have done for a classical kind of contribution. In general, not only the appropriate consideration of all kinds of scientific contribution types matters to assessment reform. Showing that this is the case via feedback texts also helps.

Moreover, if a particular scientific idea sparked a discussion in the board or panel meeting, it is advisable to mention this, or even to use the justificatory text to engage scientifically with the idea. This is not only true for negative decisions, but also for positive decisions. From the perspective of research assessment reform, it helps if an applicant learns that their research ideas were understood, taken up, and led to the grant. Such information is more valuable to the researcher – and more valuable from the perspective of assessment reform –

¹⁴ Not all funders anonymize reviews. In Finland, for example, public funders are required by law to reveal reviewer names.

than, say, the name of the journal in which a previous finding appeared, or of the grant which made it possible. In general, if members of the scientific community understand that their scientific reasoning intellectually engages the review boards and is capable of driving positive funding decisions, they may find themselves less compelled to optimize their research towards the production of indirect quality markers.

Practice example

FCT, FWO, and DFG: Dealing with quantitative proxies in discussions of projects

At some funders, for instance FCT (Portugal) or FWO (Belgium), quantitative proxies are – as a matter of policy – not to be used as arguments and, thus, not included in the panel comments. Other organisations, while not prohibiting the use of quantitative proxies outright, promote particular care in handling them. The DFG (Germany), for instance, does not consider quantitative indicators such as impact factors and h-indices as part of its review process. However, if reviewers mention indirect indicators such as numbers of publications or names of journals, DFG's officers are committed to ensuring that this information is embedded in a discussion of what the indirect quality or qualification indicator means in the respective discipline and complemented by a qualitative assessment of the research content.

3.5.2 Recognizing, rewarding and debriefing reviewers

Once a funder has secured external reviews for a proposal, the question of how to follow up with the reviewers may appear to be of low importance. This is not the case, however. Not only is it appropriate to recognize the significant – often unpaid – work. Reviewing a proposal is also an important aspect of scientific communication, and as such calls for a response – at the minimum an information regarding the decision, ideally a decision and justification by the responsible board or panel which explicitly addresses the review(s). Such a reaction is not only called for, but also benefits the funding organisation. Anecdotal – but very broad and consistent – evidence suggests that a reviewer who is recognized and included in scientific communication in the way described is much more likely to review again, and to review in a serious and qualitative way. The WG wishes to point out that another CoARA Working Group entitled “Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review”¹⁵ is discussing the issue in more detail; the reader is advised to consult this WG’s recommendations.

Among the innovative practices and ideas recorded in the WG’s respective survey (more on which can be found in annex S 2) are: recognizing reviewing duties through the ORCID profile, providing recognition letters to institutions in which reviewers work, providing grant extensions (where applicable) for the time spent reviewing, reimbursing additional child-care costs associated with reviewing time and using innovative tools such as the Review Quality Collector (RQC, <https://reviewqualitycollector.org/>).

¹⁵ <https://www.coara.org/working-groups/wg-recognizing-and-rewarding-peer-review/>

References

- Anli, Z., Bergmans, J., & van der Weijden, I. (2022). *Career pathways in research: the current data landscape (RoRI Working Paper No.8)*. Research on Research Institute. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.19609512.v1
- Arentoft, M., Berghmans, S., Borrell-Damian, L., Bottaro, S., Faure, J.-E., Gaillard, V., . . . Stroobants, K. (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.13480728
- Ayoubi, C., Pezzoni, M., & Visentin, F. (2021). Does It Pay To Do Novel Science? The Selectivity Patterns in Science Funding. *Science and Public Policy*, 48(5), 635-648. doi:10.1093/scipol/scab031
- DORA. (2021). *Findings from the Health Research Board Ireland on the Implementation of a Narrative CV*. Retrieved Mai 2, 2024, from <https://sfdora.org/2021/04/12/findings-from-the-health-research-board-ireland-on-the-implementation-of-a-narrative-cv/>
- DORA. (2026). Practical Guide for Responsible Research Assessment for Research Funding Organizations. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.18402271
- European Commission, & Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2020). Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation. *Publications Office of the European Union*. Retrieved from <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/316197>
- Fritch, R., Hatch, A., Hazlett, H., & Vinkenbunrg, C. (2021). Using Narrative CVs: Process Optimization and bias mitigation. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5799413
- Kolarz, P., Vingre, A., Vinnik, A., Neto, A., Vergara, C., Rodriguez, C. O., . . . Sutinen, L. (2023). *Review of Peer Review Final Report Technopolis*. Retrieved 10 30, 2024, from <https://www.technopolis-group.com/report/review-of-peer-review/>
- Leptin, M. (2024). *Evaluation of research proposals: the why and what of the ERC's recent changes*. Retrieved from https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-02/Evaluation_of_research_proposals.pdf
- Marras, C. (2011). *European Peer Review Guide - Integrating Policies and Practices into Coherent Procedures*. European Science Foundation. Retrieved November 5, 2025, from https://www.esf.org/fileadmin/user_upload/esf/European_Peer_Review_Guide_2011.pdf
- Morris, J., & Saenen, B. (2024). *Survey Report 'Strategic Approaches to and Research Assessment of Open Science'*. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.13961123
- National Institutes of Health. (2024). Simplified Peer Review Framework. Retrieved on 06/08/2024 from <https://grants.nih.gov/policy/peer/simplifying-review/framework.htm>

- Research on Research Institute (RORI), Butters, A., Benson Marshall, M., Pinfield, S., Stafford, T., Bondarenko, A. N., . . . Denecke, H. (2025). Applicants as Reviewers: Evaluating the Risks, Benefits, and Potential of Distributed Peer Review for Grant Funding Allocations (RoRI Working Paper No. 17). *Research on Research Institute. Preprint*. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.29994841.v2
- Research on Research Institute (RoRI), Varga, J., & Kaltenbrunner, W. (2025). RoRI Insights: Implementing Narrative CVs - Five recommendations for Funders. *Research on Research Institute. Report*. doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.28524755.v1
- Résumé Resources Library: support for adopting narrative CVs - UKRI*. (2025). Retrieved November 4, 2025, from <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/research-and-innovation-culture/supporting-the-community-adoption-of-r4r-like-narrative-cvs/resume-resources-library-support-for-adopting-narrative-cvs/>
- Schiffbänker, H., Sauer, A., & Peterson, H. (2024). GRANteD D6.3 Reforming peer review practices - lessons learned from the implementation of gender equality policies in Reserach Funding Organisations. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10613191
- Science Europe, & Morris, J. (2024). Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10602234
- Technopolis. (2020). Science Europe Study on Research Assessment Practices. *Zenodo*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4915999
- UNESCO. (2021). UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. doi:10.54677/MNMMH8546
- Veugelers, R., Wang, J., & Stephan, P. (2025). Do funding agencies select and enable novel research: evidence from ERC. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 1-18. doi:10.1080/10438599.2025.2486344

Organisations affiliated to this WG

The following organisations have endorsed this paper (in alphabetical order):

**Research Council
of Finland**

**Australian Government
National Health and
Medical Research Council**

**Research Council
of Norway**

UNIVERSIDADE
LUSÓFONA

CENTRO
UNIVERSITÁRIO
LISBOA

<i>Name of organisation affiliated to this WG</i>	<i>Country/Region</i>
National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC)	Australia
Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Lundbeck Foundation	Danmark
European Commission	Europe
European Science Foundation (ESF)	Europe
Science Europe	Europe
Young Academy of Europe	Europe
Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Research Council of Finland (RCF)	Finland
École d'ingénieurs du numérique (isep)	France
Institut National du Cancer (INCa)	France
Alexander von Humboldt Foundation	Germany
German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Global Young Academy (GYA)	Global
International Federation of Scholarly Associations of Management (IFSAM)	Global
Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA)	Hungary
Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Research Ireland	Ireland
Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Dutch Organisation for knowledge and innovation in health, healthcare and well-being (ZonMw)	Netherlands
Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Research Council of Norway	Norway
Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Universidade Lusófona	Portugal
Universidad San Pablo CEU	Spain
Knowledge Foundation (KKS)	Sweden
Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden

Working Group Overview

Working Groups are key communities of practice that work to implement research assessment reform in specific thematic areas. Participating members exchange knowledge, learn from each other's experience, discuss and develop outputs to advance research assessment and support the implementation of members' commitments.

The overall objective of the Working Group "Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals" was discuss all matters relating to the handling and assessment of research project proposals, with a view to improving alignment with the principles and commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

The WG focused on three overarching topics:

Criteria for the selection of research projects and innovative approaches to review processes: The Working Group exchanged information and learned mutually on how quality is understood and operationalised by research funding and other organisations through their assessment criteria. It shared experiences and lessons learnt and identified general trends and evolutions. It also discussed innovative approaches to the selection, including approaches beyond peer review, and the challenge of focusing on quality and impact, at scale.

Selection of and guidance to reviewers on responsible research assessment practices: The Working Group exchanged experiences and good practices as regards the selection of and guidance to experts and associated materials and their effectiveness. It addressed how reviewers can be selected and provided with adequate, high-quality training on the selection criteria and processes, how to use indicators appropriately, and how to apply high standards of ethics and integrity in their decision-making. It also touched on how to recognise and support the work of peer-reviewers.

Information requested from applicants: The Working Group exchanged practices on the information requested from applicants, how to balance quantitative and qualitative information, as well as how to recognise a diversity of outputs, tasks, practices, skills and competences. It also explored further aspects, including the appropriate time(s) to request information from applicants.

CoARA

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated. Current research assessment methods rely heavily on publication-based metrics such as citation counts, and often fail to recognise the wide array of contributions made by researchers.

Over 800 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and guiding principles to implement reform in the assessment of research, researchers, and research organisations, outlined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) published in July 2022 which provides an outline for reform and implementation.

Find out more about CoARA at www.coara.org.

Annexes

Survey 1. The understanding and operationalisation of “research quality”

S 1.1 Introduction and method

The WG has set itself the task to identify improvement potentials in the ways academic research funding agencies assess project proposals. “Improvement”, in this context, is to be read in the light of the core CoARA commitments, principally the commitment 1 to recognize a diversity of contributions and careers in science, and the commitment 2¹⁶ of scientific quality and its operationalization through the evaluation procedures; WP 2 focuses on the selection and guidance of reviewers and assessment panel members; and WP 3 discusses the information requested from applicants.

This report represents the first step of WP 1, which is to take stock of the WG member organisations’ understanding of *research quality* and how it relates to the assessment criteria used in their evaluation of projects. The report also discusses the WG members’ approaches and practices of selecting and guiding of reviewers.

The method chosen by the WG members contributing to WP1 and WP 2 was a survey with yes/no, multiple choice as well as open-answer (text) questions conducted through LimeSurvey (see S 1.3.1 and S 2.4). The survey was prepared by the Chairs of WP1 and WP 2 with help by colleagues from their respective organisation. It was carried out in February and March 2024. The questions were selected with a view to comparability with earlier surveys, notably one carried out by Science Europe in 2019.

The basis of the following report are the answers of 35 funding organisations (or their associations) to the survey questions. Where appropriate, answers by 13 non-funders (universities, associations of applicants) are taken into account or used to amplify or give nuance to emergent findings.

¹⁶ The members of the WP 1 subgroup have provisionally agreed to differentiate between the *concept* of scientific quality (denoting a general understanding of scientific quality as different from non-quality oriented aspects and on which the various members of WP 1 find themselves in broad agreement) and various *conceptions* of scientific quality which allow for significant differences in content and in the weights of their respective conceptual components.

Figure S 1: Question 2 “Please state the type of your organisation”. n=48

The respondents are mostly CoARA Working Group members (36). Some non-WG CoARA members (6) and a few non CoARA members (6) have also contributed to the survey. The main focus of WP 1 was to include the views of a diverse range of funding organisations. For this reason, some funders outside of the CoARA community were invited to participate in the survey. All respondents are authorized staff of their respective organisations (funders and others) and have responded to the survey questions in light of their experience with their respective employers.

Based on previous discussions within the subsection of WG members working on WP 1 (henceforth “WP 1 group”), most of the questions of the survey did not distinguish between “(high) scientific quality” and “scientific excellence”. (The one exception is question 3, which asked for each term whether it explicitly figures as a funding criterion.) While not explicitly treating these terms as interchangeable, all questions (with the aforementioned exception) addressed a disjunction of the two terms (e.g. “Does your organisation operate with a formal definition of “research/scientific quality” or “research/scientific excellence?”). The WP 1 group itself operates with a preliminary understanding that these terms are closely connected, in that “scientific quality” denotes a scale, the higher regions of which are denoted by “scientific excellence”. On this understanding, “scientific excellence” is synonymous with “high scientific quality” or “very high scientific quality”.

S 1.2 Main findings

S 1.2.1 Research quality not typically explicitly defined

Although the majority of funders prominently mention “(high) research quality” or “research excellence” in their communications with the public as well as with applicants and reviewers (question 3; fig. S2), fewer than half of the funders state that they have an explicit definition of the term(s). When the entries in the respective text fields are considered, the proportion

of funders operating with an explicit definition appears even lower, but also harder to determine exactly. Rather than laying down an explicit definition in a strict sense, most answers (given by the funders who stated that they operate with a definition) are entered in the form of lists or discussions of criteria, conditions or questions intended to guide reviewers. (The text-based answers are reproduced below.)

Figure S 2: Questions 4 "Does your organisation operate with a formal definition of "research/scientific quality" or "research /scientific excellence"?" and question 6 conditional on a positive answer to 4: "Do the funding criteria refer to this definition of "research/scientific quality" resp. "research/scientific excellence"?. n=48

S 1.2.2 Review criteria corresponding with "research quality" or "research excellence"

Preliminary remarks

As stated above, some funders, in their answer to the question on the definition of research quality or excellence, opted to give a list of criteria or point to a website with information on such criteria. These are typically the criteria reviewers are asked to consider when assessing research project proposals. This would seem a reasonable approach in terms of describing or defining research quality or excellence. However, some caveats should be kept in mind:

- The weighing of criteria against one another is often underspecified and therefore (at least partly) left to the reviewer. (For more details on weighing of criteria, see below, under "Weighing of criteria".)
- Review criteria used by funders are sometimes scales (for example "originality") and sometimes variables taking "yes" or "no" as their value (for example "is highly original").
- Review criteria sometimes address areas which are not (understood as) falling under "research quality" or "excellence".
- Besides criteria used in the ex-ante evaluation of research projects (via the assessment of proposals), there are other ways in which funders promote high quality projects: for example, by setting certain (often formal) prerequisites for funding, by adjusting their funding strategies in light of ex post evaluations of

projects or by various ways of setting and promoting high standards of scientific work.

Aspects listed by funders as constituting “research quality” (q 7)

There is a continuum of importance which funders assign to different aspects when characterizing “(high) scientific quality” or “scientific excellence”. On this continuum, there is a first group of aspects which are in use by a large majority of funders (i.e. between 32 and 27 positive answers in terms of the respondents’ organisations finding the aspects very/moderately important). These are:

- Novelty / originality of the scientific question (“very important”: 29, “important”: 3 times selected)
- Methodological or theoretical rigour of the proposal (“very important”: 23, “important”: 9 times selected)
- Clarity of the scientific question (“very important”: 28, “important”: 3 times selected)
- Consideration of the current state of the art (“very important”: 22, “important”: 9 times selected)
- Feasibility of the proposed project (“very important”: 22, “important”: 8 times selected)
- Expected academic significance or impact of the project (“very important”: 22, “important”: 8 times selected) - note that this criterion features *academic* significance or impact; in the survey, another criterion was also listed which focuses on *non-academic* significance or impact. That criterion scored noticeably lower. Of course, like all criteria, this criterion is somewhat open to interpretation.
- Novelty or originality of approach or method(s) to be used (“very important”: 18, “important”: 11 times selected)
- Consideration of ethical aspects of the proposed project (here, the question appears salient whether this criterion figures under “scientific quality”, see below.) (“very important”: 19, “important”: 9 times selected)
- “Quality and/or relevance of preliminary work” (“very important”: 9, “important”: 18 times selected - it is noteworthy, though, that for this aspect, the number of respondents selecting “very important” drops sharply; a high number of respondents, however, selected “important”.)

Among the remaining criteria mentioned in the survey, no clear groupings can be identified. The diagram given on the following page lists them in descending order of importance according to survey respondents. Note that the diagram only considers the responses given by funders (answer option “no answer” not shown). If non-funders are also considered, the result is only marginally different.

How important are each of the following aspects in your organisation's understanding of research quality resp. research excellence in the assessment of research proposals? (n = 35 funders)

Figure S 3: Question 7 "How important are each of the following aspects in your organisation's understanding of research quality resp. research excellence in the assessment of research proposals?". n=35 funders

The results are not to be taken as an argument for a conception of “research quality” which features only or mainly the first group of criteria or quality dimensions, but simply as evidence of differing conceptions with an overlap around certain dimensions of quality.

It is also noteworthy that there are funders which do not treat certain aspects as falling under or contributing to quality (for example the “expected non-academic significance or impact”). Some aspects may also score low because funders feel that they are not appropriate in each review or for each project. The same may be true for “consideration of sex or gender”. For some types of project - or for some disciplines - this may be an important consideration, for others it may not be.

It may be worthwhile to conduct the survey again in the future to determine whether there are differences over time.

Further aspects and their role with respect to “research quality” or “excellence” (q 9)

In a further question (question 9), survey respondents were asked to classify each item on a list of criteria with respect to its respective *role* in review: do they view it as contributing to determine “research quality” or “excellence”, do they view it as an independent criterion, or do they not use the dimension in question as a review criterion at all? (There was also a “not sure” option.)

The answers present a quite heterogeneous field of funding organisations. There are quite different ways in which criteria are understood, and there are many dimensions which figure as review criteria for some funders, while not figuring as criteria at all for other funders.

Please note that the diagram below only includes the answers given by funding organisations.

Figure S 4: Question 9 "Please indicate whether your organisation considers any of the following criteria when making funding decisions". n=35 funders

Some answers appear particularly noteworthy. “Public outreach / science communication” and “Open Access / Open Science” are considered by some funders as integral to scientific quality, while others do not include these aspects in their sets of review criteria at all. This may mirror different positions in ongoing debates in science policy. The focus of these debates is not primarily whether public outreach or open science are *valuable* – there is an emerging consensus that they are – but what the most appropriate ways are to support them. While some funders encourage or require applicants of individual projects to include public outreach activities and to include open science measures in individual projects – and document planned activities or measures in their proposals –, other funders see the burden to further such practices not on individual researchers or individual projects, but at the level of institutions or the science system as a whole. The latter thus opt against evaluating individual researchers or projects against such review criteria. This may also be the case for some other aspects, viz. “inclusion of non-academic stakeholders” or “citizen science”, although there may be more controversy around the precise meanings of these terms and hence the value of these aspects among funders.

Another interesting matter concerns the role of “expertise / qualification of the applicant (or research team)” and perhaps also “past scientific performance of the applicant (or research team)”: do these criteria contribute to determining the quality of the proposal / project, or do they figure as an independent criterion? There are various possible interpretations for the variety of views. It could point to different conceptions of “research quality” or “excellence”, or to different procedures in the review process. It is also possible that the differences are caused by an indeterminacy in the question whether the object of review is the *proposed project* or the *proposal*.

Finally, some of the aspects listed in the question may have variable weight as criteria, depending on the kind of project under review. “Risk analysis”, “dual use concerns” or “measures planned to foster research careers” may play a significant role in the evaluation of some kinds of project, but be virtually irrelevant in the evaluation of other kinds. A proposal regarding an exploratory study should give some thought to the risk of failure; the same may not be true for a meta-analysis or a replication study. A study in the Humanities may not consider “dual use concerns” in the way that a project on turbine design should. Small projects need not concern themselves with career development, while this may be important for larger, coordinated projects with significant funds for staff. Due to such differences, there may be some distortion in the answers to this question, if certain kinds of project figure more prominently in the portfolio of some funders than in that of others.

Text-based information on the concept of “research excellence” or “research quality”

Some funders stated that they are operating with a formal definition of “research quality” or “research excellence” and proceeded to give information on it.

As stated above, even these responses tend to take the form of lists of aspects or criteria but contrary to the multiple choice answers to questions 7 and 9, these are full texts outlining considered and coherent approaches.

They differ on various scales / in various ways:

- **From complex to compact**
The answers range from that of a funder operating with a long list of criteria, each of which is characterized in relatively high level of detail, to that of a funder with an extremely compact set of criteria (“bold, creative, high-quality”).
- **Focus on expectation of outcome vs focus on quality of proposed work**
One funder lays the focus squarely on the expected output of proposed projects while other funders put the emphasis on how proposed projects are devised. In the latter, the expected outputs may, of course, also play an important role, but there are differences in the nuances of explicit textual answers.
- **How much indication is given about the weighing of criteria**
In the set of answers, one funder makes it a point to list the evaluation criteria in alphabetical order so as not to suggest a ranking of priorities among them. Other funders indicate or even specify the relative weights of their criteria or begin their lists of criteria with those which are deemed key criteria. (For more information on the weighing of criteria, see below, under “Weighing of criteria”.)
- **Relative vs absolute conception of excellence**
One funder explicitly defines “excellent” as designating a top percentage of assessed projects (in the field, viewed internationally). From such a definition, it follows that were the whole field to improve in terms of other, material markers of quality, an erstwhile “excellent” project could be pushed out of this category, because a sufficient number of competitors come to occupy it. Other funders officially regard excellence in absolute terms (although presumably, all funders are forced to differentiate between to-be-funded and not-to-be-funded projects in view of financial limits, which either forces a distinction between fundability and excellence or implicitly re-introduces a relative conception of “excellence”).
- Of course, **there are also various kinds of difference in content.**
One important exemplary difference concerns the question whether – or to what extent – the qualification or academic standing of the applicant is understood as contributing to, or conceptually distinct from, the quality of the project (proposal). Another example of a difference in content concerns the role that the expected extra-scientific impact plays in the assessment of the project. Some funders consider it – even as a key criterion – while other funders make it a point to ignore this dimension in the assessment.

The given responses also shine a light on **commonalities**.

- Consistent with the quantitative data extracted from the answers to question 7, a very clear majority of the text-based answers give high prominence to **novelty or originality** in the questions addressed, in project design or employed methods. (Not all, though. There are funders for whom originality does not figure in the list of criteria; an example is a funder specializing in supporting medical research. Another funder states that it is a matter of policy to ask reviewers not to focus on the “novelty” of a project proposal, but instead on how the proposed project will contribute to the state of the art in the relevant discipline.) Funders, that is, value projects which

set themselves apart from other, supposedly more conservative or mainstream, projects, as a separate criterion from their expected scientific yield or progress. Other terms used under this heading include “bold(ness)” and “creative” respective “creativity”. Many funders which have entered text in this field have included some version of the expectation that excellent projects **significantly extend knowledge, break ground, enable or encompass scientific advances or go beyond the state of the art**. This is not typically spelled out in much detail, for instance in relation to other possible themes such as strengthening confidence of existing knowledge, filling out known gaps, or increasing exactness of extant data or predictions.

- Another common theme attaches to the project proposal itself; here, the condition is that it is **clear in hypothesis, question, work programme and/or method, rigorous and mindful of existing literature**.

Changes envisaged (q 11 and 12)

The survey results, and in particular the answers to questions 11 and 12, provide a glimpse into potential changes of funding criteria. In detail, out of a total of 48 answers to the two linked questions (other than Yes/No/NA, respondents had the opportunity to provide textual evidence), a total of 22 respondents answered that their organisation was considering the review of their criteria or the introduction of new ones. Out of these 22, 16 were funding organisations. Fourteen (14) respondents answered “No” to the question, but a small number of these (3) mentioned discussions and internal thinking on potential changes. Finally, 12 did not answer the question.

A complex picture emerges as regards the elements of change. The implemented or envisaged changes often pertain to the introduction of criteria concerning Open Science, and in particular the Open Access practices of researchers, but also citizen participation and involving stakeholders. Nonetheless, a wide array of themes relevant to responsible research assessment are reported to be included in review plans. These relate to: how grants can contribute to the career development, competences and research independence of early career researchers; introducing narrative CVs, strengthening criteria on inclusion and gender, promoting interdisciplinarity, reflecting both ecological and non-ecological sustainability. The answers to these questions give useful albeit partial insights regarding the possible directions that funders are exploring in relation to the reform process outlined by the ARRA.

Figure S 5: Question 11 “Is your organisation considering the review of any of the criteria listed above, or the introduction of new criteria?” n=48

Weighing of criteria (q 13-16)

In its questions 13 and 14, the survey addresses the weighing of criteria in the evaluation of research proposals. Question 13 asks whether the organisations give indication to their reviewers and/or granting committees about how to weigh the various criteria, to which 22 (and 17 out of 35 funders) respond with “yes, always” and 14 (10 out of 35 funders) with “no” and 6 (6 out of 35 funders) with “other”. 6 do not give an answer. It should be noted that the funders which responded “Other” or even “Yes” have strongly divergent understandings of the question and thus give indication on weighing of quite different granularity and exactness, as the answers to question 14 - “What indication regarding the weighing of criteria does your organisation give to its reviewers and/or granting committees?” - show. While there are funders which work with clear percentages associated with individual criteria, others assign weights only to broader categories of criteria or give looser indication, for example verbally or in the form of bands (“up to x %”). Furthermore, even among the funders which state that they indicate the relative weights of criteria, the latter may consist of or contain very broad criteria (for example “quality of the research proposal”, as opposed to “applicant’s skills and experience” and “research environment”).

All in all, with only some exceptions, in practice there is considerable room for reviewers to make their own weighing decisions in the programmes of the majority of funding organisations.

Two further survey questions dealing with the weighing of criteria are questions 15 and 16. Question 15 asks whether weights of criteria differ between different funding lines of funding programmes within a funding organisation, and question 16 asks whether such differences are communicated to the reviewers and/or granting committees. To the first one, the majority of respondents (26, of these 21 respondents represent funding organisations) answer affirmatively, while 13 answer “no” (11 of these are funders) and 9 do not give an answer. All the funders which stated that the relative weights differ between programmes, with only one exception, state that they inform their reviewers accordingly. (In the one exception, the funder does not give an answer to the second question, and states that specific weights of individual criteria are only set in certain specialist programmes.)

Figure S 6: Question 13 “Does your organisation give any indication to its reviewers and/or granting committees about how to weigh the various criteria they are asked to consider?”, 15 “Do the relative weights of individual criteria differ between different funding lines or funding programmes of your organisation?”, and 16 conditional on a positive answer to 15: “Are these programme-dependent differing weights of criteria explicitly communicated to the concerned reviewers and/or granting committees?”. n=48

S 1.2.3 Measures to limit the reliance on quantitative proxies (q 17 and 18)

With a view to the commitments of CoARA, within which the survey originated, two questions were included which addressed measures taken by the responding organisations to limit the reliance on quantitative proxies in the assessment of the expertise of the applicant or research team (question 17) and to support or encourage a primarily qualitative assessment (i.e. an assessment based on contents rather than quantitative proxies) of research proposals (question 18). Unsurprisingly, given that the survey was conducted within a CoARA working group, the clear majority of respondents stated they already employ measures to limit the reliance on quantitative proxies (33 organisations, 26 out of 35 funders), while only 11 respondents (8 out of 35 funders) stated that they do not employ such measures. 4 do not give answers.

Note that the WG does not take the consideration of proxies in research assessment to be objectionable per se. It recognizes that in some settings, direct modes of assessment are impractical or even impossible. For instance, if the objective is to estimate the future success of a planned project, this can only be done indirectly - i.e. by proxy. The WG only emphasizes two relevant points. Firstly: when a qualitative mode of research assessment is practicable, this mode is to be preferred to modes which proceed indirectly, i.e. via the consideration of proxies. Secondly: there are particular dangers in the use of quantitative proxies which (by their nature) abstract from qualitative contents (of manuscripts, articles, findings), and these dangers are especially pronounced in the assessment of the research output or expertise of an individual researcher. In these commitments, the Working Group sees itself in alignment with CoARA as a whole. When it looks, in the following, at funders' measures to limit their reliance on quantitative data, it does so in the light of these commitments.

The **measures to limit the reliance on quantitative data** (question 17, text field) and **further measures to support or encourage a primarily qualitative assessment** (question 18, text field) bear studying in some detail. They can be grouped under 6 headings:

- A number of organisations (notably funders) mention **written or oral appeals and reminders to reviewers and relevant moderation techniques in review sessions** highlighting qualitative aspects of a researcher’s achievements and/or discouraging or disallowing mention of certain quantitative metrics, such as Journal Impact Factor or h-index.
- A number of organisations (including funders, but also other organisations) mention **the introduction and use of narrative CV forms**, or CV forms with narrative elements, which provide fields for the explanation and discussion of past achievements and their relevance, and of biographical details potentially relevant to the evaluation of the applicant’s previous work record.
- Some funders report that they **limit the number of achievements, contributions or publications** which applicants may list in their applications.
- Some funders report that they **require applicants to give certain full-text, qualitative information** of their cited publications or of previous or preliminary work leading up to the application at hand, or of their previous achievements.
- Some funders **invite reviewers to read** an applicant’s main publications.

Some organisations make appointment or scholarship decisions based, in part, on **open ended interviews and/or tests or work samples**.

Figure S 7: Questions 17 “Does your organisation employ measures to limit the reliance on quantitative proxies in the assessment of the expertise of the applicant or research team (e.g. number of publications, h-index, Journal Impact Factors etc.)” and 18 “Does your organisation employ (further) measures to support or encourage a primarily qualitative assessment (i.e. an assessment based on contents rather than quantitative proxies) of research proposals?”. n=48

S 1.3 Further detailed results of the survey

S 1.3.1 Survey questions

Part 1: General information

1. Please state the name of your organisation

[Free text]

2. Please state the type of your organisation

[Single choice: Universities, and their associations; Research centres, research infrastructures, and their associations; Academies, learned societies, and their associations, and associations of researchers; Public or private research funding organisations and their associations; National/regional authorities or agencies that implement some form of research assessment and their associations; Other relevant not-for-profit organisations involved with research assessment, and their associations]

Part 2: Understanding and operationalisation of research quality

3. When communicating with potential applicants, reviewers, or the public, my organisation explicitly mentions ...:

	Yes, always	Yes, sometimes depending on the context	No	No answer
... "(high) research quality" or "(high) scientific quality" as a funding criterion				
... "research excellence" or "scientific excellence" as a funding criterion				

4. Does your organisation operate with a formal definition of "research/scientific quality" or "research /scientific excellence"?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free text comment]

5. [If yes in previous question] How does your organisation define "research/scientific quality" resp. "scientific/research excellence"? Feel free to either type or copy/paste your definition here, or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.

[Free text]

6. [If yes in q4] Do the funding criteria refer to this definition of "research/scientific quality" resp. "research/scientific excellence"?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free text comment]

7. How important are each of the following aspects in your organisation's understanding of research quality resp. research excellence in the assessment of research proposals? (Note: if you would like to comment on any of the listed aspects, you can do so under the next question.)

[Matrix: very important - moderately important - less important - not important at all - no answer]

- Novelty or originality of scientific question
- Novelty or originality of approach or method(s) to be used
- Clarity of scientific question and proposed approach or methods(s)
- Methodological or theoretical rigour of the proposal
- Feasibility of the proposed project
- Quality and/or relevance of preliminary work
- Expected academic significance or impact (i.e. expected contribution to the development of the field in question)
- Expected non-academic (e.g. social, economic, defence etc.) significance or impact
- Consideration of the current state-of-the-art
- Consideration of ethical aspects of the proposed project (if relevant)
- Consideration of sex or gender in the context of the research question or proposed methods (if relevant)
- Approach to risk (of project failure)
- Appropriateness of the publication or dissemination strategy of the proposed project
- Collaboration with other researchers on a national level
- Collaboration with other researchers on an international level
- Interdisciplinarity
- Design, degree of elaboration and/or appropriateness of data management plan
- Adherence to Open Science principles
- International visibility of the proposed project

8. Would you like to leave a comment on any of the aspects listed in the previous question? Or are there any additional aspects or dimensions that your organisation considers important in terms of research quality resp. research excellence?

[Free text]

9. Please indicate whether your organisation considers any of the following criteria when making funding decisions. (Note, if you would like to comment on any of the listed criteria, you can do so under the next question.)

[Matrix: As part of the criterion "research excellence/quality", as a separate criterion, as a criterion but unsure whether as part of "research excellence/quality" or as a separate criterion, not considered as funding criterion, no answer]

- Expertise / qualification of the applicant (and, if applicable, of members of research team) in relation to the project
- Past scientific performance of the applicant (and, if applicable, of members of the research team)
- Quantitative indicators regarding applicant or team (e.g. numbers of publications, h-index, Journal Impact Factors, number an amount of third-party funds raised, number of patents, position in rankings, ...)

- Team composition (equity, diversity, inclusion, others) and division of responsibilities
- Measures planned by applicant or proposed host institution to foster research careers
- Research environment such as availability and accessibility of personnel, facilities and infrastructures
- Risk analysis
- Dual-use concerns
- Inclusion of non-academic stakeholders
- Implementation: clear and realistic project plan (in relation to project objectives and available resources)
- Ecological Sustainability
- Sustainability dimensions other than ecological sustainability (e.g. contribution to non-ecological Sustainable Development Goals)
- Potential non-academic (e.g. social, economic, defence, etc.) significance, relevance, or impact
- Regional balance / regional allocation of funds
- Public outreach / science communication
- Citizen science / participation
- Open Access / Open Science

10. Would you like to leave a comment on any of the aspects listed in the previous question? Or are there any other funding criteria missing?

[Free text]

11. Is your organisation considering the review of any of the criteria listed above, or the introduction of new criteria?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

12. [If yes in previous question] Please briefly describe the changes envisioned.

[Free text]

13. Does your organisation give any indication to its reviewers and/or granting committees about how to weigh the various criteria they are asked to consider?

[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]

14. [If yes, always or yes, depending in previous question] What indication regarding the weighing of criteria does your organisation give to its reviewers and/or granting committees?

[Free text]

15. Do the relative weights of individual criteria differ between different funding lines or funding programmes of your organisation?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

16. [If yes in previous question] Are these programme-dependent differing weights of criteria explicitly communicated to the concerned reviewers and/or granting committees?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

17. Does your organisation employ measures to limit the reliance on quantitative proxies in the assessment of the expertise of the applicant or research team (e.g. number of publications, h-index, Journal Impact Factors etc.)?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

18. Does your organisation employ (further) measures to support or encourage a primarily qualitative assessment (i.e. an assessment based on contents rather than quantitative proxies) of research proposals?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

The survey contained 25 further questions which are not copied here, as they were intended for consideration by WP 2 (see S 2.3).

S 1.3.2 List of organisations that provided answers to the survey

<i>Name of organisation</i>	<i>Type of organisation</i>	<i>Country/Region</i>
National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET)	Research centres, research infrastructures, and their associations	Argentina
Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Austria
Christian Doppler Forschungsgesellschaft	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Austria
F.R.S.-FNRS	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Belgium
Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Belgium
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Canada
Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Denmark
Independent Research Fund Denmark (IRFD)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Denmark
Lundbeck Foundation	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Denmark
Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Estonia
European Commission	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Europe
European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (EURODOC)	Academies, learned societies, and their associations, and associations of researchers	Europe
Science Europe	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Europe
Universities of Applied Sciences for Europe (UAS4EUROPE)	Universities, and their associations	Europe
Research Council of Finland	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Finland
Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	France
ANRS Emerging infectious diseases (ANRS MIE)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	France
French National Cancer Institute (INCa)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	France
Paris Institute of Digital Technology (ISEP)	Universities, and their associations	France
Université Côte d'Azur (UniCA)	Universities, and their associations	France
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft - German Research Foundation (DFG)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Germany
DORA, San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment	Other relevant not-for-profit organisations involved with research assessment, and their associations	Global
Global Young Academy (GYA)	Academies, learned societies, and their associations, and associations of researchers	Global

Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA)	Academies, learned societies, and their associations, and associations of researchers	Hungary
Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Research centres, research infrastructures, and their associations	Hungary
Icelandic Centre for Research (Rannis)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Iceland
Health Research Board (HRB)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Ireland
Italian National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes (ANVUR)	National/regional authorities or agencies that implement some form of research assessment, and their associations	Italy
Università di Pisa (UNIFI)	Universities, and their associations	Italy
University of Florence (UNIFI)	Universities, and their associations	Italy
Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Luxembourg
Ministry of Business Innovation and Employment (MBIE)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	New Zealand
Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Norway
Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Poland
National Science Centre	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Poland
Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Portugal
Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Romania
Aragonese Foundation for Research & Development (ARAID Foundation)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Spain
State Research Agency (AEI)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Spain
Universidad San Pablo CEU	Universities, and their associations	Spain
Knowledge Foundation / Stiftelsen för kunskaps och kompetens (KK-stiftelsen)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Sweden
Swedish Governmental Agency for Innovation Systems (VINNOVA)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Sweden
Swedish research council for health, working life and welfare (FORTE)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Sweden
Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Switzerland
Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TUBITAK)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Turkey
National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Public or private RFO, and their associations	Ukraine
UK Research & Innovation (UKRI)	Public or private RFO and their associations	United Kingdom
Wellcome Trust	Public or private RFO, and their associations	United Kingdom

Survey 2. Selection of reviewers and panel composition (survey result)

S 2.1 Guiding principles for the selection of reviewers and panel composition that support quality and diversity of selected projects (q 19)

The survey results indicate that most of the respondents (40 out of 48; or 83%) apply guiding principles for appointing assessment panel and peer reviewers (fig. S 8).

Figure S 8: Question 19 “Does your organisation apply guiding principles for appointing assessment panel/peer reviewers?”. n=48

The nature of those guiding principles and how they are applied are instrument dependent, in that respect that it may depend on the programme, the criteria in focus or the scope of the funding organisation. The guiding principles may be different also for different funding programmes or calls within the same organisation.

Principles for selection of peer reviewer also depend on the role of a specific panel or an individual peer reviewer. Funders may employ individual international peer reviewers (often remote) or panels of international composition for the sole purpose of assessing the scientific quality of the proposed project. The written assessment from the international peer reviewers serves as critical documentation for the standing panel designated for the more generic criteria, such as implementation and overall assessment of the same project proposal. A practical reason for this two-step assessment approach is that the panel members may prefer to use their first language during in-depth discussions. A national panel may also be required to evaluate the applications in a specific national context or local knowledge.

Other organisations may use a one-step approach with a single panel of both national and international experts, and a mix of research discipline specialists and academic generalists which are assessing the full proposals. From the survey result it was not possible to distinguish between the respondents using separate panels (two step approach), and those respondents using single (one step) panels.

Funders may apply regular replacing of the panel members to avoid extended use of the same panels or reviewers. Others prefer to balance their panels with new and experienced members to keep some of the experience continuity within the group, and at the same time also providing it with some “fresh eyes”.

S 2.1.1 Identity transparency between reviewers and panels (q 22)

Survey results show that the identities of the panel members in most cases are shared with applicants and are sometimes accessible on the funders website. 17 out of 48 respondents - 35% - answered "Yes, always" and 16 out of 48 respondents, or 33% - answered "Yes, depending on the context" (fig. S 9).

Figure S 9: Question 22 "Are the identities of assessment panel members known to applicants?". n=48

Making the reviewers' identities available increases the transparency of the process and offers the opportunity to identify and avoid biases or conflicts of interest. Some funders also apply double open system where the identity of both the applicants and reviewers is shared.

As regards the methods used to identify suitable reviewers, different approaches are applied depending on the programme or instrument. The methods range from the use of internal or external databases to using services that support identifying reviewers with the right expertise. Different (disciplinary) divisions within the same organisation may not work in uniform ways. Often the suggested peer or panels needs to be validated by a governing board, scientific council or the current panel chair.

In practice, various methods are used to identify suitable reviewers. The following table lists some of the most relevant methods in use.

Methods for identifying suitable reviewers
<p><u>Open call for reviewers</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts express their interest in acting as a reviewer through an online form • The research community (i.e., universities, scientific societies, governments and companies) can also submit, nominate candidates for reviewer
<p><u>Internal databases</u></p> <p>Some organisations do also keep a record of past reviewers' performance. The use of databases or other record of peer and panel members make it easier to monitor and balance diversity.</p>
<p>External databases/Manual reviewer identification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Databases of researchers such as https://brainmap.ro • Bibliographic databases such as Dimensions, Scopus, Web of Science (paid services), internet and bibliographic searches Google Scholar, PubMed Research Gate, ORCID (free services)

Reviewer finding services

Commercial actors (like Dimensions Reviewer Finder, Prophy and formerly Elsevier Expert Lookup may provide reviewer finding services. They generate a list of relevant experts based on semantic and bibliographic information, and can be used to check CoIs related to co-publication. However, care should be taken that the generated matches are properly validated by trained scientific staff and also on needs to be aware that these tools are suggesting matches based on nr of matched publications and use quantitative indicators (e.g., H-index); these do not take into account e.g., peer review experience of the reviewers).

Proposal of reviewers by peers

Reviewers can be proposed by peers such as other experts or researchers (Health Research Board, DFG, Lundbeck Foundation)

Proposal of reviewers by the applicants themselves

Reviewers can be proposed by the applicants themselves. However, a study¹⁷ conducted by the Swiss National Science Foundation found out that that reviewers nominated by applicants were more likely to give these applicants higher evaluation scores. Even if the named reviewer is not engaged by the organisation, it may help to identify the relevant research area to start the search from.

Review by other applicants (experiment)

Under Distributed Peer Review, currently being experimented by the Volkswagen Foundation, applicants for funding review each other's proposals.

Internal decision support systems

Some organisations do have in-house decision support systems that:

- Provide a dynamic list of potential reviewers from which the most appropriate reviewers will be selected;
- Check the validity of the reviewers' pools against the various criteria that needs to be met (e.g. gender, geographical balance, etc.).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools

Some funders have developed their own algorithms to match individual proposals to reviewers in their own database based on machine reading and analysis of the proposal text on the one hand, and data on the publications of potential reviewers from abstract and citation databases on the other hand (Titles, Keywords, Abstracts, Journal titles Subject areas and Publication years). However, analysis based on machine learning may reproduce known biases in the system

S 2.2 Practices in relation to mentoring and training of reviewers on responsible assessment (q 23, q 31 and q 32)

Guidance and training to reviewers are provided as support throughout the different steps of the evaluation process. The majority of the survey respondents early in the assessment process (30 out of 48, or 63%) provide guiding, support or training sessions for assessment

¹⁷ Severin A, Martins J, Heyard R, et al Gender and other potential biases in peer review: cross sectional analysis of 38 250 external peer review reports BMJ Open 2020;10:e035058. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2019-035058

panels, which depends on the assessment approach or the step in the assessment process (fig. S 10). Most of the respondents (36 out of 48, or 75%) also provide guidance in the form of written instructions to external (non-panel) reviewers (fig. S 11).

More than half of the respondents (30 out of 48, or 63%). stated that the instructions to external reviewers are made available to applicants (fig. S 12).

Figure S 10: Question 23 (“Does your organisation provide guiding or training sessions for assessment panels on how to apply criteria, balance perspectives/aspects, etc.?”) n=48

Figure S 11: Question 31 (“Does your organisation provide written instructions for external (non-panel) reviewers?”) n=48

Figure S 12: Question 32 (“Are the instructions for external reviewers also known to the applicants?”) n=48

S 2.2.1 Rules on conflict of interest (q 25, q 27 and q 29)

Absence of conflict of interest or biases is a fundamental core aspect in assessment process. From the survey results, most of the respondents (41 out of 48, or 85%) apply rules or principles concerning reviewers and bias and/or conflict of interest (fig. S 13). Before joining a panel, the potential member can be asked to declare in writing their impartiality, confidentiality, and competence in the domain, subdomain, and the research area. There are however different practices in place if the potential biases are to be assured or guaranteed by the individual panel member or an investigation task for the RFO staff, or both.

Many organisations, also have routines for handling sudden unexpected bias among reviewers that may appear when the assessment activities already have started (33 out of 48, or 69% (fig. S 14). This may also include routines to handle unexpected situations such as reviewers deviating from rules of conduct during panel meetings or during the assessment process (28 out of 48, or 58%) (fig. S 15).

Figure S 13: Question 25 “Does your organisation apply any rules/regulations/principles concerning reviewers and bias/conflicts of interest?”. n=48

Figure S 14: Question 27 “Does your organisation have routines to handle sudden unexpected biases among reviewers (including in panels, e.g. a panel reviewer disclosing a conflict of interest during a review meeting)?”. n=48

Figure S 15: Question 29 “Does your organisation have routines to handle unexpected situations such as reviewers deviating from rules of conduct (or similar inappropriate behaviour) during panel meetings or during assessment processes?”. n=48

S 2.2.2 Feedback between reviewers and applicants (q 34, q 36, and q 41)

The majority of the surveyed organisations (35 out of 48, or 73%) provide feedback to the applicants. Additional 7 of the organisations (15%) give feedback depending on the context, which amount a total of 42 or 88% (fig. S 16). The feedback should emanate from the panel discussion, however, is sometimes written at least in part by the office administrator. 33% (or 16) of the feedback is produced by the reviewers. In 21% (or 10) of the organisations the feedback is provided by the administrator and in 23% (11) of the cases by both (fig.S 17).

Finally, the majority of the surveyed organisations (37 out of 48, or 77%) in most cases request feedback from their reviewers on the assessment process (fig. S 18). However, it requires some routines in place for systematically handling of the information in order for constructive change to be implemented in a structured way.

Figure S 16: Question 34 “Do the applicants get feedback on their applications?”. n=48

Figure S 17: Question 36 “Who or which unit produces this feedback to the applicants?”. n=48

Figure S 18: Question 41 “Are the assessment panel / peer reviewers asked to give feedback to the funder on the assessment procedure?”. n=48

S 2.2.3 Recognition and reward of peer review (q 39)

The majority of surveyed organisations (31 out of 48, or 65%) provide some form of recognition for peer review efforts (fig. S 19). The forms of recognition and reward mentioned may include: remunerations paid to the reviewer, thank-you-letters, Confirmation letter/certificate, list of reviewers available on the RFO website.

Figure S 19: Question 39 “Does your organisation show any recognition of review / panel efforts such as credits honoraries, etc?”. n=48

S 2.3 Further Survey Results

Figures 20-24 show further survey results that are not further discussed elsewhere.

Figure S 20: Question 37 “Does your organisation have rebuttal procedures in place (i.e. applicant can respond to review feedback before the final decision)?”. n=48

Figure S 21: Question 38 “Does your organisation have (other) procedures regarding applicant complaints in place?”. n=48

Figure S 22: Question 43 “Does your organisation transparently share the steps of the assessment procedure (from application to approval/denial) to the applicants on the web or similar?”. n=48

Figure S 23: Question 44 (“Is your organisation considering any changes to their current practices regarding the selection and training of reviewers?”. n=48

Figure S 24: Question 46 “Has your organisation collected evidence about the positive (or negative) impact of any of the practices for the selection and training of reviewers as covered above?”. n=48

S 2.4 Survey Questionnaire

WP1 and WP2 conducted a joint survey. A list of organisations that responded to the survey can be found in annex S 1.3.2.

Parts 1 and 2 of this survey are covered by WP1 in annex S 1. Part 3 of this survey, starting with question 19, addresses topics relating to WP2:

Part 3: Practices in selecting and guiding reviewers

19. Does your organisation apply guiding principles for appointing assessment panel/peer reviewers?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

20. [Logic: If yes in previous question] What guiding principles does your organisation apply for appointing assessment panel / peer reviewers? Feel free to either type or copy/paste the principles here, or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.

[Free text]

21. What concrete methods does your organisation employ to identify suitable peer reviewers?

[Free text]

22. Are the identities of assessment panel members known to applicants?

[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]

23. Does your organisation provide guiding or trainings sessions for assessment panels on how to apply criteria, balance perspective/aspects, etc.?

[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]

24. [Logic: If yes, always or yes, depending in previous question] Please briefly describe the guiding or training sessions or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.

[Free text]

25. Does your organisation apply any rules/regulations/principles concerning reviewers and bias/conflicts of interest?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

26. [Logic: If yes in previous question] Please briefly describe these rules/regulations/principles, or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.

[Free text]

27. Does your organisation have routines to handle sudden unexpected biases among reviewers (including in panels, e.g. a panel reviewer disclosing a conflict of interest during a review meeting)?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

28. [Logic: If yes in previous question] Please briefly describe these routines.

[Free text]

- 29. Does your organisation have routines to handle unexpected situations such as reviewers deviating from rules of conduct (or similar inappropriate behavior) during panel meetings or during the assessment process?**
[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]
- 30. [Logic: If yes in previous question] Please briefly describe these routines.**
[Free text]
- 31. Does your organisation provide written instructions for external (non-panel) reviewers?**
[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]
- 32. [Logic: if yes, always or yes, depending in question 31] Are these instructions known to the applicants?**
[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]
- 33. [Logic: if yes, always or yes, depending in question 31] Please briefly describe these written instructions or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.**
[Free text]
- 34. Do the applicants get feedback on their applications?**
[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]
- 35. [Logic: If yes, always or yes, depending in previous question no. 34] Please briefly indicate the nature of such feedback or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.**
[Free text]
- 36. [Logic: If yes, always or yes, depending in previous question no. 34] Who or which unit produces this feedback?**
[Single choice] the reviewer(s) / panelist(s) - the administrator(s) - both - other [text]]
- 37. [Logic: If yes, always or yes, depending in previous question no. 34] Does your organisation have rebuttal procedures in place? (I.e. applicant can respond to review feedback before the final decision)**
[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]
- 38. [Logic: If yes, always or yes, depending in previous question no. 34] Does your organisation have (other) procedures regarding applicant complaints in place?**
[Single choice: yes, such as [text] - no - no answer]
- 39. Does your organisation show any recognition of review/panel efforts such as credits, honoraries, etc?**
[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]
- 40. [Logic: If yes in previous question] Please indicate how the efforts are recognized or rewarded, or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.**

A decorative graphic in the top-left corner consisting of a grid of blue dots of varying sizes, forming a wavy, abstract shape.

[Free text]

41. Are the assessment panel/peer reviewers asked to give feedback to the funder on the assessment process?

[Single choice: yes, always - yes, depending on the context such as [text] - no - no answer]

42. [Logic: if yes, always or yes, depending in previous question] Please indicate how this feedback is processed, or paste a link if this information can be found in the public domain.

[Free text]

43. Does your organisation transparently share the steps of the assessment procedure (from application to approval/denial) to the applicants on the web or similar?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

44. Is your organisation considering any changes to their current practices regarding the selection and training of reviewers?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

45. [Logic: if yes in previous question] Please briefly describe the changes envisioned.

[Free text]

46. Has your organisation collected evidence about the positive (or negative) impact of any of the practices for the selection and training of reviewers as covered above?

[Single choice: yes - no - no answer + free comment]

47. [Logic: If yes in previous question] Please briefly describe the collected evidence about the positive (or negative) impact of any of the practices for the selection and training of reviewers as covered above.

[Free text]

Survey 3. The information requested from applicants

S 3.1 Introduction

Work Package (WP) 3 focused on information requested from applicants. It aimed at identifying good practices on how to balance qualitative and quantitative information requested from applicants and how to structure information (notably regarding their competences, earlier achievements and potential), while reflecting the diversity of outputs, tasks, practices, skills and competences, and without an extra burden to the applicants.

The main questions/issues underlying the reflections and output of the WP are:

- How to ask information on earlier achievements of applicants which allows consideration of a broader spectrum of types of contributions?
- How to request information on earlier achievements of applicants, while ensuring that reputation of journals, JIF, and other indicators are not used inappropriately during the evaluation?
- How to best balance quantitative and qualitative information requested from applicants?
- What is the minimum amount of information an applicant must provide in a proposal, that allows its assessment?

In order to collect relevant evidence a survey was developed by the Chairs and put into consultation with the Working Group. The survey was sent to WG members and selected stakeholders in February 2025 and responses were collected until the end of March 2025. A total of 26 responses were received, 25 from funders and 1 from a European university. All respondents are authorised staff of their respective organisations and have responded to the survey in light of their occupational experience. Annex S 3.2 provides a synthesis of the survey results.

Meetings were organised with WP3 contributors to present and discuss the findings of the survey. Additionally, a workshop took place online on 27 June 2025. The aim of the workshop was to solicit information and exchanges on good practices in relation to the following questions:

1. Is the way that information is requested currently (including narrative forms) an optimal way to implement ARRA's commitments 1 and 2? What is the existing evidence?
2. What quantitative information could/should funders ask for (if any), for what purpose, and how should it be used?

S 3.2 Survey findings

Funding type

The first question of the survey prompted respondents to state the types of projects they typically fund. The great majority (21) fund both single and multi-beneficiary projects, while five organisations fund exclusively single beneficiary projects.

Figure S 25: Question 1 “Does your organisation fund primarily:”

Information typically requested from applicants

The second question related to the information typically requested from applicants. Respondents were offered fourteen choices covering a wide gamut of information potentially requested. The results show that all organisations (26) request information in relation to the methodology, feasibility and objectives of the project. These are closely followed by information on the expected impact of the project, work plan, information about the participants’ competencies, earlier achievements and potential and ethical issues (23 responses). The innovative character of proposed projects was also frequently chosen (21), followed by information regarding other applications/projects (17) and project dissemination and communication activities (16).

Figure S 26: Question 2 “What information does your organisation typically request from applicants?”

How information is structured.

With regard to how information is structured, a great majority of organisations (18) responded that the information received is structured according to the assessment criteria. At the same time, 8 organisations contextualised their answers (choosing Other). The latter responses referred to the fact that for example some of the information requested were not part of the assessment criteria (e.g. ethical or legal aspects).

Figure S 27: Question 3 “How is this information structured?”

Information on competences and earlier achievements, and potential

This question regarded to the types of information requested from applicants as regards their competencies, earlier achievements and potential. All organisations request information on scientific publications. Moreover, almost all of them request information on current and past positions held (25) and on education, training or the organisation of academic events. A good number (16) of organisations request information on teaching and mentoring, engagement in collaborative practices and leadership, management duties.

Figure S 28: Question 4a “What type of information is requested from the applicants on their competences, earlier achievements, and potential?”

A complementary question gave the opportunity to respondents to add whether they request research outputs other than publications. The question provided a number of examples for consideration: articles on preprint servers; non-peer-reviewed contributions to conferences; blog contributions; data sets; software and algorithms; protocols (e.g. of clinical trials); standards patents; infrastructural components, collection of samples.

The majority of organisations (16) reported that they either ask for research outputs other than peer-reviewed publications directly or leave it to applicants to provide such references. The consideration of outputs such as data sets, pre-prints, patents, protocols, non-peer reviewed publications, contributions to conferences were mentioned by several respondents. In general, the answers to question 4b showed a high degree of openness to a more diverse set of research outputs.

Information on competences, earlier achievements and potential. How is it requested?

It was also asked in what form information on competences, earlier achievements, and potential are requested. Results show that organisations request information in different ways. Fifteen reported that they use lists with a limited number of outputs. Standard and hybrid CVs were used by thirteen organisations, while narrative CVs by eleven. In relation to question 5b, only three answers from funders mentioned use of metrics. All three use citation metrics, while the H-index is mentioned twice, and the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) once.

Figure S 29: Question 5 ". In what form is the information on competences, earlier achievements and potential requested?"

Information template

Regarding to the use of an information template to collect information, responses show that a strong majority (22) provide a specific template for the required information. Only four organisations leave the choice of the template up to the applicants.

Figure S 30: Question 6 "For any of the cases above, does your organisation require that the information is presented according to a template provided by"

Multiple choice questions were complemented by a number of free text questions. Respondents were asked to report on whether they indicate any limit on the quality (understood in the context of the question in relation to metrics) or the number of contributions (e.g. publications) by applicants. The answers show a mixed landscape in terms of practices. A good number of respondents (11) replied positively and pointed to the fact that they limit the number of publications that can be listed (often this is maximum ten publications). At the same time, nine respondents said that they do not utilise such limits. A few answers referred to the fact that on some occasions the number of publications requested operates as a minimum or a threshold.

Moreover, another free-text question focused on the ways information collected (on the competences, earlier achievements and potential of the applicants) is used in the assessment of the proposal's merits. Respondents reported that information is collected through application forms or CV templates provided (standard, hybrid, or narrative) with a view to assessing the feasibility of the proposed research. In this vein, the competencies, earlier achievements, and potential of the applicants are used to support the merit assessment of the applicants. As also reported in the previous question, there is often a limit on how many achievements applications can indicate.¹⁸

Interviews to clarify proposal

In relation to the use of interviews to clarify aspects of the proposal, a strong majority (19) reported that this may take place depending on the programmes or calls. Six organisations stated that they never use interviews.

Figure S 31: Question 10 "Do you also make use of interviews or other mechanisms allowing the applicant(s) to clarify aspects of their proposal at the request of the panel?"

The survey also aimed at better understanding the changes implemented by organisations in the last years, in relation to the reform of research assessment. It equally aimed to solicit evidence concerning uptake and impact.

Several organisations reported implementing changes to improve research proposal assessment practices; four organisations did not fill in the question and another two reported no significant changes. The changes often focus on revising the way information is requested from applicants and refining the evaluation processes.

Key areas of change include:

Adoption of Narrative or Hybrid CVs. Ten organisations have adopted narrative or hybrid CVs. The goals for this shift include providing a more rounded view of the applicant, simplifying the evaluation process, making evaluation more effective, emphasizing the impact and contribution of the applicant's work, aligning applications with specific funding

¹⁸ Answers to question 9 ('If possible provide a weblink to the template/instructions used to collect the information from applicants (free text)') were not reported in this guide.

A decorative graphic in the top-left corner consisting of a dense pattern of blue dots of varying sizes, arranged in a roughly circular shape that tapers towards the top-left corner.

goals, and allowing researchers to highlight experiences and results relevant to particular funding opportunities. The structure of these new CVs varies but can include sections such as education, positions, career breaks, project management experience, a list of scientific contributions (sometimes limited to a set number of important outputs), and a narrative summary of importance and impact. Evidence concerning the uptake and impact of narrative CVs is being monitored by a small number of organisations with some preliminary findings tentatively suggesting favourable reception (though others report that further rounds of evaluation would be needed in order to draw concrete conclusions).

Emphasis on impact and non-traditional outputs. A small number of organisations (three) report that they effected changes in order to put greater emphasis on impact (asking applicants to describe research outcomes and roadmaps to impact). In this regard, one organisation reported that they started soliciting information concerning collaboration with actors outside academia and the relevance of research to the Sustainable Development Goals. Similarly, other funding organisations mention that they have started putting more emphasis on sustainability and societal issues (and developed relevant funding streams) or that applicants are required to address any relevant sex-specific and/or gender related aspects inherent in research questions and/or research design.

Incorporating principles of Responsible Research Assessment. Whether prior or subsequent to joining CoARA, several organisations have implemented changes which contribute to attaining its goals (or which are in alignment with DORA principles). This includes adopting hybrid or narrative CVs, shifting away from the use of quantitative indicators (like the H-index) etc.

Considering Career Breaks and Personal Circumstances. Three organisations report that they have put changes in place in order to allow justified, documentable career breaks to be taken into consideration when assessing applicant eligibility or career paths (the reasons for non-linear career paths can include maternity / paternity or adoptive leave, parental leave, caregiving obligations, health issues, military or civilian service, asylum seeking etc).

Revising evaluation processes and criteria. Changes implemented include modifying evaluation criteria to align with the information collected via narrative CVs, limiting bibliographical references and asking for context for more relevant outputs (also discussing their impact), introducing interviews as part of the evaluation process so as to nuance the proposed research, requiring institutions to create research data management strategies, introducing criteria for open science as part of the evaluation process.

How do such changes align with CoARA goals?

Key changes being considered include: the adoption of narrative CVs; the implementation of open access and rights retention strategies in order to lower costs for researchers; re-examining the types of research outputs applicants can enter in order to allow more flexibility; including sustainability aspects in proposals (in a way similar to ethical aspects); extending the range of recognised research practices (e.g. open science practices, service to the scientific community, industrial research experience); improving guidelines for

applicants and evaluators after the introduction of new CV formats (also through the development of explanatory videos).

It is worth noting that while a good number of changes have been implemented or are being planned, for some organisations the impact and uptake of recently introduced changes are still being monitored. Improving assessment processes by reflecting on lessons learned from changes in funding calls is referenced as important by some funders.

A key element in CoARA is qualitative evaluation of research. Respondents were asked to comment on what is currently missing (e.g. tools, guidance, etc.) so that the information requested would enable a (more) qualitative assessment and recognition of (more) diverse contributions. (18 answers were received).

The key elements considered missing or needed are:

More and Improved Guidance for Applicants and Reviewers. This includes additional guidance for applicants to effectively use narrative CVs and better instructions for reviewers to support the assessment of these types of CVs. Developing guidance documents on appropriate and inappropriate uses of quantitative indicators. Providing better structures in templates which would allow entering non-conventional research outputs. Appropriately considering diverse contributions (including training, mentoring etc. other than research) and assisting reviewers in acknowledging non-linear career pathways.

Fostering skills and competencies to perform qualitative assessment which is bias-free while addressing the fact that this can lead to heavier workloads for evaluation panels and individual evaluators/reviewers. Multiplying training and workshops on qualitative assessment in order to foster wider cultural change. A structured effort to increase the diversity (gender, career stage, geography) of evaluation panels.

Informing applicants about evaluation outcomes

Lastly, respondents were asked to report on how they inform applicants about evaluation outcomes. Responses show a mixed picture. Almost all organisations (24) provide panel comments or individual evaluation reports by panel members or other external evaluators. Thirteen organisations provide numerical scores for each of the proposal sections or evaluation criteria. Numerical scores for the whole application are communicated by nine organisations, while eight send recommendations on how to improve.

Figure S 32: Question 14 "How does your organisation inform applicants on the evaluation outcomes?"

S 3.3 Survey questionnaire

Please state the name of your organisation:

Please state the type of your organisation:

Research centres, research infrastructures, and their associations.

Academies, learned societies, and their associations, and associations of researchers.

Public or private research funding organisations and their associations.

National/regional authorities or agencies that implement some form of research assessment and their associations.

Universities, and their associations.

Other relevant not-for-profit organisations involved with research assessment, and their associations.

Q1. Does your organisation fund primarily:

Single beneficiary projects.

Multiple-beneficiaries projects.

Both

Q2. What information does your organisation typically request from applicants? (please select one or more options):

Objectives of the project

Methodology and feasibility of the project

Expected impacts of the project Innovative character of the project in relation to the state of the art.

Work plan

List of milestones

List of deliverables

Dissemination activities and communication plan Information about participants competences, earlier achievements, and potential

Detailed budget

Ethical issues

Support/recommendation letters

Supporting documentation Information on any other related applications or ongoing projects.

Q3a. How is this information structured:

In accordance to the assessment criteria.

Other.

Q3b. If other please specify (free text)

Q4a. What type of information is requested from the applicants on their competences, earlier achievements, and potential? (please select one or more options):

Education, training or other key qualifications.

Current and past positions held Information on career breaks, diverse career paths, and life events or special personal circumstances.

Scientific publications.

Funding track-record.

Indicators of peer recognition, such as prizes, awards, invitations or appointments to prominent bodies or academies.

Engagement in peer review.

Engagement in teaching and mentoring.

Engagement in collaborative practices, including intersectoral collaborations.

Leadership and management duties.

Organisation of academic events.

Q4b. Are research outputs other than publications requested? Free text. (For example: Articles on preprint servers; Non-peer-reviewed contributions to conferences; Blog contributions; Data sets; Software and algorithms; Protocols (e.g. of clinical trials); Standards patents; Infrastructural components, collection of samples etc.)

Q5a. In what form is the information on competences, earlier achievements and potential requested ? (please select one or more options):

Standard CVs.

Narrative CVs.

Hybrid CVs.

Lists, with no limit in number of outputs that can be listed.

Lists, with limited number of outputs that can be listed.

Metrics (if selected continues in 5b).

Other (Free text in 5c).

Q5b. Metrics (if selected):

H-index and other author metrics.

Journal Impact Factor of the publications listed and other journal impact measures.

Citation metrics.

News media mentions.

Site downloads or user reads.

Q5c. Other (Free Text).

Q6. For any of the cases above, does your organisation require that the information is presented according to a template provided by:

The funding body itself.

A reference institution, like in the case of national or regional standardized CV templates.

Current research information system (CRIS) of public or private nature.

None of the above, applicants can decide on the format themselves.

Q7. Does your organisation indicate any limit on the quality (e.g. in relation to metrics) or the number of contributions (e.g. publications) by applicants? (Either as an eligibility or evaluation criteria or as an indicative threshold of the expected level of competition in the call). [Free text]

Q8. *How is the information collected on the competences, earlier achievements and potential of the applicants used in the assessment of the proposal's merits? (free text)*

Q9. *If possible provide a weblink to the template/instructions used to collect the information from applicants. (free text)*

Q10. *Do you also make use of interviews or other mechanisms allowing the applicant(s) to clarify aspects of their proposal at the request of the panel?*

Systematically.

Depending on the programmes/calls.

Never.

Q11. *What changes have you implemented in the last years, and why? Do you have evidence concerning their uptake and impact? (you can provide weblinks to such evidence). (free text)*

Q12. *What changes do you plan to implement or envisage, and for what purpose? (free text)*

Q13. *What is currently missing (e.g. tools, guidance, etc.) so that the information requested from applicants enables a (more) qualitative assessment and recognition of (more) diverse contributions? (free text)*

Q14a. *How does your organisation inform applicants on the evaluation outcomes? Do you share with applicants (please select one or more options):*

Numerical scores for their whole application.

Numerical scores for each of the proposal sections or evaluation criteria.

Panel comments or individual evaluation reports by panel members or other external evaluators explaining the strengths and weaknesses of their application, including some degree of detail of how their input has been used to address the evaluation criteria.

Recommendations on how to improve potential future applications.

Other, please specify: [free text in 14b]

Q14b. *Other, please specify: [free text]*

Other initiatives and projects

DORA (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment) is a declaration which originated in 2012 at the Annual Meeting of the American Society for Cell Biology in San Francisco. It recognizes the need to improve the ways in which researchers and the outputs of scholarly research are evaluated. Over the years, DORA has become a worldwide initiative covering all scholarly disciplines and all key stakeholders including funders, publishers, professional societies, institutions, and researchers. Over 25,000 individuals and organisations have signed DORA. (See <https://sfdora.org/> for more information.)

DORA has recently released a [*Practical Guide for Responsible Research Assessment for Research Funding Organisations*](#) (in short: DORA Funders Guide). Readers of this document are advised to consider this publication, too.

NOR-CAM (Norway) is a flexible and holistic framework for recognition and rewards in academic research assessment. The framework was developed by a working group appointed by Universities Norway (UHR) and published in 2021. It proposes a matrix of areas of competences and research results and is conceived as a toolbox to fit the specific context of the research institution using it. The framework was designed specifically for academic assessment but can also represent a source of inspiration for research funders willing to explore the diversity of research results types. (See <https://www.uhr.no/en/news-from-uhr/nor-cam-a-toolbox-for-recognition-and-rewards-in-academic-careers.5780.aspx> for more information)

Rewards and Recognition (R&R, Netherlands) is a nationwide programme in the Netherlands that began with the publication of a position paper titled "Room for Everyone's Talent" in November 2019. Through this paper, Dutch knowledge institutions and research funding bodies set a course to revise the current system for recognising and rewarding academics, and to move towards valuing academic work from a broader perspective. This means less emphasis on the number of publications and more attention for performance in other core areas such as education, societal impact, leadership and, in the case of University Medical Centers, also patient care. (See <https://recognitionrewards.nl/> for more information)

The **Latin American Forum for Research Assessment** (Foro Latinoamericano sobre Evaluación Científica, FOLEC) is a forum across Latin America and the Caribbean for discussing the meanings, policies, and practices of scientific evaluation processes in the region. From an open, collaborative, and public domain perspective, it seeks to strengthen democratizing and sustainable approaches and models of science that are committed to addressing the issues facing our societies. (See <https://www.clacso.org/folec/> for more information)

The **Responsible Research Assessment Working Group** of the Global Research Council (GRC) was formed in 2021 in order to advance responsible research assessment. The GRC is a worldwide organisation of national academic funding organisations. The RRA working group comprises 25 members from 23 countries across the globe. The group's

membership includes representation from every region of the GRC, ensuring a worldwide perspective and outreach among global funders. As one of its main achievements, it published the “Dimensions of Responsible Research Assessment” paper, detailing 11 dimensions in which funders can become active. (See <https://globalresearchcouncil.org/about/responsible-research-assessment-working-group/> for more information.)

There are also **Working Groups on Research Culture and Open Science** in Science Europe. These WGs also regularly discuss research assessment and linked issues. (See <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-culture/working-group/> and <https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/working-group/> for more information)

The **Open and Universal Science Project (OPUS)**, funded by the EU Commission and running from 2022 to 2025, developed a Research Assessment Framework (RAF) to effectively evaluate the impact and quality of research while promoting the principles of Open Science. It offers a comprehensive array of interventions, indicators and metrics to facilitate researcher assessment in RPOs and RFOs, covering a wide range of activities undertaken by researchers extending beyond research-related endeavours. These activities are categorized into research, education, leadership, and valorisation, allowing organisations to tailor their assessment systems to their specific requirements. The framework encompasses two dimensions: a generic approach and a dedicated Open Science focus, ensuring the appropriate recognition and reward of both types of activities. (See <https://opusproject.eu> for more information.)

Literature on research assessment and reform activities

The following list contains literature that the working group considered inspiring and took into account in its discussions. The list is incomplete as it was neither within the scope of the working group to provide a literature review nor was it manageable given the time such a review would demand.

No	Document title	Year	Weblink	Organisation	Document type
Literature on research assessment in general					
1	Marras C (2011) European Peer Review Guide - Integrating Policies and Practices into Coherent Procedures. European Science Foundation,	2011	https://www.esf.org/fileadmin/user_upload/esf/European_Peer_Review_Guide_2011.pdf	ESF	Guidance
2	Pina DG, Hren D, Marušić A (2015) Peer Review Evaluation Process of Marie Curie Actions under EU's Seventh Framework Programme for Research. PLoS ONE 10(6): e0130753.	2015	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0130753		Research article
3	Ofir Z, Schwandt T, Duggan C, McLean R (2016) Research Quality Plus: A holistic approach to evaluating research	2016	http://hdl.handle.net/10625/56528	IDRC	Report
4	Lebel J, McLean R. A better measure of research from the global south. Nature. 2018 Jul;559(7712):23-26	2018	https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-05581-4		Article
5	Cancer Research UK (2018) Improving how we evaluate research: how we're implementing DORA	2018	https://news.cancerresearchuk.org/2018/02/20/improving-research-evaluation-dora/	Cancer Research UK	News
6	Technopolis. (2020). Science Europe Study on Research Assessment Practices. Zenodo	2020	https://zenodo.org/records/4915999	Technopolis for Science Europe	Report
7	Science Europe (2020) Recommendations on research assessment processes	2020	https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/3twjxm0/se-position-statement-research-assessment-processes.pdf	Science Europe	Recommendations
8	DORA (2020) Rethinking research assessment: Unintended cognitive and system biases	2020	https://sfdora.org/resource/rethinking-research-assessment-unintended-cognitive-and-systems-biases/	DORA	Guidance

9	Curry, S., de Rijcke, S., Hatch, A., Pillay, D., van der Weijden, I. and Wilsdon, J. (2020) The changing role of funders in responsible research assessment: progress, obstacles & the way ahead. RoRI Working Paper No. 3	2020	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13227914	RoRI	Working Paper
10	Hug SE, Aeschbach M (2020), Criteria for assessing grant applications: a systematic review. Palgrave Commun 6, 37.	2020	https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0412-9		Research article
11	University of Glasgow. Assessment and Feedback Resources Hub	2021	https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/learningandteaching/afresourceshub/	University of Glasgow	Guideline
12	Wellcome Trust (2021) Commitment to responsible research assessment: Wellcome and funded organisations	2021	https://wellcome.org/grant-funding/guidance/open-access-guidance/research-organisations-how-implement-responsible-and-fair-approaches-research	Wellcome Trust	Guidance
13	Woods HB, Wilsdon J (2021) Why draw lots? Funder motivations for using partial randomisation to allocate research grants. RoRI Working Paper No.7	2021	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17102495.v2	RoRI	Report
14	International Network of Research Management Societies - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework.	2021	https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1	INORMS	Guidance
15	David G Pina, Ivan Buljan, Darko Hren, Ana Marušić (2021) Meta-Research: A retrospective analysis of the peer review of more than 75,000 Marie Curie proposals between 2007 and 2018 eLife 10:e59338	2021	https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.59338		Research article
16	DORA (2022) Rethinking research assessment: Debiasing committee composition and deliberative processes	2022	https://sfdora.org/resource/rethinking-research-assessment-debiasing-committee-composition-and-deliberative-processes/	DORA	Guidance
17	DORA (2022) Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators	2022	https://sfdora.org/resource/balanced-broad-responsible-a-practical-guide-for-research-evaluators/	DORA	Guidance
18	Publications Office of the European Union (2022) Study on the proposal evaluation system for the EU R&I framework programme : final report.	2022	https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/16211	European Commission	Report

19	Jong, L., Franssen, T.P., and Pinfield, S. (2021) 'Excellence' in the Research Ecosystem: A Literature Review. RoRI Working Paper No. 5	2022	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.16669834.v2	RoRI	Review
20	Curry, S., Gadd, E., & Wilsdon, J. (2022). Harnessing the Metric Tide: indicators, infrastructures & priorities for UK responsible research assessment. (Version 2)	2022	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21701624.v2	RoRI	Review
21	Forsberg E, Geschwind L, Levander S, Wermke W (2022) Peer review in an Era of Evaluation. Understanding the Practice of Gatekeeping in Academia. Springer Link	2022	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75263-7		Book
22	Heyard, R., Ott, M., Salanti, G., & Egger, M. (2022). Rethinking the Funding Line at the Swiss National Science Foundation: Bayesian Ranking and Lottery. Statistics and Public Policy, 9(1), 110-121.	2022	https://doi.org/10.1080/02330443X.2022.2086190	SNSF	Research article
23	Hren D, Pina DG, Norman CR, Marušić A (2022) What makes or breaks competitive research proposals? A mixed-methods analysis of research grant evaluation reports, Journal of Informetrics 16(2), 101289	2022	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2022.101289		Research article
24	Andreas Kjær Stage, Ea Høg Utoft (2023) Fun and less fun funding: the experiential affordances of research grant conditions, Science and Public Policy 50(6), 1091-1102	2023	https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad047	Danish Villum Foundation	Research article
25	Bendiscioli, S., Firpo, T., Bravo-Biosca, A., Czibor, E., Garfinkel, M., Stafford, T., Wilsdon, J., Woods, H. B., & Balling, G. V. (2022). The experimental research funder's handbook (2nd edition, ISBN 978-1-7397102-0-0) (Version 5). Research on Research Institute.	2023	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.19459328.v5	RoRI	Report
26	Kolarz P, Vingre A, Vinnik A, Neto A, Vergara C, Obando Rodriguez C, Nielsen K, Sutinen L (2023) Review of Peer Review - Final report	2023	https://www.ukri.org/publications/review-of-peer-review/	Technopolis for UKRI	Report
27	ACOLA (2023), Research Assessment in Australia: Evidence for Modernisation. A report to the Office of the Chief Scientist, Australian Government, Canberra.	2023	https://acola.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/ACOLA_ResearchAssessment_FINAL.pdf	ACOLA	Report

28	OPUS Research Assessment Framework - Deliverable 3.1 Indicators and Metrics to Test in the Pilots	2023	https://opusproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/OPUS_D3.1_IndicatorsMetrics_FINAL_PUBLIC.pdf	OPUS	Project deliverable
29	NWO (2023) How does NWO implement DORA	2023	https://www.nwo.nl/en/dora	NWO	News
30	International Science Council (2023) The Case for the Reform of Scientific Publishing	2023	https://doi.org/10.24948/2023.14	ISC	Guidance
31	Leptin M (2024) Evaluation of research proposals: the why and what of the ERC's recent changes	2024	https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-02/Evaluation_of_research_proposals.pdf	ERC	Statement
32	Pedersen, D.B., Gensby, U., Hedegaard, J., Hansen, O. K., Theilgaard, J. B., & Bennike, K. B. (2025). Emerging Practices in Research Assessment: Cross-Case Analysis of 10 International Funders. Evidence Report produced for the EU Presidency High-Level Conference on Reforming Research Assessment (CeRRA). Aalborg University.	2025	https://www.cerra.aau.dk	Aalborg University	Report
33	Practical Guide for Responsible Research Assessment for Research Funding Organizations	2026	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18402271	DORA	Guidance
Chapter 2.4 Providing dedicated space in CVs for displaying a broader variety of research outputs, activities and career trajectories					
34	Narrative CV: Resources to help you write one	2021	https://rise.articulate.com/share/NyPk_PNIENdfRS5R5catqqiJzs3woS3Y-/	University of Glasgow	Course - Online workshop (25 minutes)
35	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) (2021) Narrative CV: Implementation and feedback results	2021	https://www.fnr.lu/narrative-cv-implementation-and-feedback-results/	FNR	Report
36	DORA (2021) Using Narrative CVs: Process optimization and bias mitigation	2021	https://sfdora.org/resource/using-narrative-cvs-process-optimization-and-bias-mitigation/	DORA	Guidance
37	University of Glasgow (2021) Narrative CVs: Supporting applicants and review panels to value the range of contributions to research	2021	https://osf.io/preprints/osf/4fmj7	University of Glasgow	Article
38	Strinzel M, Kaltenbrunner W, van der Weijden I, von Arx M, Hill M (2022) SciCV, the Swiss National Science Foundation's new CV format. bioRxiv 2022.03.16.484596	2022	https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.03.16.484596	SNSF	Research article

39	The Royal Society (2022) Résumé for Researchers	2022	https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/projects/research-culture/tools-for-support/resume-for-researchers/	Royal Society	Guidance and template
40	Bordignon F, Chaignon L, Egret D (2023) Promoting narrative CVs to improve research evaluation? A review of opinion pieces and experiments, Research Evaluation 32(2). 313-320	2023	https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvad013		Review
41	DFG (2024) Introduction of a Standardised CV Template - Interim Report After One Year	2024	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18314375	DFG	Report
42	Varga, J., & Kaltenbrunner, W. (2025). RoRI Insights: Implementing Narrative CVs - Five recommendations for Funders (Version 1)	2025	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28524755.v1	RoRI	Recommendations
Chapter 2.7 Consideration of sex, gender and diversity in the composition of research teams and in the scientific content of the projects to promote quality					
43	ANR (2019) Action plan for Gender Equality and Gender Mainstreaming 2020 - 2023	2019	https://anr.fr/fileadmin/documents/2020/PA-Genre-ANR-en.pdf	ANR	Action plan
44	Resources and examples of measures that research funding organisations can take to promote gender equality	2023	https://www.superaproject.eu/rfos-journey-map/	SUPERA project	Toolbox
45	NWO (2023) Inclusive assessment - Tools for Written assessment (factsheet)	2023	https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/NWO-handout-inclusive-assessment-tools-for-written-assessments.pdf	NWO	Guidance
46	NWO (2023) Inclusive assessment - Written assessment (tips)	2023	https://www.nwo.nl/en/written-assessment	NWO	Guidance
47	NWO (2023) Inclusive assessment - Tools for evaluation committee meetings (factsheet)	2023	https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/NWO-handout-inclusive-assessment-tools-for-evaluation-committee-meetings.pdf	NWO	Guidance
48	NWO (2023) Inclusive assessment - Assessment committee meetings (tips)	2023	https://www.nwo.nl/en/assessment-committee-meetings	NWO	Guidance
49	Schiffbänker, H., Sauer, A., & Peterson, H. (2024). GRANteD D6.3 Reforming peer review practices - lessons learned from the implementation of gender equality policies in Research Funding Organisations	2024	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613191	GRANteD project	Project deliverable

Chapter 2.8 Incentivising open science practices

50	ORFG (2020) Incentivizing the sharing of research outputs through research assessment: a funder implementation blueprint	2020	https://www.orfg.org/projects-tools	ORFG	Action plan
----	--	------	---	------	-------------

51	Pietilä, M., Rintamäki, K., Aguilera, R., Fernández del Pino, B., Méndez, E., & Bautista-Puig, N. (2022). Open Science Assessment and Incentives at the YUFE Alliance. 26th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators (STI 2022), Granada, Spain.	2022	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6974766		Conference paper
----	---	------	---	--	------------------

Chapter 3.2 The selection of and guidance to reviewers

52	Seeber M, Vlegels J, Reimink E, Marušić A, Pina DG (2021) Does reviewing experience reduce disagreement in proposals evaluation? Insights from Marie Skłodowska-Curie and COST Actions. Research Evaluation 30(3). 349-360	2021	https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvab011		Research article
----	--	------	---	--	------------------

53	Hesselberg J-O, Dalsbø TK, Stromme H, Svege I, Fretheim A (2023) Reviewer training for improving grant and journal peer review. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews 11. MR000056	2023	https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.MR000056.pub2	Cochrane Database	Review
----	--	------	---	-------------------	--------

Chapter 3.4.5 Concluding the discussion(s): Coming to a funding decision

54	Buljan I, Pina DG, Mijatović A and Marušić A (2023) Are numerical scores important for grant assessment? A cross-sectional study. F1000Research 2024, 12:1216	2024	https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.139743.2	European Commission	Research article
----	---	------	---	---------------------	------------------